

Supporting Information

Migrative Carbofluorination of Saturated Amides Enabled by Pd-based Dyotropic Rearrangement

Guoqiang Yang,¹ Hua Wu,^{1,2} Simone Gallarati,³ Clémence Corminboeuf,³ Qian Wang,¹ Jieping Zhu^{1,*}

Affiliations:

1. Laboratory of Synthesis and Natural Products (LSPN), Institute of Chemical Sciences and Engineering, Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, EPFL-SB-ISIC-LSPN, BCH5304, CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland.
2. School of Pharmacy, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, 800 Dongchuan Road, Shanghai 200240, P. R. China.
3. Laboratory for Computational Molecular Design (LCMD), Institute of Chemical Sciences and Engineering, Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland

*Correspondence to: jieping.zhu@epfl.ch

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1. General Information

Reagents and solvents were purchased from commercial sources (Aldrich and Acros) and used without further purification. Flash column chromatography was performed using Silicycle P60 silica: 230-400 mesh (40-63 μm) silica. Reactions were monitored using Merck Kieselgel 60F254 aluminium plates. TLC was visualized by UV fluorescence (254 nm) then one of the following: KMnO_4 , phosphomolybdic acid, ninhydrin. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III-400, Bruker Avance-400 or Bruker DPX-400 spectrometer at room temperature. Chemical shifts (δ) were reported in parts per million (ppm) relative to residual solvent peaks rounded to the nearest 0.01 for proton and 0.1 for carbon (ref: CDCl_3 [^1H : 7.26, ^{13}C : 77.16], CD_2Cl_2 [^1H : 5.32, ^{13}C : 53.84], Acetone- d_6 [^1H : 2.05 ppm, ^{13}C : 29.8 ppm]). Coupling constants (J) were reported in Hz to the nearest 0.1 Hz. Peak multiplicity was indicated as follows s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), m (multiplet) and br (broad). Attribution of peaks was done using the multiplicities and integrals of the peaks. When needed, the COSY, HSQC and HMBC experiments were carried out to confirm the attribution. The accurate masses were measured by the mass spectrometry service of the EPFL by ESI-TOF using a QTOF Ultima from Waters. Optical rotations were obtained with a Jasco P-2000 polarimeter (589 nm). Melting points were measured using a Stuart SMP30. Enantiomeric excesses were determined with a Thar SFC Investigator system using chiral stationary columns by comparing the samples with the appropriate racemic samples. IR spectra were recorded in a Jasco FT/IR-4100 spectrometer outfitted with a PIKE technology MIRacleTM ATR accessory as neat films compressed onto a Zinc Selenide window, and were reported in cm^{-1} .

2. Preparation of Substrates

Scheme S1. General Procedure A

To a solution of the acid (1.0 equiv) in dichloromethane (0.5 M) was added dropwise SOCl_2 (1.5 equiv) followed by 3 drops of DMF at 0 $^\circ\text{C}$. The reaction mixture was stirred at rt for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated. The resulting acid chloride was redissolved in dichloromethane (0.3 M) and amine or N,O-dimethylhydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.1 equiv) and triethylamine (2.5 and 1.5 equiv, respectively) were added. The resulting mixture was stirred at rt overnight. Whereupon diluted with dichloromethane, it was washed twice with HCl (1 M), once with satd. NaHCO_3 solution, and once with brine. The organic extracts were dried (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated under reduced pressure. Flash chromatography on silica gel (hexanes:ethyl acetate 15:1) afforded the amides **1**, **S1** and **6**, respectively.

Scheme S2. General Procedure B^[1]

To a solution of diisopropylamine (4.0 equiv) in THF (1.0 M) at 0 °C was added dropwise a solution of *n*BuLi in hexane (2.5 M, 4.0 equiv). After stirring at 0 °C for 15 min, a solution of arylacetic acid (1.0 equiv) in THF (1.0 M) was added dropwise and the solution was stirred at this temperature for another 30 min. Iodomethane (6.0 equiv) was added and the solution was allowed to warm to rt slowly overnight. The mixture was acidified with aqueous HCl solution and extracted with ethyl acetate. The combined organic fractions were dried over anhydrous $MgSO_4$ and evaporated in vacuo. The crude product **S2** was used directly for the next step following the General Procedure A to afford amide **1**.

Scheme S3. General Procedure C

According to the reported methods,^[2] $LiHMDS$ (1.0 M in THF, 3.0 equiv) was added dropwise at 0 °C to a solution of the ester (1.0 equiv) in THF (1.0 M). The reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 30 minutes then MeI (3.0 equiv) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was stirred at rt for 1 h. A saturated aqueous solution of NH_4Cl was added. The aqueous phase was extracted with Et_2O (twice) and the combined organic layers were washed with brine, dried over $MgSO_4$ and concentrated in vacuo to give **S3**. The crude product was used directly for the next reaction.

To a solution of NaOH (5.0 equiv) in methanol (1.0 M) was added **S3** (1.0 equiv) and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux overnight (for *o*-substituted esters, reaction time was 48 h). The reaction mixture was cooled to rt and partially concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was diluted with water and extracted twice with ether. The aqueous layer was acidified until pH = 1 with HCl (3 M) and extracted twice with ethyl acetate. The combined organic extracts were dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure to afford **S2** which was used for the next step without further purification. Substrates **1** were prepared from **S2** following the General Procedure A.

Scheme S4. General Procedure D

According to the reported methods,^[3] to a cooled (0 °C) solution of α -substituted arylacetic acid (1.0 equiv) in THF (1.0 M) was slowly added LDA (1.0 M solution in THF, 2.4 equiv). The resulting mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to 0 °C and alkyl halide (3.0 equiv) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and stirred overnight. The mixture was quenched with dilute HCl (3 M) and extracted with ethyl acetate (twice). The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure to give α,α -disubstituted arylacetic acid which was used for the next step without further purification. Substrates **1** were prepared from **S1** following the General Procedure A.

Scheme S5. General Procedure E

According to a modified procedure reported by Hartwig group,^[4] to a Schlenk tube containing $\text{HBF}_4 \cdot \text{PtBu}_3$ (28.6 mg, 0.098 mmol, 0.04 equiv), $\text{Pd}(\text{dba})_2$ (28.3 mg, 0.049 mmol, 0.02 equiv), ZnF_2 (127 mg, 1.23 mmol, 0.5 equiv), and aryl bromide (2.46 mmol) was added *tert*-butyl trimethylsilyl methyl ketene acetal (644 mg, 3.69 mmol, 1.5 equiv), followed by anhydrous DMF (10.0 mL). The mixture was further deoxygenated via three freeze-pump-thaw cycles. The reaction mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and then stirred at 80 °C for 12 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and diluted with Et_2O (50 mL). The resulting solution was washed with H_2O (2×30 mL). The organic phase was dried over Na_2SO_4 , filtered, and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was then purified by chromatography on silica gel (hexanes:ethyl acetate 30:1 to 20:1) to provide compounds **S4a** and **S4b** in 77% and 91% yield, respectively. **S4a** and **S4b** were used directly for the preparation of substrate **1** following the General Procedure C.

Characterization of substrates **1**:

2-Methyl-1-morpholino-2-phenylpropan-1-one (S1): Colorless crystals. m.p = 84.5 – 86.5 °C. **IR** (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2976 (m), 2854 (m), 1631 (s), 1417 (s), 1269 (m), 1240 (s), 1173 (m), 1113 (s), 1034 (s), 845 (m), 769 (m), 702 (s); **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.37 – 7.30 (m, 2H), 7.25 – 7.19 (m, 3H), 4.00 – 2.70 (m, 8H), 1.53 (s, 6H); **¹³C NMR** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 175.0, 146.2, 129.0, 126.6, 124.8, 66.4 (br), 47.0, 43.4 (br), 28.3; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_2^+$ 234.1489; Found 234.1480.

N-Methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-2-phenylpropanamide (1a): Colorless oil. **IR** (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2974 (m), 2931 (w), 1649 (s), 1444 (m), 1383 (m), 1356 (m), 1169 (m), 1080 (m), 995 (s), 769 (m), 700 (s); **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.33 – 7.27 (m, 2H), 7.26 – 7.23 (m, 2H), 7.20 – 7.15 (m, 1H), 3.08 (s, 3H), 2.62 (s, 3H), 1.52 (s, 6H); **¹³C NMR** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.8, 146.2, 128.4, 126.2, 125.6, 59.0, 46.9, 33.5, 26.7; **HRMS** (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 230.1151; Found 230.1151.

***N*-Methoxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (S5):** Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2972 (m), 2933 (m), 1647 (s), 1512 (s), 1460 (m), 1356 (m), 1298 (m), 1246 (s), 1180 (s), 1032 (s), 993 (s), 831 (s), 762 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.19 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 6.86 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 3.79 (s, 3H), 3.10 (s, 3H), 2.71 (s, 3H), 1.52 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 178.0, 158.0, 138.4, 126.7, 113.7, 59.3, 55.4, 46.2, 33.6, 26.9; **HRMS** (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{19}\text{NNaO}_3^+$ 260.1257; Found 260.1264.

***N*-Methoxy-*N*,2-dimethyl-2-(*p*-tolyl)propanamide (1b):** Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2976 (m), 2929 (m), 1653 (s), 1512 (m), 1460 (m), 1383 (m), 1356 (s), 1169 (m), 1115 (m), 995 (s), 820 (s), 760 (m), 661 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.16 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.12 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 3.09 (s, 3H), 2.70 (s, 3H), 2.32 (s, 3H), 1.53 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.9, 143.2, 135.7, 129.0, 125.5, 59.2, 46.6, 33.6, 26.8, 21.1; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_2^+$ 222.1489; Found 222.1495.

2-(4-(*tert*-Butyl)phenyl)-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (1c): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2962 (m), 1655 (s), 1513 (m), 1460 (m), 1358 (s), 1167 (m), 1122 (m), 1015 (m), 995 (s), 833 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.33 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.19 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 3.09 (s, 3H), 2.60 (s, 3H), 1.54 (s, 6H), 1.29 (s, 9H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 178.0, 149.1, 143.0, 125.4, 125.1, 58.9, 46.5, 34.5, 33.5, 31.5, 26.7; **HRMS** (APPI/LTQ-Orbitrap) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{26}\text{NO}_2^+$ 264.1958; Found 264.1969.

2-([1,1'-Biphenyl]-4-yl)-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (1d): Colorless crystals. $m.p = 69.2 - 71.0$ °C. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2976 (m), 2931 (m), 1648 (s), 1487 (m), 1383 (m), 1356 (m), 1167 (m), 995 (s), 839 (m), 768 (s), 737 (s), 698 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.62 – 7.55 (m, 4H), 7.43 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H), 7.37 – 7.31 (m, 3H), 3.13 (s, 3H), 2.72 (s, 3H), 1.59 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.8, 145.4, 140.7, 139.0, 128.9, 127.4, 127.0, 127.0, 126.2, 59.1, 46.8, 33.6, 26.8; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{21}\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 306.1464; Found 306.1468.

2-(4-Fluorophenyl)-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (1e): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2979 (m), 2935 (m), 1649 (s), 1508 (s), 1461 (m), 1385 (m), 1358 (m), 1224 (s), 1164 (s), 1096 (m), 995 (s), 835 (s), 767 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.26 – 7.20 (m, 2H), 7.05 – 6.98 (m, 2H), 3.11 (s, 3H), 2.71 (s, 3H), 1.53 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.6, 161.4 (d, $J = 244.5$ Hz), 142.1 (d, $J = 3.3$ Hz), 127.2 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz), 115.1 (d, $J = 21.1$ Hz), 59.2, 46.5, 33.5, 26.9; **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -117.2; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{FNO}_2^+$ 226.1238; Found 226.1249.

2-(4-Chlorophenyl)-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (1f): Colorless crystals. m.p = 56.9 – 57.9 °C. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2974 (w), 2936 (w), 1654 (s), 1491 (s), 1357 (m), 1169 (m), 1102 (s), 1012 (s), 996 (s), 828 (s), 722 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.30 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.20 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 3.10 (s, 3H), 2.73 (s, 3H), 1.52 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.3, 144.9, 131.9, 128.5, 127.1, 59.2, 46.6, 33.5, 26.7; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClNO}_2^+$ 242.0942; Found 242.0952.

2-(4-Bromophenyl)-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (1g): White solid. m.p = 45.8 – 47.6 °C. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2978 (m), 2932 (m), 1651 (s), 1489 (s), 1460 (m), 1385 (m), 1356 (m), 1168 (m), 1100 (m), 1009 (s), 996 (s), 824 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.47 – 7.43 (m, 2H), 7.18 – 7.12 (m, 2H), 3.11 (s, 3H), 2.74 (s, 3H), 1.52 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.3, 145.4, 131.5, 127.5, 119.9, 59.2, 46.7, 33.5, 26.7; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrNO}_2^+$ 286.0437; Found 286.0442.

***N*-Methoxy-*N*,2-dimethyl-2-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)propanamide (1h):** Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2987 (m), 2939 (m), 1655 (s), 1618 (m), 1327 (s), 1165 (s), 1120 (s), 1066 (m), 1014 (m), 997 (m), 841 (m), 661 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.59 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 2H), 7.39 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 2H), 3.12 (s, 3H), 2.68 (s, 3H), 1.56 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.1, 150.4, 128.6 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 32.5$ Hz), 126.0, 125.4 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.7$ Hz), 124.3 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 271.9$ Hz), 59.0, 47.1, 33.5, 26.6; **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -62.3; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{F}_3\text{NO}_2^+$ 276.1206; Found 276.1209.

***N*-Methoxy-*N*,2-dimethyl-2-(*m*-tolyl)propanamide (1i):** Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2974 (w), 2930 (m), 1654 (s), 1459 (m), 1383 (m), 1356 (m), 1168 (m), 996 (s), 787 (m), 705 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.24 – 7.17 (m, 1H), 7.08 (brs, 1H), 7.07 (d, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.01 (d, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.10 (s, 3H), 2.67 (s, 3H), 2.34 (s, 3H), 1.53 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.9, 146.1, 137.9, 128.3, 126.9, 126.5, 122.6, 59.1, 46.8, 33.6, 26.8, 21.7; **HRMS** (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{19}\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 244.1308; Found 244.1313.

2-(3-Chlorophenyl)-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (1j): Colorless crystals. m.p = 41.2 – 42.6 °C. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2977 (m), 2936 (m), 1654 (s), 1595 (m), 1570 (m), 1473 (m), 1412 (m), 1357 (m), 1167 (m), 1079 (m), 996 (s), 818 (m), 787 (s), 697 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.31 – 7.29 (m, 1H), 7.28 (d, $J = 0.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.21 (ddd, $J = 8.0, 2.0, 1.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.16 (ddd, $J = 7.8, 1.8, 1.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.13 (s, 3H), 2.75 (s, 3H), 1.55 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.1, 148.4, 134.4, 129.7, 126.3, 125.9, 124.0, 59.2, 46.9, 33.5, 26.6; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClNO}_2^+$ 242.0942; Found 242.0948.

***N*-Methoxy-*N*,2-dimethyl-2-(3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)propanamide (1k):** Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2987 (m), 2935 (m), 1655 (s), 1329 (s), 1244 (m), 1165 (s), 1122 (s), 1072 (s), 997 (m), 806 (m), 758 (m), 704 (s), 661 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.54 (s, 1H), 7.51 – 7.41 (m, 3H), 3.11 (s, 3H), 2.63 (s, 3H), 1.57 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.1, 147.4, 130.9 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 31.9$ Hz), 129.3, 128.8, 124.3 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 270.7$ Hz), 123.0 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.6$ Hz), 122.3 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.8$ Hz), 59.0, 47.0, 33.5, 26.6; **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -62.51; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{F}_3\text{NO}_2^+$ 276.1206; Found 276.1210.

2-(2-Fluorophenyl)-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (1l): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2976 (w), 2935 (w), 1658 (s), 1487 (m), 1446 (m), 1354 (m), 1211 (m), 1163 (m), 1113 (m), 997 (s), 758 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.34 (td, $J = 7.8, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.24 – 7.17 (m, 1H), 7.15 (td, $J = 7.6, 1.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.02 (ddd, $J = 11.4, 8.0, 1.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.11 (s, 3H), 2.72 (s, 3H), 1.56 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.4, 160.7 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 246.7$ Hz), 133.7 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 12.9$ Hz), 127.8 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 8.3$ Hz), 126.6 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 4.9$ Hz), 124.4 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.4$ Hz), 115.9 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 22.3$ Hz), 59.2, 44.1, 33.6, 25.5, 25.5; **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -114.2; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{FNO}_2^+$ 226.1238; Found 226.1245.

2-(2-Chlorophenyl)-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethylpropanamide (1m): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2976 (m), 2935 (m), 1657 (s), 1469 (m), 1431 (m), 1383 (m), 1354 (m), 1165 (m), 1115 (m), 1039 (m), 995 (s), 762 (s), 744 (s), 710 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.41 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.33 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.28 (t, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.16 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.13 (s, 3H), 2.76 (s, 3H), 1.60 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.1, 143.7, 133.1, 130.8, 127.5, 127.3, 126.7, 59.2, 46.6, 33.5, 25.7; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClNO}_2^+$ 242.0942; Found 242.0940.

2-(3,5-Dimethylphenyl)-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethylpropanamide (1n): White solid. m.p = 79.3 – 80.3 °C. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2972 (w), 2931 (m), 1643 (s), 1603 (m), 1456 (m), 1356 (m), 1169 (m), 991 (m), 850 (m), 706 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.87 (s, 2H), 6.84 (s, 1H), 3.10 (s, 3H), 2.70 (s, 3H), 2.30 (s, 6H), 1.52 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.9, 146.0, 137.7, 127.8, 123.5, 59.2, 46.7, 33.6, 26.8, 21.5; **HRMS** (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{21}\text{NNO}_2^+$ 258.1464; Found 258.1471.

N-Methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-2-(naphthalen-2-yl)propanamide (1o): White solid. m.p = 55 – 57 °C. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2978 (m), 2931 (m), 1648 (s), 1459 (m), 1383 (m), 1363 (m), 1165 (m), 995 (s), 855 (m), 820 (s), 749 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.85 – 7.78 (m, 3H), 7.73 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.50 – 7.42 (m, 2H), 7.40 (dd, $J = 8.8, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.12 (s, 3H), 2.55 (s, 3H), 1.65 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.7, 143.6, 133.6, 132.0, 128.0, 128.0, 127.6, 126.2, 125.7, 124.9, 123.5, 59.2, 47.1, 33.6, 26.8; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{NNO}_2^+$ 280.1308; Found 280.1311.

2-(3,5-Difluoro-4-methoxyphenyl)-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethylpropanamide (1p): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2975 (m), 2938 (m), 1656 (s), 1577 (m), 1510 (s), 1428 (m), 1334 (s), 1251 (m), 1029 (s), 999 (s), 853 (m), 771 (m), 668 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.86 – 6.77 (m, 2H), 3.97 (s, 3H), 3.12 (s, 3H), 2.87 (s, 3H), 1.49 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 176.6, 155.6 (dd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 247.8, 6.4$ Hz), 142.0 (t, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 7.8$ Hz), 134.5 (t, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 14.1$ Hz), 109.6 (dd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 16.9, 6.8$ Hz), 62.1 (t, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.3$ Hz),

59.4, 46.6, 33.6, 26.6; ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -128.6; HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{F}_2\text{NO}_3^+$ 274.1249; Found 274.1251.

2-(2,6-Difluorophenyl)-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethylpropanamide (1q): Colorless oil. IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2983 (w), 2939 (m), 1664 (s), 1572 (m), 1458 (s), 1356 (m), 1263 (m), 1234 (m), 1163 (m), 987 (s), 789 (s), 756 (m), 729 (m); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.11 (tt, $J = 8.4, 6.0$ Hz, 1H), 6.87 – 6.79 (m, 2H), 3.12 (s, 3H), 2.92 (s, 3H), 1.61 (t, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 6H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.5, 161.0 (dd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 248.6, 9.2$ Hz), 127.5 (t, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 11.2$ Hz), 121.8 (t, $J = 15.4$ Hz), 112.3 (dd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 21.1, 7.2$ Hz), 59.2, 44.2, 33.6, 26.2 (t, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 4.4$ Hz); ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -110.5. HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{F}_2\text{NO}_2^+$ 244.1144; Found 244.1144.

N-Methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-2-(1-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)sulfonyl)indolin-5-yl)propanamide (1r): White solid. m.p = 134.6 – 136 °C. IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2933 (w), 1647 (m), 1486 (m), 1403 (m), 1360 (m), 1321 (s), 1169 (s), 1131 (s), 1062 (s), 996 (m), 830 (m), 738 (m), 708 (m); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.92 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.69 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.58 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.12 (dd, $J = 8.4, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.01 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.95 (t, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 3.08 (s, 3H), 2.93 (t, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 2.61 (s, 3H), 1.48 (s, 6H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.5, 142.6, 140.5, 139.5, 134.9 (q, $J = 33.2$ Hz), 131.9, 127.9, 126.2 (q, $J = 3.7$ Hz), 125.2, 123.2 (q, $J = 271.1$ Hz), 122.8, 114.6, 59.1, 50.4, 46.6, 33.6, 28.0, 26.8; ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -63.2; HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{F}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}^+$ 457.1403; Found 457.1409.

N-Methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-2-(1-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)sulfonyl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinolin-6-yl)propanamide (1s): White solid. m.p = 102.5 – 104 °C. IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2932 (w), 1647 (m), 1496 (m), 1403 (m), 1356 (m), 1321 (s), 1166 (s), 1131 (s), 1108 (s), 1062 (s), 1016 (m), 996 (m), 832 (m), 736 (m), 714 (s); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.74 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.72 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.64 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.10 (dd, $J = 8.6, 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 6.91 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.92 – 3.79 (m, 2H), 3.10 (s, 3H), 2.69 (s, 3H), 2.48 (t, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 2H), 1.69 (apparent p, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2H), 1.50 (s, 6H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.5, 143.3, 143.3, 134.5 (q, $J = 34.4$ Hz), 134.3, 130.4, 127.8, 126.5, 126.10 (q, $J = 3.6$ Hz), 124.3, 124.1, 123.2 (q, $J = 271.2$ Hz), 59.1, 47.0, 46.5, 33.6, 26.9, 26.7, 22.0; ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -63.1; HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{F}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}^+$ 471.1560; Found 471.1562

N-Methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-2-phenylbutanamide (1t): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}) 2970 (m), 2935 (m), 1649 (s), 1448 (m), 1358 (m), 1153 (m), 993 (s), 762 (s), 700 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.35 – 7.29 (m, 2H), 7.26 – 7.22 (m, 2H), 7.19 (tt, $J = 7.2, 1.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.10 (s, 3H), 2.65 (s, 3H), 2.26 (dq, $J = 13.6, 7.2$ Hz, 1H), 1.88 (dq, $J = 13.6, 7.6$ Hz, 1H), 1.49 (s, 3H), 0.77 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.6, 145.5, 128.3, 126.1, 126.1, 59.0, 50.7, 33.5, 30.8, 23.0, 8.9; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_2^+$ 222.1489; Found 222.1497.

N-Methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-2-phenylpentanamide (1u): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2958 (m), 2871 (m), 1651 (s), 1448 (m), 1354 (m), 1161 (m), 1111 (m), 993 (s), 769 (m), 700 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.34 – 7.28 (m, 2H), 7.27 – 7.22 (m, 2H), 7.21 – 7.16 (m, 1H), 3.09 (s, 3H), 2.64 (s, 3H), 2.26 – 2.16 (m, 1H), 1.85 – 1.74 (m, 1H), 1.50 (s, 3H), 1.21 – 1.07 (m, 2H), 0.91 (t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.6, 145.8, 128.3, 126.1, 126.0, 59.0, 50.4, 40.4, 33.5, 24.0, 17.8, 14.9; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{21}\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 258.1464; Found 258.1474.

8-Chloro-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-2-phenyloctanamide (1v): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2934 (m), 1649 (s), 1462 (m), 1355 (m), 1174 (w), 995 (s), 771 (m), 732 (m), 701 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.33 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H), 7.29 – 7.23 (m, 2H), 7.20 (t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.49 (t, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 2H), 3.09 (s, 3H), 2.65 (s, 3H), 2.22 (ddd, $J = 13.2, 10.4, 6.4$ Hz, 1H), 1.80 (ddd, $J = 13.2, 10.3, 6.4$ Hz, 1H), 1.72 (p, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 2H), 1.52 (s, 3H), 1.46 – 1.37 (m, 2H), 1.37 – 1.25 (m, 2H), 1.19 – 1.08 (m, 2H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.6, 145.6, 128.3, 126.2, 126.0, 59.0, 50.3, 45.2, 38.2, 33.5, 32.7, 29.6, 26.9, 24.3, 23.7; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{27}\text{ClNO}_2^+$ 312.1725; Found 312.1733.

6-Fuoro-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-2-phenylhexanamide (1w): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}) 2958 (m), 1649 (s), 1446 (m), 1358 (s), 1065 (m), 1030 (m), 993 (s), 771 (m), 717 (s), 702 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.35 – 7.28 (m, 2H), 7.26 – 7.22 (m, 2H), 7.22 – 7.16 (m, 1H), 4.40 (dm, $^2J_{\text{H-F}} = 47.3$ Hz, 2H), 3.09 (s, 3H), 2.63 (s, 3H), 2.23 (td, $J = 12.8, 4.8$ Hz, 1H), 1.85 (td, $J = 12.8, 4.8$ Hz, 1H), 1.76 – 1.60 (m, 2H), 1.53 (s, 3H), 1.33 – 1.11 (m, 2H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.4, 145.2, 128.4, 126.2, 126.0, 84.1 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 164.3$ Hz), 59.0, 50.2, 38.3, 33.5, 31.1 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 19.4$ Hz), 23.1, 20.2 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 5.6$ Hz); **^{19}F**

NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -218.1; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : [M + H]⁺ Calcd for C₁₅H₂₃FNO₂⁺ 268.1707; Found 268.1713.

N,6-Dimethoxy-N,2-dimethyl-2-phenylhexanamide (1x): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹): 2933 (m), 2866 (m), 1649 (s), 1448 (m), 1358 (m), 1174 (m), 1117 (s), 995 (s), 769 (m), 729 (m), 702 (s); **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.31 (t, J = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 7.24 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 7.19 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 1H), 3.33 (t, J = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 3.29 (s, 3H), 3.09 (s, 3H), 2.63 (s, 3H), 2.23 (td, J = 12.8, 5.2 Hz, 1H), 1.83 (td, J = 12.8, 5.0 Hz, 1H), 1.61 – 1.53 (m, 2H), 1.51 (s, 3H), 1.27 – 1.06 (m, 2H); **¹³C NMR** (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 177.5, 145.5, 128.3, 126.1, 126.0, 72.8, 59.0, 58.7, 50.3, 38.2, 33.5, 30.4, 23.5, 21.1; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₂₅NNaO₃⁺ 302.1727; Found 302.1735.

N-Methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-2-phenyl-6-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenoxy)hexanamide (1y): White solid, m.p = 80.0 – 82.0 °C. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹): 2938 (w), 1648 (m), 1615 (m), 1325 (s), 1256 (s), 1158 (m), 1109 (s), 1066 (s), 995 (m), 836 (s), 701 (s); **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.51 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.35 – 7.28 (m, 2H), 7.26 – 7.22 (m, 2H), 7.22 – 7.17 (m, 1H), 6.90 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 3.99-3.91 (m, 2H), 3.09 (s, 3H), 2.63 (s, 3H), 2.27 (td, J = 12.8, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 1.89 (td, J = 12.8, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 1.85 – 1.72 (m, 2H), 1.54 (s, 3H), 1.39 – 1.20 (m, 2H); **¹³C NMR** (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 177.4, 161.6, 145.3, 128.4, 126.9 (q, J_{C-F} = 3.8 Hz), 126.3, 126.0, 124.6 (q, J_{C-F} = 269.4 Hz), 122.7 (q, J_{C-F} = 32.6 Hz), 114.5, 68.0, 59.0, 50.2, 38.3, 33.5, 29.7, 23.1, 20.9; **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -61.4; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : [M + H]⁺ Calcd for C₂₂H₂₇F₃NO₃⁺ 410.1938; Found 410.1937.

6,6,6-Trifluoro-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-2-phenylhexanamide (1z): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹): 2939 (m), 1649 (s), 1360 (m), 1282 (m), 1252 (s), 1130 (s), 989 (s), 769 (m), 731 (m), 702 (s), 661 (m); **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.36 – 7.30 (m, 2H), 7.25 – 7.17 (m, 3H), 3.10 (s, 3H), 2.63 (s, 3H), 2.21 (td, J = 13.0, 5.0 Hz, 1H), 2.15 – 1.94 (m, 2H), 1.87 (td, J = 13.0, 4.6 Hz, 1H), 1.56 (s, 3H), 1.50 – 1.36 (m, 1H), 1.37 – 1.22 (m, 1H); **¹³C NMR** (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 177.1, 144.6, 128.5, 127.2 (q, J_{C-F} = 274.6 Hz), 126.5, 126.0, 59.0, 50.0, 38.4, 34.4 (q, J_{C-F} = 28.4 Hz), 33.5, 22.3, 17.2 (q, J_{C-F} = 3.0 Hz); **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -66.3; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : [M + H]⁺ Calcd for C₁₅H₂₁F₃NO₂⁺ 304.1519; Found 304.1516.

N-Methoxy-N,5-dimethyl-6,7,8,9-tetrahydro-5H-benzo[7]annulene-5-carboxamide (1aa): White solid. m.p = 68.0 – 69.0 °C. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2925 (m), 1655 (s), 1459 (m), 1339 (m), 1166 (m), 1112 (m), 1045 (m), 998 (s), 761 (m), 743 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.28 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.18 (td, J = 7.6, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 7.09 (td, J = 7.2, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 7.05 (dd, J = 7.4, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 3.05 (s, 3H), 2.83 (ddd, J = 14.4, 12.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 2.60 (dd, J = 14.0, 6.0 Hz, 1H), 2.50 (s, 3H), 2.45 (ddd, J = 14.0, 6.2, 4.4 Hz, 1H), 2.40 – 2.26 (m, 1H), 1.94 – 1.84 (m, 1H), 1.77 – 1.64 (m, 1H), 1.59 (s, 3H), 1.46 – 1.32 (m, 2H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 178.6, 143.7, 142.9, 130.0, 126.9, 126.4, 126.2, 58.9, 50.0, 37.8, 34.9, 33.9, 26.8, 26.7, 25.7; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{NO}_2^+$ 248.1645; Found 248.1645.

2-(1,3-Dioxoisindolin-2-yl)-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethylpropanamide (1ab): Colorless crystals. m.p = 88.4 – 90.0 °C. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2941 (m), 1705 (s), 1668 (s), 1466 (m), 1369 (s), 1325 (s), 1167 (m), 1074 (s), 1001 (s), 955 (m), 876 (s), 719 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.95 – 7.83 (m, 2H), 7.83 – 7.56 (m, 2H), 3.50 (s, 3H), 3.18 (s, 3H), 1.83 (s, 6H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 174.1, 168.3, 134.1, 131.9, 123.2, 60.7, 60.7, 34.0, 24.9; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_4^+$ 299.1002; Found 299.1003.

N-Methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-3-phenylpropanamide (5a): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2970 (m), 2935 (m), 1657 (s), 1454 (m), 1417 (m), 1385 (m), 1176 (m), 993 (s), 756 (s), 741 (s), 700 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.29 – 7.23 (m, 2H), 7.21 – 7.14 (m, 3H), 3.47 (s, 3H), 3.22 – 3.08 (m, 1H), 3.13 (s, 3H), 3.03 (dd, J = 13.2, 7.8 Hz, 1H), 2.61 (dd, J = 13.2, 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.15 (d, J = 6.8 Hz, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.1, 140.3, 129.1, 128.3, 126.2, 61.4, 39.9, 37.7, 32.2, 17.4; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_2^+$ 208.1332; Found 208.1330.

[D₆]-1a. Prepared following General Procedure A using CD_3I as the electrophile. Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2935 (m), 1649 (s), 1446 (m), 1360 (s), 1184 (m), 1117 (m), 1043 (m), 984 (s), 812 (m), 754 (s), 700 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.35 – 7.29 (m, 2H), 7.28 – 7.24 (m, 2H), 7.22 – 7.16 (m, 1H), 3.10 (s, 3H), 2.64 (s, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.9, 146.2, 128.4, 126.2, 125.7, 59.0, 46.5,

33.5, 25.8 (hept, $J = 6.6$ Hz); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + H]^+$ Calcd for $C_{12}H_{12}D_6NO_2^+$ 214.1709; Found 214.1709.

2-Methyl-2-phenyl-N-(2,4,6-trifluorophenyl)propanamide (6). White solid. $m.p = 92.5 - 93.6$ °C. **IR** (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 3298 (br), 2974 (m), 1676 (m), 1606 (m), 1514 (s), 1442 (s), 1120 (s), 1043 (s), 997 (m), 839 (m), 756 (m), 719 (s), 698 (s); **1H NMR** (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.50 – 7.45 (m, 2H), 7.45 – 7.38 (m, 2H), 7.35 – 7.29 (m, 1H), 6.71-6.64 (m, 2H), 6.30 (brs, 1H), 1.68 (s, 6H); **^{13}C NMR** (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 176.5, 160.9 (dt, $J_{C-F} = 247.7, 14.6$ Hz), 158.4 (ddd, $J_{C-F} = 244.8, 15.2, 7.2$ Hz), 144.5, 129.1, 127.6, 126.7, 110.8 (td, $J_{C-F} = 16.9, 5.0$ Hz), 100.6 (apparent td, $J_{C-F} = 26.0, 3.2$ Hz), 47.9, 27.2; **^{19}F NMR** (377 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ -109.3 (t, $J = 5.5$ Hz), -115.1 (d, $J = 5.5$ Hz); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + H]^+$ Calcd for $C_{16}H_{15}F_3NO^+$ 294.1100; Found 294.1098.

3. Condition Optimization

Scheme S6. Preliminary Study

Screening of F-oxidants

Screening of Amide Directing Groups

Table S1. Effect of Solvents

entry	solvent	3a	4a
1	HFIP	43%	23%
2	TFE	38%	15%
3	DCE	--	--
4	toluene	--	--
5	EA	--	--
6	dioxane	--	--
7	CF ₃ Ph	--	--

[a] Reactions were performed on 0.10 mmol scale for substrate **1a**. [b] Yield was determined by ¹H NMR of the crude reaction mixture using BnOAc as the internal standard.

Table S2. Effect of Reaction Temperature

entry	T (°C)	3a	4a
1	60	50%	13%
2	50	58%	14%
3	45	58%	16%
4	40	47%	15%

[a] Reactions were performed on 0.10 mmol scale for substrate **1a**. [b] Yield was determined by ¹H NMR of the crude reaction mixture using BnOAc as the internal standard.

Table S3. Effect of Silver Salts

entry	Ag(I)	3b	4b
1	AgOAc	58%	14%
2	AgOAc (1.0 equiv)	58%	15%
3	AgOAc (1.5 equiv)	58%	15%
4	Ag ₂ CO ₃	50%	21%
5	AgNO ₃	36%	16%
6	AgBF ₄	52%	18%
7	AgTFA	43%	12%
8	Ag ₂ O	44%	17%
9	AgF	57%	17%
10	Ag ₃ PO ₄	41%	23%
11	AgOPiv	44%	17%
12	AgO ₂ CMes	62%	15%
13	AgO ₂ CAd	49%	18%

[a] Reactions were performed on 0.10 mmol scale for substrate **1a**. [b] Yield was determined by ¹H NMR of the crude reaction mixture using BnOAc as the internal standard.

Table S4. Effect of Acid Additives

entry	Acid	3a	4a	SM	Mass balance
1	PivOH (0.5 equiv)	43%	15%		
2	AdmCO ₂ H (0.5 equiv)	50%	15%		
3	MesCO ₂ H (0.5 equiv)	72%	11%	6%	89
4	MesCO ₂ H (1.0 equiv)	69%	9%	16%	94
5	MesCO ₂ H (1.5 equiv)	62%	6%	24%	92

[a] Reactions were performed on 0.10 mmol scale for substrate **1a**. [b] Yield was determined by ¹H NMR of the crude reaction mixture using BnOAc as the internal standard.

Table S5. Screening of Different Loadings

entry	z	x	y	3a	4a
1	1.5	1.0	1.0	61%	7%
2	1.7	0.5	1.0	72%	9%
3 (36 h)	1.7	0.5	1.0	75% (68% Isolated)	9%
4 (36 h)	2.0	0.5	1.0	75%	9%

[a] Reactions were performed on 0.10 mmol scale for substrate **1a**. [b] Yield was determined by ¹H NMR of the crude reaction mixture using BnOAc as the internal standard.

4. Representative Procedures for Rearrangement/Fluorination

General Procedure A (Condition A): To an 8 mL vial equipped with a stir bar was added substrate **1** (0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Pd(OAc)₂ (2.3 mg, 0.010 mmol, 0.1 equiv), AgOAc (8.4 mg, 0.050 mmol, 0.5 equiv), MesCO₂H (16.4 mg, 0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Selectfluor (60.2 mg, 0.17 mmol, 1.7 equiv), and HFIP (1.0 mL). The vial was sealed, heated to 50 °C and allowed to stir for 36 h. Then, the mixture was diluted with EtOAc, filtered over a plug of silica gel (washed with 10 mL EtOAc), and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by preparative TLC (three ~0.25 mm plates, hexanes/acetone = 10/1 or hexanes/DCM = 5/1).

General Procedure B (Condition B): To an 8 mL vial equipped with a stir bar was added substrate **1** (0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Pd(OAc)₂ (1.6 mg, 0.0070 mmol, 0.07 equiv), AgOAc (5.8 mg, 0.035 mmol, 0.35 equiv), MesCO₂H (16.4 mg, 0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Selectfluor (28.3 mg, 0.08 mmol, 0.8 equiv), and HFIP (1.0 mL). The vial was sealed and allowed to stir at 50 °C. Two portions of Pd(OAc)₂ (1.6 mg, 0.0070 mmol, 0.07 equiv), AgOAc (5.8 mg, 0.035 mmol, 0.35 equiv) and Selectfluor (28.3 mg, 0.08 mmol, 0.8 equiv) were added at the time of 24 h and 48 h. After stirring for 72 h, the mixture was diluted with EtOAc, filtered over a plug of silica gel (washed with 10 mL EtOAc), and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by preparative TLC (three ~0.25 mm plates, hexanes/acetone = 10/1 or hexanes/DCM = 5/1).

Characterization of the rearrangement products **3** and **4**:

2-Fluoro-N-methoxy-N-(2,2-dimethyl-3-phenylpropanamide (3a): 15.3 mg, 68% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹): 2936 (m), 1657 (s), 1454 (m), 1377 (s), 1200 (m), 1097 (m), 998 (s), 943 (m), 757 (m), 738 (m), 702 (s); **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.32 – 7.21 (m, 5H), 3.66 (s, 3H), 3.37 (dd, J = 23.0, 14.2 Hz, 1H), 3.13 (s, 3H), 3.10 (dd, J = 23.8, 14.2 Hz, 1H), 1.56 (d, J = 22.0 Hz, 3H); **¹³C NMR** (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.3 (br), 135.3, 130.7, 128.3, 127.1, 97.3 (brd, J_{C-F} = 189.6 Hz), 61.4 (br), 43.8 (brd, J_{C-F} = 18.2 Hz), 34.4 (br), 23.3 (br); **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -153.2 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₂H₁₆FNNaO₂⁺ 248.1057; Found 248.1062.

3-Fluoro-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethyl-2-phenylpropanamide (4a): (preparative TLC: hexanes/acetone = 10/1) Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2942 (m), 1651 (s), 1460 (m), 1373 (m), 1195 (m), 1017 (s), 995 (s), 703 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.40 – 7.34 (m, 2H), 7.31 – 7.27 (m, 2H), 7.27 – 7.24 (m, 1H), 4.80 (dd, $J = 47.6, 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 4.63 (dd, $J = 47.4, 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 3.12 (s, 3H), 2.72 (s, 3H), 1.74 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 174.8 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 4.0$ Hz), 140.6 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.3$ Hz), 128.7, 127.2, 126.4, 88.7 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 174.9$ Hz), 59.3, 51.2 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 19.0$ Hz), 33.1, 18.3 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 5.1$ Hz); **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -225.3; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{FNNaO}_2^+$ 248.1057; Found 248.1063.

2-Fluoro-2-methyl-1-morpholino-3-phenylpropan-1-one (S6): Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2906 (m), 2856 (m), 1630 (s), 1431 (s), 1265 (m), 1221 (m), 1176 (m), 1115 (s), 1034 (s), 958 (m), 850 (m), 760 (m), 702 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.35 – 7.20 (m, 5H), 3.78 – 3.38 (m, 7H), 3.32 (dd, $J = 29.8, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.08 (dd, $J = 20.0, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.15 – 2.97 (m, 1H), 1.65 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 170.0 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 19.8$ Hz), 135.4, 130.8, 128.4, 127.3, 100.0 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 190.4$ Hz), 67.0, 66.8, 46.9 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 20.4$ Hz), 45.3 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 21.2$ Hz), 43.9 (br), 25.3 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 24.4$ Hz); **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -152.4; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{FNNaO}_2^+$ 274.1214; Found 274.1220.

3-Fluoro-2-methyl-1-morpholino-2-phenylpropan-1-one (S7): White solid. $m.p = 41.5 - 42.5$ °C. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}) 2854 (w), 1626 (s), 1427 (m), 1271 (m), 1242 (m), 1115 (s), 1007 (s), 847 (w), 760 (m), 702 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.42 – 7.35 (m, 2H), 7.33 – 7.26 (m, 3H), 4.72 (dd, $J = 48.2, 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 4.53 (dd, $J = 47.6, 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 4.0 – 2.65 (m, 8H), 1.70 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 172.7 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 4.4$ Hz), 140.3 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 2.6$ Hz), 129.2, 127.7, 126.1, 89.3 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 175.8$ Hz), 66.7, 66.1, 50.9 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 18.9$ Hz), 46.9 (br), 43.0 (br), 18.9 (d, $J = 5.5$ Hz); **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -223.8; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{FNNaO}_2^+$ 274.1214; Found 274.1218.

2-Fluoro-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethyl-3-(*p*-tolyl)propanamide (3b): 16.1 mg, 67% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2966 (m), 1649 (s), 1446 (m), 1358 (s), 1176 (m), 1030 (m), 993 (s), 771 (m), 717 (s), 702 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.12 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.09 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H),

3.67 (s, 3H), 3.32 (dd, $J = 22.2, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.14 (s, 3H), 3.07 (dd, $J = 23.8, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 2.32 (s, 3H), 1.55 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.4 (br), 136.6, 132.2, 130.6, 129.0, 97.4 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 188.9$ Hz), 61.4 (br), 43.4 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 22.4$ Hz), 34.5 (br), 23.2 (br), 21.2; $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -153.0 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{FNNaO}_2^+$ 262.1214; Found 262.1217.

3-(4-(*tert*-Butyl)phenyl)-2-fluoro-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (3c): 18.3 mg, 65% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2964 (m), 1659 (s), 1462 (m), 1366 (m), 1202 (m), 1110 (m), 1000 (s), 937 (m), 837 (m), 701 (m); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.31 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.16 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 3.67 (s, 3H), 3.33 (dd, $J = 22.2, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.14 (s, 3H), 3.07 (dd, $J = 22.4, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 1.55 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H), 1.30 (s, 9H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.5 (br), 149.9, 132.2, 130.4, 125.2, 97.4 (brd, $J = 187.1$ Hz), 61.3 (br), 43.2 (br), 34.6, 34.4 (br), 31.5, 23.1 (br); $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -153.0 (br); **HRMS** (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{24}\text{FNNaO}_2^+$ 304.1683; Found 304.1685.

3-([1,1'-Biphenyl]-4-yl)-2-fluoro-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (3d): 18.2 mg, 60% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2934 (m), 1658 (s), 1487 (s), 1448 (m), 1377 (s), 1200 (m), 1118 (m), 1079 (m), 999 (s), 937 (m), 769 (s), 749 (s), 699 (s); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.62 – 7.56 (m, 2H), 7.54 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.43 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 2H), 7.38 – 7.29 (m, 3H), 3.69 (s, 3H), 3.43 (dd, $J = 22.8, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.17 (s, 3H), 3.15 (dd, $J = 24.0, 14.0$ Hz, 4H), 1.60 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.3 (br), 141.0, 139.9, 134.4, 131.2, 128.9, 127.3, 127.1, 127.0, 97.3 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 189.4$ Hz), 61.4 (br), 43.4 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 21.5$ Hz), 34.6 (br), 23.3 (br); $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -153.1 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{F}_2\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 266.0963; Found 266.0967.

2-Fluoro-3-(4-fluorophenyl)-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (3e): 17.2 mg, 71% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2940 (m), 1658 (s), 1509 (s), 1460 (m), 1377 (m), 1222 (s), 1159 (m), 1104 (m), 1000 (s), 934 (m), 839 (m), 821 (m); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.20 (dd, $J = 8.4, 5.6$ Hz, 2H), 6.97 (t, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 2H), 3.65 (s, 3H), 3.35 (dd, $J = 23.6, 14.4$ Hz, 1H), 3.14 (s, 3H), 3.06 (dd, $J = 22.8, 14.4$ Hz, 1H), 1.55 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.4 (br), 162.2 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 245.0$ Hz), 132.2 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 8.0$ Hz), 131.1, 115.1 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 21.1$ Hz), 97.2 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 190.2$ Hz), 61.5 (br), 43.0 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 16.8$ Hz), 34.2 (br), 23.2 (br); $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -116.1 (br), -153.8 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{F}_2\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 266.0963; Found 266.0967.

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-fluoro-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethylpropanamide (3f): 17.1 mg, 66% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2979 (m), 2937 (m), 1656 (s), 1492 (s), 1460 (m), 1377 (s), 1200 (m), 1178 (m), 1112 (s), 1092 (s), 1016 (s), 999 (s), 936 (m), 836 (m), 804 (s), 663 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.30 – 7.24 (m, 2H), 7.19 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 3.67 (s, 3H), 3.37 (dd, $J = 23.6, 14.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.16 (d, $J = 1.6$ Hz, 3H), 3.07 (dd, $J = 22.6, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 1.57 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.2 (br), 133.9, 133.0, 132.1, 128.4, 97.1 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 189.7$ Hz), 61.5 (br), 43.2 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 22.1$ Hz), 34.3 (br), 23.3 (br); **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -153.8 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClFNNaO}_2^+$ 282.0668; Found 282.0669.

3-(4-Bromophenyl)-2-fluoro-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethylpropanamide (3g): 18.2 mg, 60% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2937 (m), 1656 (s), 1488 (s), 1460 (m), 1377 (s), 1201 (m), 1111 (m), 1071 (s), 1011 (s), 999 (s), 936 (m), 834 (m), 801 (s), 732 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.43 – 7.38 (m, 2H), 7.12 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 3.66 (s, 3H), 3.34 (dd, $J = 23.8, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.15 (d, $J = 1.6$ Hz, 3H), 3.04 (dd, $J = 22.6, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 1.55 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.3 (br), 134.4, 132.5, 131.4, 121.2, 97.0 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 190.0$ Hz), 61.5 (br), 43.2 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 19.4$ Hz), 34.2 (br), 23.2 (br); **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -153.8 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{BrFNNaO}_2^+$ 326.0162; Found 326.0163.

2-Fluoro-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-3-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)propanamide (3h): 15.2 mg, 52% (Condition A with 0.5 equiv MesCO_2H). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2978 (w), 2933 (w), 1655 (s), 1456 (m), 1381 (m), 1184 (m), 1115 (m), 1009 (m), 976 (m), 731 (m), 700 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.54 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.37 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 2H), 3.66 (s, 3H), 3.45 (dd, $J = 23.6, 14.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.16 (s, 3H), 3.14 (dd, $J = 21.2, 14.0$ Hz, 1H), 1.57 (d, $J = 21.6$ Hz, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.0 (br), 139.6, 131.1, 129.4 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 32.3$ Hz), 125.2 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.8$ Hz), 124.4 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 270.2$ Hz), 97.0 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 190.2$ Hz), 61.6 (br), 43.6 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 22.1$ Hz), 34.2 (br), 23.3 (br); **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -62.5, -153.9 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{15}\text{F}_4\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 316.0931; Found 316.093.

2-Fluoro-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethyl-3-(*m*-tolyl)propanamide (3i): 15.1 mg, 65% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2985 (m), 2935 (m), 1657 (s), 1456 (m), 1377 (s), 1203 (m), 1101 (m), 999 (s), 943 (m), 791 (m), 752 (m), 700 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.18 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.09 – 7.01 (m, 3H), 3.67 (s, 3H), 3.33 (dd, $J = 22.4, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.14 (s, 3H), 3.07 (dd, $J = 24.2, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 2.33 (s, 3H), 1.56 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.4 (br), 137.8, 135.2, 131.5, 128.1, 127.8, 127.8, 97.3 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 189.2$ Hz), 61.4 (br), 43.4 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 16.9$ Hz), 34.5 (br), 23.2 (br), 21.5; **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -152.9 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{F}_2\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 266.0963; Found 266.0965.

3-(3-Chlorophenyl)-2-fluoro-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (3j): 15.0 mg, 58% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2939 (m), 1658 (s), 1473 (m), 1433 (m), 1379 (m), 1205 (m), 1082 (m), 1001 (m), 945 (m), 789 (m), 733 (m), 698 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.25 – 7.20 (m, 3H), 7.12 (d, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.67 (s, 3H), 3.36 (dd, $J = 23.2, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.16 (s, 3H), 3.06 (dd, $J = 23.4, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 1.56 (d, $J = 21.6$ Hz, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.4 (br), 137.4, 134.0, 130.8, 129.5, 129.0, 127.3, 97.0 (brd, $J = 190.2$ Hz), 61.6 (br), 43.4 (br), 33.9 (br), 23.0 (br); **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -153.5 (br); **HRMS** (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClFNNaO}_2^+$ 282.0668; Found 282.0670.

2-Fluoro-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethyl-3-(3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)propanamide (3k): 14.7 mg, 50% (Condition A with 0.5 equiv MesCO_2H). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2983 (m), 2939 (m), 1658 (s), 1452 (m), 1379 (m), 1333 (s), 1201 (m), 1163 (s), 1122 (s), 1072 (s), 999 (m), 804 (m), 702 (m); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.54 – 7.48 (m, 2H), 7.46 – 7.38 (m, 2H), 3.65 (s, 3H), 3.45 (dd, $J = 23.8, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.15 (dd, $J = 22.4, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.15 (d, $J = 1.6$ Hz, 3H), 1.58 (d, $J = 21.6$ Hz, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.3 (br), 136.4, 134.2, 130.6 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 32.1$ Hz), 128.7, 127.4 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.9$ Hz), 124.3 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 270.5$ Hz), 123.9 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 4.0$ Hz), 97.0 (br d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 189.5$ Hz), 61.6 (br), 43.6 (br), 33.7 (br), 23.1 (br); **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -62.6, -153.7 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{15}\text{F}_4\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 316.0931; Found 316.0934.

2-Fluoro-3-(2-fluorophenyl)-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethylpropanamide (3l): 13.1 mg, 54% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2980 (w), 2939 (w), 1658 (s), 1493 (m), 1454 (m), 1378 (m), 1231 (m), 1183 (m), 1116 (s), 999 (m), 938 (m), 758 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.30 – 7.20 (m, 2H), 7.11

– 7.00 (m, 2H), 3.71 (s, 3H), 3.32 (d, $J = 21.6$ Hz, 2H), 3.20 (d, $J = 1.6$ Hz, 3H), 1.56 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.6 (br), 161.7 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 246.2$ Hz), 132.9 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 4.2$ Hz), 129.0 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 8.1$ Hz), 124.0 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.6$ Hz), 122.4 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 15.7$ Hz), 115.4 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 22.9$ Hz), 96.9 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 189.6$ Hz), 61.5 (br), 36.1 (br), 34.0 (br), 22.6 (br); $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -116.5 (br), -152.9 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{F}_2\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 266.0963; Found 266.0965.

3-(2-Chlorophenyl)-2-fluoro-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethylpropanamide (3m): 12.4 mg, 48% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2985 (w), 2939 (w), 1657 (s), 1473 (m), 1441 (m), 1377 (m), 1196 (m), 1072 (m), 999 (s), 939 (m), 766 (m), 746 (s), 717 (m), 677 (m); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.42 – 7.28 (m, 2H), 7.24 – 7.15 (m, 2H), 3.71 (s, 3H), 3.51 (dd, $J = 25.8, 14.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.43 (dd, $J = 19.2, 14.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.21 (d, $J = 1.2$ Hz, 3H), 1.56 (d, $J = 22.4$ Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.6 (br), 135.4, 133.5, 132.8, 129.7, 128.5, 126.7, 97.2 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 189.8$ Hz), 61.5 (br), 39.6 (br), 34.0 (br), 22.4 (br); $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -152.0; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClFNNaO}_2^+$ 282.0668; Found 282.0672.

3-(3,5-Dimethylphenyl)-2-fluoro-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethylpropanamide (3n): 16.0 mg, 63% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2982 (m), 2939 (m), 1658 (s), 1605 (m), 1460 (m), 1375 (s), 1203 (m), 1095 (m), 999 (s), 938 (m), 852 (m), 746 (m), 703 (m); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.89 (s, 1H), 6.84 (s, 2H), 3.68 (s, 3H), 3.28 (dd, $J = 22.0, 14.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.15 (s, 3H), 3.03 (dd, $J = 24.4, 14.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.29 (s, 6H), 1.55 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.9 (br), 137.7, 135.1, 128.7, 128.5, 97.3 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 188.4$ Hz), 61.4 (br), 43.5 (br), 34.0 (br), 23.0 (br), 21.4; $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -152.7 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{FNNaO}_2^+$ 276.1370; Found 276.1375.

2-Fluoro-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-3-(naphthalen-2-yl)propanamide (3o): 14.1 mg, 51% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2985 (m), 2937 (m), 1657 (s), 1456 (m), 1377 (s), 1203 (m), 1090 (m), 999 (s), 941 (m), 820 (s), 758 (s); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.86 – 7.75 (m, 3H), 7.70 (s, 1H), 7.51 – 7.41 (m, 2H), 7.39 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 3.66 (s, 3H), 3.55 (dd, $J = 23.0, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.26 (dd, $J = 23.6, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.13 (s, 3H), 1.60 (d, $J = 22.4$ Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.8 (br), 133.4, 133.0, 132.6, 129.5, 129.0, 127.8, 127.7, 127.7, 126.1, 125.8, 97.5 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 190.5$ Hz), 61.5 (br), 43.9

(br), 34.0 (br), 23.2 (br); ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -153.0 (br); HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{FNNaO}_2^+$ 298.1214; Found 298.1212.

3-(3,5-Difluoro-4-methoxyphenyl)-2-fluoro-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethylpropanamide (3p): 17.2 mg, 59% (Condition A). Colorless oil. IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2980 (w), 2939 (w), 1658 (s), 1584 (m), 1516 (s), 1441 (s), 1379 (m), 1347 (m), 1319 (m), 1244 (m), 1212 (m), 1079 (m), 1030 (s), 1000 (s), 933 (w), 858 (w), 751 (w); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.84 – 6.76 (m, 2H), 3.97 (s, 3H), 3.68 (s, 3H), 3.30 (dd, $J = 23.6$, 14.4 Hz, 1H), 3.18 (d, $J = 1.6$ Hz, 3H), 2.98 (dd, $J = 22.4$, 14.4 Hz, 1H), 1.55 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 170.9 (br), 155.3 (dd, $J = 247.5$, 6.3 Hz), 135.4 (t, $J = 14.0$ Hz), 130.7 (t, $J = 8.7$ Hz), 114.5 (dd, $J = 16.6$, 6.8 Hz), 96.9 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 189.9$ Hz), 62.0 (t, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.3$ Hz), 61.6 (br), 43.0 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 22.3$ Hz), 34.1 (br), 23.1 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 20.5$ Hz); ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -129.4, -153.9 (br); HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{25}\text{NNaO}_3^+$ 302.1727; Found 302.1735.

3-(2,6-Difluorophenyl)-2-fluoro-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethylpropanamide (3q): 12.0 mg, 46% (Condition A). Colorless oil. IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2945 (w), 1660 (s), 1626 (m), 1593 (m), 1469 (s), 1379 (m), 1269 (m), 1233 (m), 1113 (s), 1085 (m), 1000 (s), 943 (m), 787 (s), 753 (m); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.22 (tt, $J = 8.4$, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 6.92 – 6.84 (m, 2H), 3.74 (s, 3H), 3.44 – 3.30 (m, 2H), 3.24 (s, 3H), 1.55 (d, $J = 22.2$ Hz, 3H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.6 (br), 162.2 (dd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 248.3$, 8.3 Hz), 129.1 (t, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 10.2$ Hz), 111.4 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 23.1$ Hz), 111.2 (dd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 21.6$, 4.9 Hz), 96.5 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 190.1$ Hz), 61.7 (br), 33.8 (br), 30.0 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 25.2$ Hz), 22.2 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 18.7$ Hz); ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -112.7, -152.7 (br); HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{F}_3\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 284.0869; Found 284.0875.

2-Fluoro-N-methoxy-N,2-dimethyl-3-(1-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)sulfonyl)indolin-5-yl)propanamide (3r): 23.6 mg, 50% (Condition A). Colorless oil. IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2941 (w), 1655 (m), 1487 (m), 1404 (m), 1361 (m), 1321 (s), 1169 (s), 1131 (s), 1108 (s), 1062 (s), 987 (m), 842 (m), 737 (m), 714 (s); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.90 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.70 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.55 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.07 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 6.98 (s, 1H), 3.93 (t, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 3.65 (s, 3H), 3.29 (dd, $J = 23.2$, 14.4 Hz, 1H), 3.11 (s, 3H), 3.02 (dd, $J = 23.4$, 14.4 Hz, 1H), 2.88 (t, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 1.53 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H); ^{13}C NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.5 (br), 140.6, 140.4, 134.9 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 33.3$ Hz), 131.9, 131.6 (br),

130.3, 127.9, 127.7, 126.3 (q, $J_{C-F} = 3.5$ Hz), 123.3 (q, $J_{C-F} = 272.8$ Hz), 114.6, 97.2 (brd, $J_{C-F} = 183.2$ Hz), 61.5 (br), 50.3, 43.1 (br), 33.9 (br), 27.9, 23.1 (br); ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -63.2, -153.0 (br); HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{23}\text{F}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}^+$ 475.1309; Found 475.1313.

2-Fluoro-*N*-methoxy-*N*,2-dimethyl-3-(1-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)sulfonyl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinolin-6-yl)propanamide (3s): 30.3 mg, 62% (Condition A). Colorless oil. IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2943 (w), 1657 (m), 1495 (w), 1358 (m), 1321 (s), 1167 (s), 1130 (s), 1061 (s), 1016 (m), 839 (m), 715 (s); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.72 – 7.62 (m, 5H), 7.07 (dd, $J = 8.8, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 6.89 (s, 1H), 3.85 – 3.78 (m, 2H), 3.69 (s, 3H), 3.29 (dd, $J = 22.4, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.14 (d, $J = 1.2$ Hz, 3H), 3.06 (dd, $J = 23.2, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 2.40 (t, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 2H), 1.67 – 1.60 (m, 2H), 1.55 (d, $J = 22.0$ Hz, 3H); ^{13}C NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.5 (br), 143.1, 135.2, 134.42 (q, $J_{C-F} = 33.0$ Hz), 132.7 (br), 131.4, 130.6, 129.0, 127.7, 126.19 (q, $J_{C-F} = 3.7$ Hz), 124.6, 123.30 (q, $J_{C-F} = 273.0$ Hz), 97.17 (d, $J_{C-F} = 188.3$ Hz), 61.5 (br), 47.0, 43.1 (br), 33.8 (br), 26.6, 23.1 (br), 21.7; ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -63.1, -152.3; HRMS (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{24}\text{F}_4\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_4\text{S}^+$ 511.1285; Found 511.1299.

2-Benzyl-2-fluoro-*N*-methoxy-*N*-methylbutanamide (3t): 10.2 mg, 43% (Condition B). Colorless oil. IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2978 (w), 2933 (w), 1655 (s), 1456 (m), 1381 (m), 1184 (m), 1115 (m), 1009 (m), 976 (m), 731 (m), 700 (s); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.32 – 7.20 (m, 5H), 3.58 (s, 3H), 3.32 (dd, $J = 29.1, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.07 (dd, $J = 19.6, 14.1$ Hz, 1H), 3.04 (brs, 3H), 2.27 – 1.97 (m, 1H), 1.92 – 1.78 (m, 1H), 0.97 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 3H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 170.3 (br), 135.4, 130.7, 128.3, 127.1, 100.7 (brd, $J_{C-F} = 194.3$ Hz), 61.2 (br), 43.1 (br), 35.0 (br), 30.4 (br), 7.89 (d, $J_{C-F} = 5.0$ Hz); ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -163.5 (br); HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{FNNaO}_2^+$ 262.1214; Found 262.1217.

2-Benzyl-2-fluoro-*N*-methoxy-*N*-methylpentanamide (3u): 11.1 mg, 44% (Condition B). Colorless oil. IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2968 (m), 2931 (m), 1658 (s), 1456 (m), 1380 (m), 1184 (m), 1113 (m), 1011 (m), 983 (m), 701 (s); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.30 – 7.20 (m, 5H), 3.57 (s, 3H), 3.32 (dd, $J = 29.4, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.14 – 2.93 (m, 4H), 2.19 – 1.93 (m, 1H), 1.78 (tdd, $J = 14.0, 11.8, 4.8$ Hz, 1H), 1.57 – 1.44 (m, 1H), 1.44 – 1.30 (m, 1H), 0.92 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 3H); ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.4 (br), 135.3, 130.7, 128.2, 127.1, 100.3 (brd, $J_{C-F} = 193.2$ Hz), 61.2 (br), 43.4 (br), 39.3 (br), 34.0 (br), 16.9 (brd, J_{C-F}

= 3.9 Hz), 14.2; ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -161.5 (br); HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{FNNaO}_2^+$ 276.1370; Found 276.1376.

2-Benzyl-8-chloro-2-fluoro-N-methoxy-N-methyloctanamide (3v): 13.3 mg, 40% (Condition B). Colorless oil. IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2933 (m), 1656 (m), 1455 (m), 1383 (m), 1086 (w), 988 (m), 734 (m), 701 (s); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.32 – 7.20 (m, 5H), 3.57 (s, 3H), 3.51 (t, J = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 3.32 (dd, J = 29.0, 14.2 Hz, 1H), 3.15 – 2.92 (m, 4H), 2.25 – 2.04 (m, 1H), 1.87 – 1.70 (m, 3H), 1.53 – 1.27 (m, 6H); ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.2, 135.2, 130.7, 128.3, 127.1, 100.2 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 192.8 Hz), 61.2 (br), 45.2, 43.3 (br), 36.8 (br), 34.0 (br), 32.6, 29.0, 26.8, 23.3 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 3.8 Hz); ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -161.7 (br); HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{25}\text{ClFNNaO}_2^+$ 352.1450; Found 352.1448.

2-Benzyl-2,6-difluoro-N-methoxy-N-methylhexanamide (3w): 12.3 mg, 43% (Condition B). Colorless oil. IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) 2966 (m), 2935 (m), 1655 (s), 1456 (m), 1383 (m), 1113 (m), 1012 (s), 982 (s), 739 (m), 702 (s); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.32 – 7.19 (m, 5H), 4.42 (dt, J = 47.2, 6.0 Hz, 2H), 3.57 (s, 3H), 3.33 (dd, J = 28.6, 14.2 Hz, 1H), 3.16 – 2.91 (m, 4H), 2.26 – 1.97 (m, 1H), 1.83 (tdd, J = 13.6, 11.4, 4.6 Hz, 1H), 1.77 – 1.55 (m, 3H), 1.55 – 1.40 (m, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.0 (br), 135.1, 130.7, 128.3, 127.2, 100.1 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 191.9 Hz), 83.9 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 164.5 Hz), 61.3 (br), 43.3 (br), 36.5 (br), 34.0 (br), 30.5 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 19.8 Hz), 19.5 (t, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 4.7 Hz); ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -162.0 (br), -218.5; HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{21}\text{F}_2\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 308.1433; Found 308.1430.

2-Benzyl-2-fluoro-N,6-dimethoxy-N-methylhexanamide (3x): 10.2 mg, 34% (Condition B). Colorless oil. IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2938 (m), 2870 (m), 1656 (s), 1455 (m), 1383 (m), 1190 (m), 1116 (s), 1016 (m), 971 (m), 730 (m), 701 (s); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.30 – 7.20 (m, 5H), 3.57 (s, 3H), 3.35 (t, J = 6.0 Hz, 2H), 3.39 – 3.25 (m, 1H), 3.31 (s, 3H), 3.14 – 2.94 (m, 4H), 2.25 – 1.96 (m, 1H), 1.83 (tdd, J = 13.8, 11.8, 4.4 Hz, 1H), 1.60 – 1.49 (m, 3H), 1.47 – 1.34 (m, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.4 (br), 135.3, 130.7, 128.3, 127.1, 100.2 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 191.2 Hz), 72.6, 61.2 (br), 58.7, 43.0 (br), 36.7 (br), 33.9 (br), 29.7, 20.2; ^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -161.4 (br); HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{24}\text{FNNaO}_3^+$ 320.1632; Found 320.1639.

2-Benzyl-2-fluoro-N-methoxy-N-methyl-6-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenoxy)hexanamide (3y): 17.5 mg, 41% (Condition B). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2934 (w), 1657 (m), 1615 (m), 1326 (s), 1256 (s), 1159 (m), 1109 (s), 1066 (s), 1010 (m), 984 (m), 836 (s), 701 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.52 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 2H), 7.33 – 7.19 (m, 5H), 6.92 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 2H), 3.97 (t, $J = 6.4$ Hz, 2H), 3.57 (s, 3H), 3.34 (dd, $J = 28.0, 14.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.17 – 2.93 (m, 4H), 2.33 – 2.05 (m, 1H), 1.97 – 1.73 (m, 3H), 1.73 – 1.61 (m, 1H), 1.61 – 1.46 (m, 1H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.0 (br), 161.5, 135.1, 130.7, 128.3, 127.2, 127.0 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.8$ Hz), 124.6 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 269.4$ Hz), 122.8 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 32.6$ Hz), 114.5, 100.1 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 194.5$ Hz), 67.9, 61.3 (br), 43.3 (br), 36.6 (br), 33.8 (br), 29.2, 20.2 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.8$ Hz); **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -61.5, -161.9; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{25}\text{F}_4\text{NNaO}_3^+$ 450.1663; Found 450.1664.

2-Benzyl-2,6,6,6-tetrafluoro-N-methoxy-N-methylhexanamide (3z): 13.1 mg, 41% (Condition B). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2928 (m), 1659 (s), 1462 (m), 1385 (m), 1285 (s), 1254 (s), 1140 (s), 999 (s), 971 (m), 702 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.33 – 7.25 (m, 3H), 7.24 – 7.18 (m, 2H), 3.59 (s, 3H), 3.34 (dd, $J = 27.4, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.07 (dd, $J = 20.0, 14.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.05 (brs, 3H), 2.32 – 2.00 (m, 3H), 1.88 – 1.60 (m, 3H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 170.8 (br), 134.7, 130.6, 128.4, 127.3, 127.0 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 276.4$ Hz), 99.8 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 197.5$ Hz), 61.5 (br), 43.0 (br), 37.0 (br), 35.6 (br), 33.8 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 28.6$ Hz), 16.4; **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -66.4, -162.8; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{19}\text{F}_4\text{NNaO}_2^+$ 344.1244; Found 344.1249.

6-Fluoro-N-methoxy-N-methyl-5,6,7,8,9,10-hexahydrobenzo[8]annulene-6-carboxamide (3aa): 10.6 mg, 40% (Condition A); 17.5 mg, 66% (Condition B); 172 mg, 65% (Condition B on 1.0 mmol scale). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2927 (m), 1655 (s), 1454 (m), 1381 (m), 1358 (m), 999 (m), 974 (m), 758 (s), 719 (s); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.23 – 7.03 (m, 4H), 3.76 (s, 3H), 3.63 (dd, $J = 33.6, 14.4$ Hz, 1H), 3.29 (s, 3H), 3.15 (dd, $J = 14.4, 12.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.87 – 2.72 (m, 2H), 2.15 – 1.98 (m, 1H), 1.93 – 1.80 (m, 1H), 1.77 – 1.45 (m, 4H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 171.7 (br), 142.2, 134.2, 131.7, 129.5, 127.6, 126.1, 99.0 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 189.9$ Hz), 61.7, 38.2 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 22.9$ Hz), 34.0 (br), 33.6, 32.8 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 22.0$ Hz), 32.2, 20.5 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 7.3$ Hz); **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -157.1 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{FNNaO}_2^+$ 288.1370; Found 288.1367.

6-Fluoro-*N*-methoxy-*N*-methyl-5,6,7,8,9,10-hexahydrobenzo[8]annulene-6-carboxamide (3ab): 10.6 mg, 40% (Condition A). Colorless oil. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2991 (w), 2943 (w), 1776 (m), 1716 (s), 1657 (s), 1419 (m), 1390 (s), 1329 (m), 1192 (m), 1173 (m), 1053 (m), 997 (m), 953 (m), 914 (m), 717 (s); **^1H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.86 (dd, $J = 5.4, 3.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.73 (dd, $J = 5.4, 3.0$ Hz, 2H), 4.32 – 4.15 (m, 2H), 3.72 (s, 3H), 3.24 (s, 3H), 1.64 (d, $J = 22.4$ Hz, 3H); **^{13}C NMR** (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 170.3 (br), 168.1, 134.1, 131.9, 123.5, 95.3 (d, $J = 192.4$ Hz), 61.7 (br), 42.8 (d, $J = 25.4$ Hz), 33.7 (br), 21.7 (d, $J = 23.4$ Hz); **^{19}F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -156.5 (br); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{FN}_2\text{NaO}_4^+$ 317.0908; Found 317.0912.

Substrates listed above did not give the desired rearrangement/fluorination products.

5. Mechanistic Study

5.1 Time Course

Fig. S1 Time Course of the Model Reaction

5.2 Control Experiment

To an 8 mL vial equipped with a stir bar was added C-H fluorination product **4a** (0.050 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Pd(OAc)₂ (1.1 mg, 0.0050 mmol, 0.10 equiv), AgOAc (4.2 mg, 0.025 mmol, 0.50 equiv), MesCO₂H (8.2 mg, 0.050 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Selectfluor (30.1 mg, 0.085 mmol, 1.7 equiv), and HFIP (0.5 mL). The vial was sealed, heated to 50 °C and allowed to stir for 36 h. Then, the mixture was diluted with EtOAc, filtered over a plug of silica gel (washed with 10 mL EtOAc), and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuo. The residue was analyzed by ¹H NMR and no rearrangement product **3a** was observed in the spectrum.

This result indicates that C-H fluorination product **4** is not an intermediate for the formation of rearrangement product **3**.

Scheme S7. Control Experiment Using **5** as the Starting Material

To an 8 mL vial equipped with a stir bar was added substrate **5** (0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Pd(OAc)₂ (2.3 mg, 0.010 mmol, 0.1 equiv), AgOAc (8.4 mg, 0.050 mmol, 0.5 equiv), MesCO₂H (16.4 mg, 0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Selectfluor (60.2 mg, 0.17 mmol, 1.7 equiv), and HFIP (1.0 mL). The vial was sealed, heated to 50 °C and allowed to stir for 48 h. Then, the mixture was diluted with EtOAc, filtered over a plug of silica gel (washed with 10 mL EtOAc), and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuo. The residue was analyzed by ¹H NMR and no product **3a** was observed in the spectrum.

This result indicates that the protonated compound **5** is not an intermediate for the formation of rearrangement product **3**.

5.3 KIE Experiment

Intermolecular competition

To an 8 mL vial equipped with a stir bar was added Pd(OAc)₂ (2.3 mg, 0.010 mmol, 0.1 equiv), AgOAc (8.4 mg, 0.050 mmol, 0.5 equiv), MesCO₂H (16.4 mg, 0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Selectfluor (60.2 mg, 0.17 mmol, 1.7 equiv). A solution of substrate **1a** (0.05 mmol, 0.5 equiv) in HFIP (0.5 mL) and a solution of **[D₆]-1a** (0.05 mmol, 0.5 equiv) in HFIP (0.5 mL) were added via syringe. The vial was sealed, heated to 50 °C and allowed to stir for 2 h. Then, the mixture was diluted with EtOAc, filtered over a plug of silica gel (washed with 10 mL EtOAc), and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuo. The ratio of **3a**:[D₅]-**3a** = 5.7 was determined by ¹H NMR using BnOAc as the internal standard.

Parallel experiments

To an 8 mL vial equipped with a stir bar was added substrate **1a** (0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Pd(OAc)₂ (2.3 mg, 0.010 mmol, 0.1 equiv), AgOAc (8.4 mg, 0.050 mmol, 0.5 equiv), MesCO₂H (16.4 mg, 0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Selectfluor (60.2 mg, 0.17 mmol, 1.7 equiv), and HFIP (1.0 mL). In another reaction vial, **[D₆]-1a** (0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv) was used instead of **1a**. The two vials were sealed, heated to 50 °C and allowed to stir for a certain time (less than 10% yield). Then the two vials were cooled by ice bath, diluted with EtOAc, filtered over a plug of silica gel (washed with 10 mL EtOAc), and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuo. The yields of **3a** and **[D₅]-3a** were determined by ¹H NMR using BnOAc as the internal standard. Thus, the KIE was found to be 4.0.

Fig. S2 Parallel experiments for KIE determination

Blue spots are related to the concentration of [D₅]-**3a**;
Orange spots are related to the concentration of **3a**.

[D₅]-**3a**. Colorless oil. **IR** (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2933 (w), 1657 (s), 1450 (m), 1379 (m), 1205 (m), 1120 (m), 980 (m), 737 (m), 702 (m); **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.33 – 7.21 (m, 5H), 3.66 (s, 3H), 3.14 (s, 3H); **¹³C NMR** (150 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.8 (br), 135.3, 130.7, 128.3, 127.1, 97.2 (brd, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 191.3 Hz), 61.4 (br), 43.7 (br), 34.1 (br), 22.6 (br); **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ -154.2; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₂H₁₁D₅FNNaO₂⁺ 253.1371; Found 253.1369.

Reversibility test experiment

To an 8 mL vial equipped with a stir bar was added substrate [D₆]-**1a** (0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Pd(OAc)₂ (2.3 mg, 0.010 mmol, 0.1 equiv), AgOAc (8.4 mg, 0.050 mmol, 0.5 equiv), MesCO₂H (16.4 mg, 0.10 mmol, 1.0 equiv), Selectfluor (60.2 mg, 0.17 mmol, 1.7 equiv), and HFIP (1.0 mL). The vial was sealed, heated to 50 °C and allowed to stir for 4.5 h. Then the mixture was diluted with EtOAc, filtered over a plug of silica gel (washed with 10 mL EtOAc), and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuo. The crude sample was analyzed by ¹H NMR. No proton-exchanged substrate **1a** was observed.

Fig. S3 NMR spectra for reversibility test experiment

5.4 Rearrangement/Fluorination Reaction of Pd Complexes

According to Yu's procedure,^[5] to a 10 mL vial equipped with a stir bar was added amide **6** (29.3 mg, 0.10 mmol), Pd(TFA)₂ (33.3 mg, 0.10 mmol), 2-picoline (18.6 mg, 0.20 mmol), and CsF (33.4 mg, 0.20 mmol), and DCE (2 mL). The vial was sealed, heated to 100 °C and allowed to stir for 20 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and filtered through a short pad of Celite. The residue was purified by preparative TLC using hexanes/EtOAc (1/2) as the eluent to afford **8** as a light yellow solid (18.3 mg, ~31%). The complex **8** is not a single compound and might contain the bisPd complexes based on NMR and HRMS results.

To an 8 mL vial equipped with a stir bar was added **8** (18.3 mg, ~0.031 mmol), 4,4'-di-*tert*-butyl-2,2'-bipyridine (9.3 mg, 0.034 mmol, 1.1 equiv), and DCM (1 mL). The vial was sealed and allowed to stir for 12 h. The mixture was purified by preparative TLC using hexane/EtOAc/DCM (1/2/2) as the eluent to afford **10a** as a yellow solid (18.5 mg, 89%).

10a. Yellow solid. **IR** (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 2962 (m), 1608 (s), 1495 (s), 1442 (m), 1410 (m), 1367 (m), 1334 (m), 1117 (m), 1038 (m), 997 (w), 839 (m), 698 (w); **$^1\text{H NMR}$** (400 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) δ 8.47 (d, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.99 (dd, $J = 6.5, 2.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.69 (dd, $J = 8.4, 1.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.48 (dd, $J = 6.0, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.27 (dd, $J = 8.4, 7.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.21 (dd, $J = 5.8, 1.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.14 (t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 1H), 6.87 (d, $J = 5.6$ Hz, 1H), 6.85 – 6.73 (m, 2H), 2.48 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.37 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 1.61 (s, 3H), 1.41 (s, 9H), 1.35 (s, 9H); **$^{13}\text{C NMR}$** (100 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) δ 188.3, 163.7, 163.5, 159.9 (ddd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 246.0, 14.8, 7.7$ Hz), 159.3 (ddd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 245.0, 15.0, 8.6$ Hz), 158.9 (dt, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 244.6, 14.8$ Hz), 156.3, 154.2, 150.4, 148.6, 148.0, 128.1, 126.8, 125.6, 124.2 (td, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 17.0, 4.7$ Hz), 123.9, 123.8, 119.5, 118.9, 100.6 (td, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 25.8, 3.6$ Hz), 100.5 (td, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 25.7, 3.6$ Hz), 52.7, 37.3, 35.8, 35.7, 30.4, 28.7; **$^{19}\text{F NMR}$** (377 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) δ -114.5 (apparent dd, $J = 7.2, 3.9$ Hz), -115.2 (apparent t, $J = 3.6$ Hz), -116.1 (apparent dd, $J = 7.1, 3.7$ Hz); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{37}\text{F}_3\text{N}_3\text{OPd}^+$ 666.1918; Found 666.1931.

10b (0.045 mmol scale reaction, 18.6 mg, 67%): Light yellow crystals. IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2929 (w), 1585 (s), 1495 (m), 1441 (m), 1394 (m), 1336 (w), 1117 (m), 1034 (m), 999 (m), 823 (m), 719 (m), 698 (m); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) δ 8.50 (d, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 1H), 8.05 (dd, $J = 6.0, 2.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.69 – 7.63 (m, 2H), 7.55 (dd, $J = 6.0, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.31 – 7.24 (m, 3H), 7.14 (tt, $J = 7.4, 1.6$ Hz, 1H), 6.86 (d, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 1H), 6.82 – 6.71 (m, 2H), 2.54 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 1H), 2.42 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 1H), 1.60 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) δ 188.1, 159.9 (ddd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 246.0, 14.9, 7.7$ Hz), 159.3 (ddd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 244.9, 14.8, 8.5$ Hz), 159.1 (dt, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 243.7, 14.6$ Hz), 156.2, 154.3, 149.9, 149.8, 149.2, 147.5, 147.2, 128.2, 127.5, 127.3, 126.7, 125.8, 123.8, 123.7 (td, $J = 17.1, 4.8$ Hz), 123.2, 100.7 (td, $J = 25.8, 3.8$ Hz), 100.6 (td, $J = 25.8, 10.3, 3.8$ Hz), 52.7, 38.1, 28.5; $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) δ -114.0 (dd, $J = 7.1, 4.1$ Hz), -114.4 (t, $J = 4.1$ Hz), -115.8 (dd, $J = 6.8, 3.8$ Hz); **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{19}\text{Cl}_2\text{F}_3\text{N}_3\text{OPd}^+$ 621.9887; Found 621.9889.

10c (0.024 mmol scale reaction, 10 mg, 68%): Light yellow crystals. IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}): 2927 (w), 1593 (s), 1562 (s), 1495 (s), 1441 (m), 1336 (m), 1252 (m), 1227 (m), 1117 (m), 1036 (s), 839 (m), 700 (w); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) δ 8.34 (d, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.68 (dd, $J = 8.2, 1.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.46 (dd, $J = 7.0, 2.6$ Hz, 2H), 7.27 (dd, $J = 8.4, 7.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.18 – 7.10 (m, 1H), 6.95 (dd, $J = 6.4, 2.8$ Hz, 1H), 6.82 – 6.70 (m, 3H), 6.67 (dd, $J = 6.2, 2.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.96 (s, 3H), 3.89 (s, 3H), 2.40 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.29 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 1.60 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (200 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) δ 188.3, 167.5, 167.4, 159.7 (ddd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 246.0, 15.2, 7.8$ Hz), 159.2 (ddd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 245.3, 14.9, 8.4$ Hz), 158.9 (dt, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 243.0, 15.0$ Hz), 157.4, 155.4, 150.2, 150.1, 149.6, 128.0, 126.6, 125.5, 124.1 (td, $J = 17.2, 5.0$ Hz), 111.3, 110.8, 109.6, 109.4, 100.5 (td, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 24.1, 3.5$ Hz), 100.3 (td, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 24.5, 3.6$ Hz), 56.6, 56.5, 52.5, 36.7, 28.5; $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) δ -114.5 (dd, $J = 7.1, 4.0$ Hz), -115.2 (t, $J = 3.8$ Hz), -116.1 (dd, $J = 7.1, 3.8$ Hz). **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{25}\text{F}_3\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{Pd}^+$ 614.0877; Found 614.0893.

Scheme S8. Reactions of Substrate 6 or Complex 10a with Selectfluor

To an 8 mL vial equipped with a stir bar was added the Pd-complex (1.0 equiv), Selectfluor (1.5 equiv), and HFIP (0.5 mL). The vial was sealed, heated to 50 °C and allowed to stir for 12 h. Then, the mixture was diluted with EtOAc, filtered over a plug of silica gel (washed with 10 mL EtOAc), and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuo. The yield of **7** was determined by ¹H NMR using BnOAc as the internal standard.

These results indicate that rearrangement/fluorination can proceed smoothly in different solvents. The solvent HFIP is beneficial for the C-H activation step of substrate **1**.

Scheme S9. Reactions of Complex 10a with Different [F⁺]

To an 8 mL vial equipped with a stir bar was added Pd-complex **10a** (1.0 equiv), [F⁺] (1.5 equiv), and HFIP (0.5 mL). The vial was sealed, heated to 50 °C and allowed to stir for 12 h. Then, the mixture was diluted with EtOAc, filtered over a plug of silica gel (washed with 10 mL EtOAc), and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuo. The yield of **7** was determined by ¹H NMR using BnOAc as the internal standard.

These results indicate that complex **10a** can be oxidized to Pd(IV) by different [F⁺]-reagents to trigger the rearrangement/fluorination.

2-Fluoro-2-methyl-3-phenyl-N-(2,4,6-trifluorophenyl)propanamide (7): White solid. m.p = 113.5 – 114.7 °C. **IR** ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹): 3286 (br), 1691 (m), 1608 (m), 1520 (s), 1493 (m), 1448 (m), 1176 (m), 1120 (s), 1097 (m), 1045 (s), 999 (m), 841 (m), 742 (w), 700 (m); **¹H NMR** (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.34 – 7.28 (m, 3H), 7.28 – 7.24 (m, 2H), 6.74 – 6.67 (m, 2H), 3.36 (dd, J = 32.0, 14.5 Hz, 1H), 3.13 (dd, J = 18.5, 14.5 Hz, 1H), 1.70 (d, J = 22.0 Hz, 3H); **¹³C NMR** (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.9 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 21.3 Hz), 161.2 (dt, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 250.0, 14.5 Hz), 158.3 (ddd, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 253.0, 15.0, 7.0 Hz), 134.4, 130.6, 128.4, 127.3, 109.4 (td, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 16.9, 5.2 Hz), 100.8 (m), 98.9 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 188.0 Hz), 44.1 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 21.0 Hz), 24.1 (d, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 23.3 Hz); **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -108.5 (t, J = 5.6 Hz), -114.1 (d, J = 5.6 Hz), -154.9; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) m/z: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₁₃F₄NNaO⁺ 334.0825; Found 334.0824.

5.5 Study of Stereochemistry

(R)-14 was prepared on a 0.30 g scale according to a procedure reported by Zakarian group.^[6] Known compound. [α]_D²² = -24.9 (c 1.1, benzene) (literature^[6] data for **(S)-14**: +24.2). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.34 – 7.24 (m, 4H), 7.22 – 7.17 (m, 1H), 2.10 – 1.99 (m, 1H), 1.99 – 1.88 (m, 1H), 0.79 (t, J = 7.4 Hz, 3H); **¹³C NMR** (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 183.0, 143.0, 128.5, 127.0, 126.4, 50.5, 31.8, 21.8, 9.2. The absolute configuration was also determined by X-ray single crystal analysis.

(R)-1t was prepared according to the general procedure A using **(R)-14** as the starting material (0.35 g, 94% yield). **HPLC** [Chiralpack IC, hexane/*i*-PrOH = 95/5, 230 nm, 1.0 mL/min. t_{R1} = 15.7 min (major), t_{R2} = 17.0 min (minor)], **ee** = 90%. [α]_D²⁵ = -9.7 (c 1.0, CH₂Cl₂).

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	15.682	MM	0.4214	1.73145e4	684.75299	94.8898
2	17.011	MM	0.3287	932.44629	47.27578	5.1102

Substrate (*R*)-**1t** (90% ee) was subjected to the condition B and provided (*S*)-**3t** (10.1 mg) in 42% yield. The ee of (*S*)-**3t** was determined to be 90%. HPLC [Chiralpack IB, hexane/*i*-PrOH = 95/5, 230 nm, 1.0 mL/min. t_{R1} = 5.7 min (major), t_{R2} = 6.4 min (minor)], ee = 90%. $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ = -13.7 (c 0.40, CH₂Cl₂). The absolute configuration was determined by X-ray single crystal analysis of the hydrolyzed product **15**.

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	5.700	MM	0.1462	3249.71655	370.42023	49.4166
2	6.475	MM	0.1657	3326.44873	334.50302	50.5834

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	5.662	MM	0.1638	6502.83545	661.63361	94.2848
2	6.426	MM	0.1295	394.17572	50.74761	5.7152

To a solution of (*S*)-**3t** (30.1 mg, 0.126 mmol, 1.0 equiv) in methanol (5 mL) was added KOH (35.3 mg, 5.0 equiv) and the reaction mixture was heated to 60 °C and allowed to stir for 12 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to rt and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was diluted with water, acidified until pH = 1 with HCl (3 M), and extracted twice with ethyl acetate. The combined organic extracts were dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. Flash chromatography on silica gel (hexanes:ethyl acetate 3:1) afforded **15** as colorless crystals (24.0 mg, 97%). The absolute configuration was determined by X-ray single crystal analysis.

(S)-2-Benzyl-2-fluorobutanoic acid (15): Colorless crystals. m.p = 71.5 – 72.5 °C. [α]_D²⁵ = -17.7 (*c* 0.45, CH₂Cl₂). **IR** (ν_{max} , cm⁻¹): 2939 (br), 1730 (s), 1456 (m), 1263 (m), 1155 (m), 741 (m), 700 (s); **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.32 – 7.26 (m, 3H), 7.25 – 7.20 (m, 2H), 3.21 (dd, *J* = 29.2, 14.4 Hz, 1H), 3.13 (dd, *J* = 19.4, 14.4 Hz, 1H), 2.13 – 1.81 (m, 2H), 1.01 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H); **¹³C NMR** (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 175.1 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 27.0 Hz), 134.2, 130.4, 128.5, 127.4, 98.4 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 188.0 Hz), 43.0 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 21.3 Hz), 30.2 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 22.4 Hz), 7.7 (d, *J*_{C-F} = 4.0 Hz); **¹⁹F NMR** (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -165.8; **HRMS** (ESI/QTOF) *m/z*: [M + H₋₁]⁻ Calcd for C₁₁H₁₂FO₂⁻ 195.0827; Found 195.0831.

6. Computational Study

6.1 Method

Computations were performed with the Gaussian16 (revision A.03)⁷ software package at the M06^{8,9}/Def2-SVP¹⁰ level of density functional theory in the gas-phase. An exhaustive manual conformational search has been performed and the lowest energy pathways are reported. Stationary points were characterized on the basis of their vibrational frequencies (minima with zero imaginary frequencies, transition states with one imaginary frequency). Intermediates were obtained from IRC computations¹¹ ensuring TSs and minima are connected. Free energy corrections were taken from the M06/Def2-SVP computations. Single point energies were obtained using the PBE0^{12,13} functional appended with a density-dependent dispersion correction, -dDsC,¹⁴⁻¹⁷ with the TZ2P basis set as implemented in ADF.^{18,19} Solvation corrections were determined at the PBE0-dDsC/TZ2P level using the COSMO-RS solvation model (in HFIP),²⁰ also implemented in ADF. Reported free energies include the PBE0-dDsC/TZ2P electronic energies, M06/Def2-SVP free energy corrections, and PBE0-dDsC/TZ2P solvation corrections. Molecular structures were generated using CYLView program with C-H bonds hidden for clarity.²¹

6.2 Results and Discussion

An energetically viable reaction pathway was identified by the DFT calculations. Following coordination with Pd(OAc)₂, the substrate undergoes β -C(sp³)-H activation with a barrier of only 15.1 kcal/mol, yielding Pd(II) intermediate **A** after release of a molecule of acetic acid (Fig. S4). Oxidation to Pd(IV) intermediate **B** with Selectfluor is thermodynamically favorable, being exergonic by 25.8 kcal/mol. The key rearrangement step proceeds via concerted 1,2-positional interchange between the phenyl and fluoride groups with a very small barrier (3.2 kcal/mol). **TS**_{1,2} was confirmed to directly connect intermediate **B** with Pd(OAc)-associated product (*S*)-**3t**. Analysis of the corresponding potential energy surface (PES, Fig. S5) shows the presence of a hidden intermediate (an inflection point on the PES) between **TS**_{1,2} and the product. The **TS**_{1,2} $\rightarrow$ Pd(OAc)·(*S*)-**3t** process can be split into two steps. The shift of phenyl group and the decoordination of Pd(IV) are energetically downhill by 2.6 kcal/mol. This process is associated with decrease of the β -C-Ph distance and concurrent lengthening of the β -C-Pd bond. In the second step, fluoride transfer and regeneration of Pd(II) catalyst is significantly exergonic by 24.2 kcal/mol and associated with significant shortening of the α -C-F bond. The overall reaction is exergonic by 57.6 kcal/mol with C-H bond cleavage being the rate-determining step, consistent with the results of KIE experiments. We note that TS leading to intermediate **C** (*cf* Scheme 1c) was not localized.

Figure S4. DFT Calculations. Reaction profile for the conversion of (*R*)-**1t** to (*S*)-**3t**, showing the structure of the transition state **TS_{1,2}** for the concerted migration of the phenyl and fluoride groups (hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity).

We noted that the computed energy span of the reaction (15.1 kcal/mol) is lower than expected given the experimental reaction conditions. This underestimation could come from a number of reasons, primarily from the level of theory. PBE0-dDsC/TZ2P has been found to occasionally underestimate reaction barriers. The single-point energy computations were repeated at the SMD(HFIP)/PBE0-D3(BJ)/Def2-TZVP level and the barrier for C–H activation was computed to be 18.8 kcal/mol. Other sources of error could include the treatment of entropy: herein, free energy corrections were calculated using the relatively simple rigid-rotor harmonic oscillator approximation. Using the quasi-harmonic approximation further increases the barrier to 19.2 kcal/mol. Furthermore, geometry optimisation were performed in the gas phase, and solvent effects are only account for using implicit models at the single-point level."

Fig. S5 IRC profile of $\text{TS}_{1,2}$ at the M06/Def2-SVP level.

Our computational studies identified that the reaction follows a highly asynchronous concerted transition state for 1,2-positional interchange between the phenyl and fluoride groups where Ph shift and decoordination of Pd(IV) proceeds earlier than α -C-F bond formation. IRC computations (Figure S5) at the M06/Def2-SVP level show the presence of an inflection point on the potential energy surface between $\text{TS}_{1,2}$ and Pd(OAc)·(S)-3t. In the first step of the $\text{TS}_{1,2} \rightarrow \text{Pd(OAc)·(S)-3t}$ process, the β -C-Ph distance decreases from 1.95 Å in $\text{TS}_{1,2}$ (vs. 2.30 Å in **B**) to 1.55 Å in the inflection point. Concurrently, the β -C-Pd bond increases from 2.48 Å in $\text{TS}_{1,2}$ (vs. 2.11 Å in **B**) to 3.11 Å in the inflection point. During second step, the fluoride transfer with concurrent regeneration of Pd(II) catalyst, the α -C-F distance decreases from 2.39 Å in the inflection point (3.06 Å in **B**, 2.98 Å in $\text{TS}_{1,2}$) to 1.46 Å in the product. Simultaneously, the Pd-F bond length increases from 1.97 Å (1.91 Å in **B**, 1.92 Å in $\text{TS}_{1,2}$) to 2.15 Å in Pd(OAc)·(S)-3t.

Figure S6 shows an alternative mechanism for the conversion of (*R*)-1t to (S)-3t. Following oxidation of intermediate **A** to Pd(IV) intermediate **B**, reductive elimination to yield Pd(OAc)-coordinated (S)-4t occurs with a barrier of 22.4 kcal/mol. A transition state connecting Pd(OAc)·(S)-4t to Pd(OAc)·(S)-3t, TS_{DR} , was then located. TS_{DR} lies 15.0 kcal/mol above Pd(OAc)·(S)-4t and is highly polarized, with two short C-C bonds and two long C-F bonds (2.6 Å). In contrast, the Pd-F bond length is only slightly longer (1.95 Å) than in intermediate **B-Cf2** (1.91 Å). Analysis of the NBO charges at the M06/Def2-SVP level reveals that the Pd(OAc)F moiety is essentially neutral (-0.09), whereas the rest of the substrate bears the +1 charge. Overall, the stepwise mechanism in Figure S6 has a higher energy span (22.4 kcal/mol) than the concerted mechanism proceeding *via* $\text{TS}_{1,2}$ (15.1 kcal/mol) and is deemed unfavorable. Additionally,

KIE experiments suggest that C–H cleavage is the turnover-limiting step, which is in disagreement with the Figure S6 mechanism (reductive elimination rate-limiting).

Fig. S6 Reaction profile for the conversion of (R)-1t to (S)-3t, showing the structure of the transition state TS_{DR} for the dyotropic rearrangement of Pd(OAc)·(S)-4t to Pd(OAc)·(S)-3t (hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity).

7. Optimized Geometries

Coordinates and Energies of the Stationary Points

Pd(OAc)₂:

15

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -4.04438, thermal correction = 0.06495, solvation energy = -0.01598

O	1.75845400	1.07978600	0.01696200
C	2.42455000	0.00006300	0.01700300
C	3.90761400	-0.00029900	-0.01191500
O	1.75825200	-1.07959100	0.01698800
Pd	-0.00000800	0.00012400	0.00000600
O	-1.75843900	1.07969600	-0.01689600
C	-2.42453000	-0.00005900	-0.01702800
C	-3.90758400	-0.00024000	0.01178600
O	-1.75827200	-1.07970900	-0.01691400
H	4.29832600	0.90830900	0.46496900
H	4.24217900	-0.00863300	-1.06102700
H	4.29777000	-0.90212800	0.47821700
H	-4.29807900	0.90672300	-0.46841800
H	-4.24225800	-0.00444900	1.06089000
H	-4.29785200	-0.90375500	-0.47511300

(R)-1t:

35

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -9.29234, thermal correction = 0.25392, solvation energy = -0.02492

O	-0.92636500	-0.34132900	2.25344900
C	-1.02744900	-0.07621700	1.07284600
N	-2.05182900	-0.68154300	0.35918200
O	-2.02825700	-0.70565900	-1.02229400
C	-3.17873400	-0.10579900	-1.57320200
C	-2.74528300	-1.81959400	0.91962600
C	-0.02412200	0.91891100	0.42609900
C	-0.52036100	1.67714600	-0.82361600
C	0.40722300	2.78567200	-1.29147000

C	1.20756200	0.06997300	0.08514200
C	1.12189700	-0.91490500	-0.91075600
C	2.22141400	-1.70155900	-1.24071800
C	3.43666000	-1.52433000	-0.58282700
C	3.53366300	-0.55818100	0.41306400
C	2.43021200	0.22641400	0.74577300
C	0.27225700	1.94239800	1.52401500
H	-3.04465700	-0.13310800	-2.66379000
H	-3.29011100	0.94168400	-1.24355100
H	-4.09711000	-0.66404600	-1.31720100
H	-2.72813100	-1.73036000	2.01113200
H	-2.25548900	-2.76412400	0.62481000
H	-3.79066000	-1.83448100	0.57479000
H	-0.66413400	0.97418500	-1.65480500
H	-1.51814200	2.10170000	-0.59839100
H	1.44150300	2.41863900	-1.40870800
H	0.43372400	3.64419400	-0.60263500
H	0.08443500	3.16958700	-2.27174900
H	0.17259700	-1.07648900	-1.43039700
H	2.12539600	-2.46324400	-2.02044100
H	4.30233700	-2.14055400	-0.84240800
H	4.47856500	-0.41064300	0.94464000
H	2.53617000	0.96890900	1.53982200
H	1.09004400	2.61687700	1.23254900
H	0.53717800	1.44974200	2.46810800
H	-0.62338600	2.55867400	1.71085800

HOAc:

8

$E(\text{PBE0-dDsC}) = -2.15100$, thermal correction = 0.03485, solvation energy = -0.01305

C	-0.09300000	0.12412800	0.00011400
C	1.38467100	-0.10401900	0.00000100
H	1.91058300	0.85756200	-0.00076400
H	1.67251200	-0.69283900	0.88381600

H	1.67228600	-0.69422200	-0.88295700
O	-0.64472700	1.19086900	-0.00011400
O	-0.76718200	-1.03878300	0.00002000
H	-1.71014100	-0.80784200	-0.00003200

OAc:

7

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -2.01936, thermal correction = 0.02089, solvation energy = -0.16886

C	0.22030000	0.00210400	-0.00004400
C	-1.34282700	-0.06648400	-0.00002000
H	-1.72164200	-1.10344400	-0.00079800
H	-1.73719900	0.46799300	0.88362500
H	-1.73737400	0.46949000	-0.88267500
O	0.81344000	-1.09249700	0.00001500
O	0.67798100	1.16152700	0.00001400

HFIP:

12

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -3.21482, thermal correction = 0.02891, solvation energy = -0.00730

C	-0.00290400	0.54701700	-0.48714900
H	-0.00188000	0.47350700	-1.59610000
C	-1.28584900	-0.13645300	-0.03008500
C	1.26714400	-0.16288900	-0.02460200
F	-1.48147300	-0.00999000	1.26989100
F	-2.32014800	0.40338300	-0.66086700
F	-1.24728600	-1.43173900	-0.32760000
F	1.28100600	-0.38969300	1.27748300
F	1.44031700	-1.31215000	-0.65943500
F	2.30827000	0.62604000	-0.31480000
O	-0.05016300	1.84171000	-0.00841800
H	0.70666000	2.33410800	-0.34758600

Selectfluor:

25

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -5.47601, thermal correction = 0.18351, solvation energy = -0.27860

C	-1.75134700	1.27358400	-0.13718900
N	0.56959500	0.41005300	0.00182000
C	-0.28780300	1.64708300	0.12139000
H	-2.10731100	1.52851900	-1.14749400
H	-2.44080600	1.71526700	0.59861100
H	0.06799700	2.39102800	-0.60816400
H	-0.12970400	2.05890000	1.13096000
C	-1.18909800	-0.89832400	-1.15594100
H	-1.19957200	-1.97705600	-0.93515800
H	-1.81264200	-0.71668900	-2.04486900
C	0.21355400	-0.29953000	-1.28315200
H	0.97222900	-1.07529800	-1.46764500
H	0.28383900	0.44513500	-2.09233600
C	0.26284800	-0.49946900	1.16997300
H	0.78230100	-1.45226200	0.98903600
H	0.69464000	-0.05139300	2.07856100
C	-1.25531600	-0.66590500	1.29318600
H	-1.55814700	-1.71389800	1.44104800
H	-1.71212400	-0.05460000	2.08704300
F	-3.16659600	-0.54975800	-0.00470900
N	-1.85425300	-0.21352400	-0.00165900
C	2.03755000	0.84025700	-0.00337600
H	2.18102200	1.44971700	-0.91039100
H	2.18517800	1.46123400	0.89528400
Cl	3.12369000	-0.51898000	-0.00015200

Selectfluor-F:

24

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -5.72738, thermal correction = 0.18065, solvation energy = -0.08350

C	-2.16865000	1.00259800	-0.06668700
N	0.22389900	0.36336600	0.00116200
C	-0.72823600	1.53690700	0.09167000
H	-2.59802800	1.32147300	-1.02936700

H	-2.81206600	1.41649700	0.72498100
H	-0.43693100	2.25206200	-0.69365600
H	-0.54512400	2.00828100	1.07071400
C	-1.48947300	-0.99492900	-1.15509000
H	-1.44085700	-2.09004300	-1.05009300
H	-2.06649700	-0.78656900	-2.06930800
C	-0.07375000	-0.39369400	-1.27453100
H	0.71994600	-1.14450300	-1.39742500
H	0.02026500	0.34064300	-2.09127300
C	-0.02703000	-0.54282100	1.18756700
H	0.61976600	-1.42135400	1.05062400
H	0.32300900	-0.00134700	2.08094700
C	-1.53131800	-0.88780900	1.21750300
H	-1.66626700	-1.97386200	1.33585900
H	-2.02580500	-0.40828600	2.07691200
N	-2.17165400	-0.44249000	-0.00281900
C	1.61810900	0.90754300	0.00075800
H	1.72829200	1.53067100	-0.89992000
H	1.72886200	1.53193700	0.90062400
Cl	2.85222400	-0.34050000	-0.00030300

Pd(OAc)₂·(R)-**1t**:

50

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -13.32881, thermal correction = 0.34116, solvation energy = -0.05822

Pd	-1.56621200	-0.05344800	-0.00536200
O	-3.13359800	-1.14395500	0.55486200
C	-2.90990500	-2.41934800	0.63070900
C	-4.15431400	-3.20976900	0.94459100
O	-1.82211600	-2.95850600	0.45943000
H	-0.19889700	-0.21605200	2.06742400
H	3.50182400	0.29239500	1.47359500
H	2.18374800	0.59289800	2.61145500
H	-0.44227700	-1.38462400	0.59567900
H	0.49862200	-1.82604200	1.87729400

C	1.54705000	-0.28389100	0.73689500
C	0.27294100	-0.89337500	1.33676600
C	2.57694800	-0.13917400	1.87968900
O	0.05976700	1.06357300	-0.58907600
C	1.11922200	1.03289400	0.06414600
C	1.27094700	3.35573300	-0.62088200
H	1.43218600	3.24371300	-1.70523300
H	0.19344700	3.44781500	-0.41699000
N	1.78955400	2.20493400	0.10435400
H	-4.72179300	-2.73516300	1.75765000
H	-4.80649600	-3.21544600	0.05770000
H	-3.88980700	-4.24231400	1.20670200
O	-2.83720000	1.13373400	-0.97029500
C	-2.76153800	2.38793700	-0.63188900
O	-2.01483900	2.85973600	0.21096600
C	-3.73339800	3.23499800	-1.42099700
H	-4.76076700	2.88383200	-1.24396300
H	-3.64088100	4.28738600	-1.12256500
H	-3.53957600	3.12775200	-2.49864800
O	3.13632100	2.22880600	0.37298000
C	3.44488600	3.02877100	1.49896800
H	4.52485100	2.91080000	1.65959600
H	3.22801500	4.09526100	1.31659500
H	2.89671600	2.69369800	2.39520300
H	1.79384900	4.25202700	-0.26294000
C	2.92566600	-1.43693500	2.58772100
H	2.10628600	-1.82848400	3.21012400
H	3.20764500	-2.22363500	1.86801600
H	3.78539800	-1.28378500	3.25736100
C	2.12081400	-1.14425300	-0.39722700
C	1.54864600	-2.35814200	-0.79281600
C	3.26973600	-0.69573100	-1.06447100
C	2.12352700	-3.10577500	-1.82119300
H	0.64145700	-2.74842000	-0.32050100

C	3.83722800	-1.44200100	-2.09175300
H	3.72500600	0.25891600	-0.78054200
C	3.26669000	-2.65490900	-2.47232600
H	1.66069500	-4.05235800	-2.11379100
H	4.73161100	-1.07064700	-2.60030200
H	3.71047700	-3.24472800	-3.27930200

TS_{CH}:

50

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -13.31691, thermal correction = 0.33732, solvation energy = 0.05509, imaginary frequency = -1532.2235 cm⁻¹

Pd	1.50120100	-0.01930600	-0.02231400
O	3.07890600	-1.20340900	-0.53666200
C	2.76498700	-2.41442100	-0.71588100
C	3.87770000	-3.39457600	-0.92327300
O	1.57789200	-2.82650200	-0.71294900
H	0.19466100	-0.20684000	-2.11561600
H	-3.44639300	0.13461700	-1.43789900
H	-2.15234500	0.47085300	-2.59643200
H	0.79958300	-1.67293100	-0.70876800
H	-0.35667300	-1.81321300	-1.73719400
C	-1.45661300	-0.29166600	-0.69305000
C	-0.13139300	-0.83872600	-1.26862200
C	-2.49800100	-0.25447300	-1.83484000
O	-0.04823900	1.15515900	0.57139700
C	-1.10338800	1.06853600	-0.08597000
C	-1.31527300	3.42177200	0.46784200
H	-1.52586800	3.38926800	1.54909100
H	-0.22924600	3.49982900	0.30723500
N	-1.79955900	2.21984300	-0.19419800
H	4.81401400	-2.88339100	-1.17763000
H	4.02349900	-3.95720400	0.01177000
H	3.59915700	-4.11826100	-1.70143100
O	2.78893900	1.13237800	1.00628200
C	2.76689500	2.38698100	0.67770600

O	2.06872900	2.88758700	-0.19360600
C	3.72599900	3.21103700	1.50747200
H	4.74906700	2.82368200	1.38910000
H	3.68679900	4.26410600	1.19922600
H	3.47283500	3.12069500	2.57469000
O	-3.14653800	2.19122400	-0.46489400
C	-3.47305600	2.90841800	-1.63996300
H	-4.55445000	2.77544100	-1.77722500
H	-3.25845200	3.98590500	-1.53571800
H	-2.93603300	2.51257200	-2.51816000
H	-1.81876900	4.28963200	0.02187100
C	-2.76930300	-1.59564300	-2.49282800
H	-1.92365900	-1.96128500	-3.09577600
H	-3.00975000	-2.36956900	-1.74463000
H	-3.63259100	-1.51803100	-3.17112300
C	-2.00083800	-1.12047000	0.47687800
C	-1.43453200	-2.33370900	0.87832500
C	-3.13119400	-0.65272400	1.16269300
C	-1.98942100	-3.05930700	1.93299200
H	-0.54937900	-2.73814700	0.38095300
C	-3.67950100	-1.37487500	2.21744900
H	-3.59098500	0.29697500	0.86847800
C	-3.11032800	-2.58565700	2.60642400
H	-1.53028800	-4.00680400	2.22909300
H	-4.55837800	-0.98655200	2.74024100
H	-3.53863800	-3.15667700	3.43502700

A:

42

$E(\text{PBE0-dDsC}) = -11.18850$, thermal correction = 0.28475, solvation energy = -0.03946

C	-1.11269500	0.02753300	0.78435600
C	0.25494300	-0.25973600	1.42518300
H	0.19734600	-1.17823700	2.04089400
H	0.61138100	0.56817000	2.05753100

C	-1.20235400	-1.04069500	-0.30909000
O	-0.14049700	-1.39774000	-0.85442600
C	-2.38614500	-2.44253800	-1.94877900
H	-2.97303600	-3.35651300	-1.77104200
H	-1.36189300	-2.72199600	-2.21805400
N	-2.34095800	-1.63042900	-0.75167200
Pd	1.60685700	-0.65639300	0.01847100
O	3.31220900	0.14042000	0.85848500
C	4.07000600	-0.20205400	-0.11606300
O	3.59550300	-0.80788900	-1.09766900
C	5.52529500	0.13637500	-0.01984200
H	5.64807000	1.19403700	0.25549300
H	5.98469200	-0.46080000	0.78281300
H	6.03571300	-0.07421900	-0.96827600
H	-2.84333800	-1.87029300	-2.77212400
C	-2.20102100	-0.00683600	1.88028000
O	-3.56326000	-1.14585600	-0.35809400
C	-4.29435900	-2.09500700	0.39418900
H	-3.71909100	-2.44684000	1.26713800
H	-5.19744400	-1.57239000	0.73734500
H	-4.59722000	-2.96077300	-0.22013400
C	-1.14941400	1.37231800	0.03846300
C	-0.05152900	2.23957500	0.00279700
C	-2.32124100	1.76082300	-0.62735700
C	-0.12943900	3.46054600	-0.66592400
H	0.88983200	1.96292600	0.48596400
C	-2.39600600	2.97792500	-1.29864600
H	-3.19151000	1.09750600	-0.62808600
C	-1.29958500	3.83667400	-1.31755800
H	0.74272800	4.12053900	-0.67770500
H	-3.32122300	3.25560100	-1.81230200
H	-1.35604500	4.79424200	-1.84316800
H	-3.17955400	0.24713900	1.44655900
H	-2.28225600	-1.04483600	2.25710800

C	-1.92009200	0.93288800	3.03919100
H	-1.73364300	1.96023100	2.68324800
H	-2.78388300	0.97253600	3.72037400
H	-1.04814700	0.62284200	3.63487000

B:

43

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -11.13717, thermal correction = 0.28829, solvation energy = -0.07628

C	-0.88478100	0.01969700	0.50870800
C	-1.13739600	-0.63663600	1.89221900
H	-0.74050800	-1.66292200	1.86331600
H	-2.22996000	-0.71876500	2.01312300
C	0.38936400	0.82978100	0.40400100
H	0.70902500	1.36293600	1.31060100
H	0.52301900	1.40639800	-0.52150300
C	-0.77293400	-1.08274800	-0.52898600
O	0.36101000	-1.35923700	-1.01698400
C	-1.81137400	-2.79140900	-1.96353600
H	-2.06863800	-3.78007700	-1.55523600
H	-0.80372300	-2.83508100	-2.39244000
N	-1.82876500	-1.78248300	-0.92059200
Pd	1.94207500	-0.53643900	-0.02473200
F	1.48546800	-1.69319600	1.41936200
O	3.53483300	0.49122200	0.67962600
C	3.68575300	1.09559800	-0.43815200
O	2.80459900	0.82444300	-1.31671300
C	4.81569300	2.00535600	-0.68746600
H	5.14544300	2.47250900	0.25008600
H	5.65606400	1.41526000	-1.08757300
H	4.54085600	2.75959100	-1.43673300
H	-2.53946800	-2.50597900	-2.73737600
O	-3.05176100	-1.36541900	-0.47874300
C	-3.74491300	-2.37683500	0.24732200
H	-4.60321700	-1.86554500	0.70149300

H	-4.11703200	-3.17271400	-0.41834100
H	-3.10695700	-2.80898900	1.03633200
C	-1.87352200	1.12825200	0.13918600
C	-1.94090700	1.56341600	-1.19641300
C	-2.68870000	1.74939100	1.09420600
C	-2.82610000	2.56305800	-1.57434000
H	-1.30320500	1.09975300	-1.95987900
C	-3.56663000	2.75948300	0.71439400
H	-2.65805800	1.44134000	2.14153300
C	-3.64032500	3.16706700	-0.61622500
H	-2.88010900	2.87614400	-2.61992100
H	-4.20239000	3.23165000	1.46765900
H	-4.33287100	3.96078200	-0.90797800
C	-0.51064600	0.05976800	3.08533400
H	0.58357500	-0.05825500	3.07591000
H	-0.75234200	1.13353400	3.15044100
H	-0.86774600	-0.40675300	4.01505100

TS_{1,2}:

43

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -11.12307, thermal correction = 0.28640, solvation energy = -0.08345, imaginary frequency = -305.3994 cm⁻¹

C	-0.97122800	0.00063900	0.51732000
C	-1.22107500	-0.58401900	1.92385100
H	-0.89850400	-1.63556600	1.88846200
H	-2.31020800	-0.58072700	2.09897000
C	0.06103900	1.02007700	0.35440200
H	0.34303500	1.64827700	1.20592700
H	0.39837000	1.34537900	-0.63347600
C	-0.80321100	-1.08089400	-0.53530500
O	0.30011600	-1.24112400	-1.09925000
C	-1.82839300	-2.87066100	-1.87923800
H	-2.05552300	-3.85983600	-1.45473100
H	-0.82555000	-2.89663700	-2.32127400
N	-1.84263300	-1.85241100	-0.84792600

S55

Pd	1.96145500	-0.51871100	-0.05580100
F	1.34119000	-1.68722800	1.33941500
O	3.62037400	0.37229700	0.70009700
C	3.79723200	1.02084100	-0.38369500
O	2.90006600	0.85796500	-1.27263900
C	4.98331100	1.87227700	-0.59695400
H	5.35829800	2.25640400	0.36082900
H	5.77664800	1.25761000	-1.05152400
H	4.74771200	2.68981900	-1.29109100
H	-2.57394000	-2.61463300	-2.64732700
O	-3.06045600	-1.47431700	-0.35050200
C	-3.68841900	-2.50935000	0.40147100
H	-4.54821400	-2.03202300	0.88841100
H	-4.05550300	-3.31893900	-0.25006200
H	-3.00486300	-2.91713900	1.16444000
C	-1.86983200	1.17961900	0.10203700
C	-2.08019400	1.46269100	-1.26970500
C	-2.53629500	1.96151500	1.07179000
C	-2.96135600	2.45652300	-1.65442000
H	-1.54450100	0.88697600	-2.03341900
C	-3.40764900	2.96353600	0.67701300
H	-2.37776900	1.77144200	2.13575600
C	-3.62576200	3.20798800	-0.68096700
H	-3.13013900	2.65672200	-2.71488600
H	-3.92557400	3.56047800	1.43128200
H	-4.31562400	3.99982200	-0.98503200
C	-0.46938900	0.06986700	3.06719700
H	0.61486400	-0.05818900	2.92991500
H	-0.69332300	1.14087500	3.20542500
H	-0.73241100	-0.42997000	4.01058100

Pd(OAc) $\cdot$ (S)-**3t**:

43

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -11.17863, thermal correction = 0.28738, solvation energy = -0.07162

C	-0.51030900	0.60750600	0.61951100
Pd	2.23811600	0.03919400	-0.04927000
C	-0.98890600	-0.65805400	-1.49317400
H	-0.15157400	-1.34089100	-1.25759800
F	0.75262900	0.92128400	-1.32366600
O	3.67575700	-0.76635800	1.09375600
C	4.50138400	-0.73824000	0.11735100
O	4.00981900	-0.27265100	-0.96113200
C	5.89724500	-1.18010600	0.24546700
H	6.50987400	-0.32381000	0.57038300
H	5.97928400	-1.96787800	1.00652000
H	6.27566000	-1.52511200	-0.72619800
C	-2.27695300	-1.24455800	-0.98875200
C	-2.27532500	-2.05473200	0.15069600
C	-3.48962800	-0.96581600	-1.62406300
C	-3.46963500	-2.55056200	0.66753300
H	-1.32305800	-2.30820600	0.63526200
C	-4.68458400	-1.46141800	-1.11000600
H	-3.49683500	-0.35919900	-2.53710200
C	-4.67712500	-2.24641200	0.04168400
H	-3.45738600	-3.19266800	1.55291400
H	-5.62798700	-1.24344500	-1.61790900
H	-5.61532200	-2.64089900	0.44105600
H	-1.00270000	-0.53558600	-2.58975700
O	0.58032500	0.25045400	1.12957600
C	-1.36334400	1.88854800	-1.49949800
H	-1.20392600	1.81932100	-2.59024800
H	-2.44099900	1.73272500	-1.34039300
C	-0.89552800	3.23706300	-0.98519000
H	0.14787100	3.43776600	-1.27023500
H	-1.50858300	4.04725000	-1.40454700
H	-0.95680100	3.31381000	0.11334300
N	-1.55549800	0.79700700	1.42263800
C	-1.56296300	0.41774500	2.82534300

H	-1.74180200	1.29212800	3.46827200
H	-2.36258400	-0.32591700	2.96868000
H	-0.58987300	-0.01788000	3.07897000
O	-2.77828200	0.99895900	0.84943100
C	-3.44938800	2.15017600	1.34994300
H	-4.32448000	2.27255900	0.69850300
H	-3.79913200	1.99876500	2.38409300
H	-2.81303500	3.04873900	1.29199600
C	-0.62761500	0.70913700	-0.90819300

(S)-3t:

35

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -9.35339, thermal correction = 0.24636, solvation energy = -0.02704

C	-1.33590400	0.48562800	-0.86131800
C	-0.12041900	-1.70363700	-0.87221600
H	-0.25349900	-1.69582700	-1.96784400
F	-2.42606200	-1.55723400	-0.94585100
C	1.21821100	-1.13828600	-0.50550600
C	1.82417500	-0.17605700	-1.31852300
C	1.86652700	-1.52606100	0.67053000
C	3.03127200	0.41135700	-0.94811000
H	1.33016700	0.12090700	-2.25216400
C	3.07332200	-0.94205000	1.04487000
H	1.41259000	-2.29836200	1.30261400
C	3.65541000	0.03541900	0.23936700
H	3.49194600	1.16439800	-1.59494400
H	3.56855300	-1.25690100	1.96843300
H	4.60496500	0.49399900	0.53053600
H	-0.21212200	-2.75358900	-0.54234900
O	-1.81613000	0.71082100	-1.94890600
C	-1.58166200	-1.16752400	1.16913000
H	-1.61691900	-2.26259700	1.31864400
H	-0.71330600	-0.80845300	1.74038400
C	-2.87932300	-0.54856000	1.65552500

H	-3.74136800	-0.99258100	1.13588700
H	-3.01832700	-0.70547500	2.73639500
H	-2.91336500	0.53799500	1.46779200
N	-0.77099600	1.51155600	-0.12435500
C	-0.43844000	2.75375000	-0.78362800
H	-0.48761500	3.58937100	-0.06935200
H	0.57741500	2.70653100	-1.21598000
H	-1.16794400	2.92259800	-1.58398800
O	0.12546100	1.17509600	0.87449900
C	-0.19126200	1.77934800	2.10629500
H	0.57908600	1.43193900	2.80998900
H	-0.14462100	2.88195100	2.05194800
H	-1.18778200	1.47825600	2.47409000
C	-1.34706800	-0.96454100	-0.31836500

B-Cf2:

43

$E(\text{PBE0-dDsC}) = -11.13584$, thermal correction = 0.28796, solvation energy = -0.07900

C	0.73154400	-0.28462400	0.39166800
C	0.48613000	-0.47260700	1.91101400
H	-0.18627100	0.33407600	2.25542800
H	1.45104300	-0.29692900	2.41589900
C	-0.33503400	-0.91736300	-0.47715900
H	-0.76825100	-1.85746100	-0.10796500
H	-0.17666100	-0.89578600	-1.56238900
C	0.69219300	1.21573000	0.15601200
O	-0.40631000	1.74772500	-0.16758000
C	1.76536200	3.42638300	0.07571100
H	1.75870300	4.02175300	1.00147200
H	0.88028800	3.68135400	-0.51932000
N	1.73928400	2.00358500	0.36510400
Pd	-1.91337600	0.46616500	-0.61229600
F	-1.35951300	0.69889100	-2.42252800
O	-3.45914200	-0.84418400	-0.71320700

C	-3.63408900	-0.78536000	0.55057400
O	-2.79088100	-0.06240000	1.17774600
C	-4.74785100	-1.47930600	1.21854200
H	-5.62492300	-0.81191600	1.21651900
H	-5.01699200	-2.38998000	0.66678100
H	-4.49125800	-1.70286500	2.26257900
H	2.67877100	3.63768500	-0.49890600
O	2.91940700	1.42000500	0.72175300
C	3.36778500	1.83451800	2.00752200
H	4.21005700	1.17186500	2.24501200
H	3.72510300	2.87742700	1.99790400
H	2.57378600	1.71670600	2.76511600
C	1.95691800	-0.99906000	-0.17234700
C	2.72259600	-1.89994700	0.57813500
C	2.32692000	-0.73309900	-1.50289800
C	3.84191200	-2.50297900	0.01454800
H	2.46852200	-2.12559600	1.61625800
C	3.44840500	-1.33269900	-2.05981900
H	1.73978200	-0.02849600	-2.10614200
C	4.20662200	-2.22382800	-1.30211200
H	4.43771200	-3.19838900	0.61128700
H	3.73067600	-1.10556500	-3.09071800
H	5.08573000	-2.70417100	-1.73937700
C	-0.10983000	-1.80110800	2.34387200
H	-0.04635300	-1.89805400	3.43757600
H	-1.17829000	-1.86793900	2.08721900
H	0.40265200	-2.67350600	1.90912400

TS_{RE}:

43

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -11.10206, thermal correction = 0.28755, solvation energy = -0.07666, imaginary frequency = -249.1125 cm⁻¹

C	1.02404200	0.01825800	0.73718600
C	1.42604800	0.66617000	2.11703700
H	0.84251700	1.59823200	2.22837100

H	2.48149600	0.95916300	2.02119600
C	-0.24211700	-0.69306800	1.11800500
H	-0.96784600	-0.12074700	1.71746200
H	-0.18592600	-1.76203600	1.34379100
C	0.66504000	1.11027900	-0.26429800
O	-0.48111800	1.16978500	-0.78263400
C	1.37970500	2.92988900	-1.75401600
H	1.32297000	3.97223400	-1.40597700
H	0.44473300	2.67597000	-2.26639600
N	1.56739400	2.01340200	-0.64292500
Pd	-1.94278600	-0.20145100	-0.39610900
F	-0.65344400	-1.61490300	-0.78773400
O	-3.63997600	-1.20533700	0.05817500
C	-4.27012100	-0.10585100	0.22258200
O	-3.55887900	0.94528900	0.09474000
C	-5.71351300	-0.06226600	0.50629200
H	-6.25758600	-0.03256900	-0.45152200
H	-6.02431200	-0.96704500	1.04567700
H	-5.96430100	0.84607000	1.07025700
H	2.23083000	2.80925400	-2.44053900
O	2.83862800	1.88516600	-0.16263600
C	3.30520800	3.07260300	0.46840700
H	4.26044800	2.79537100	0.93225700
H	3.48836900	3.87746300	-0.26203500
H	2.59923900	3.42068800	1.24211800
C	2.09994200	-0.89469700	0.13917500
C	3.15603900	-1.38872800	0.91111800
C	2.05473900	-1.22675200	-1.22047200
C	4.12252600	-2.21833100	0.34609500
H	3.25794100	-1.13098600	1.96726200
C	3.02651800	-2.04521700	-1.78577000
H	1.24344600	-0.85828500	-1.85280200
C	4.06112000	-2.55089100	-1.00290100
H	4.93465300	-2.59945100	0.97068800

H	2.96944000	-2.29265500	-2.84889500
H	4.82185500	-3.19868900	-1.44595400
C	1.23026600	-0.18628800	3.36729800
H	1.71193900	0.30924600	4.22275500
H	0.17245500	-0.31462400	3.64717900
H	1.67313900	-1.18942700	3.28061300

Pd(OAc) $\cdot$ (S)-4t:

43

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -11.17282, thermal correction = 0.28982, solvation energy = -0.07130

C	0.65540500	0.72980300	-0.24630800
Pd	-2.14924000	-0.35543800	-0.04142100
C	0.51818500	-1.66033100	0.50617700
H	0.37732700	-2.00196900	-0.53099300
F	-0.78699900	-1.56752700	1.07307800
O	-3.63656600	0.62273400	-0.96950300
C	-4.50827900	-0.11706200	-0.39605100
O	-4.01523000	-0.99678500	0.38203000
C	-5.95382000	0.05603700	-0.60139700
H	-6.33474500	0.76704000	0.14919800
H	-6.15062600	0.47101200	-1.59907400
H	-6.47274700	-0.90173700	-0.46043700
C	2.64840800	-0.78402200	-0.01763000
C	2.72469300	-0.96519700	-1.40348700
C	3.76954600	-1.07173700	0.76348800
C	3.90287300	-1.40226400	-2.00090600
H	1.85376200	-0.75513100	-2.03804900
C	4.94692100	-1.51593200	0.16516800
H	3.74493000	-0.95051800	1.84944300
C	5.01918100	-1.67897400	-1.21545800
H	3.94720800	-1.52935800	-3.08569100
H	5.81750100	-1.73585300	0.78876800
H	5.94595200	-2.02506100	-1.68012500
H	1.02893100	-2.44369600	1.08507800

O	-0.48927800	0.61550800	-0.75260100
C	1.42082700	0.11389700	2.06666700
H	1.67949600	-0.76543100	2.68256400
H	2.28938700	0.78795600	2.13756300
C	0.19442400	0.79874800	2.64823300
H	-0.67460200	0.12800800	2.72480300
H	0.41003100	1.15523600	3.66618200
H	-0.11243100	1.68383200	2.06343100
N	1.31935000	1.86478700	-0.48704900
C	0.87375100	2.89292500	-1.41057400
H	0.69750000	3.84368100	-0.88524600
H	1.65437000	3.03162700	-2.17368000
H	-0.05907300	2.56681500	-1.88282900
O	2.62194400	1.94339500	-0.08414900
C	2.86947700	3.06259500	0.75711700
H	3.88457000	2.91001100	1.14590800
H	2.84429900	4.01102800	0.19542400
H	2.15243600	3.10331000	1.59532400
C	1.30876300	-0.36269200	0.60216700

TS_{DR}:

43

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -11.12671, thermal correction = 0.28449, solvation energy = -0.08812, imaginary frequency = -103.0166 cm⁻¹

C	0.69343100	-0.72702500	0.27672500
Pd	-2.24050000	0.07595000	-0.14992900
C	0.85375700	1.56287000	-0.76912500
H	0.10333100	1.89275700	-0.04348300
F	-1.20250000	0.35570300	-1.78059500
O	-3.61919800	-0.07352500	1.35306100
C	-4.51633700	0.37523400	0.57083300
O	-4.12557400	0.67342100	-0.60409000
C	-5.92868500	0.51662600	0.98092000
H	-6.47914300	-0.38610200	0.67239900
H	-6.00257700	0.61314200	2.07195000

H	-6.38640000	1.37769200	0.47552300
C	2.27008000	1.43504300	-0.12944900
C	2.36534400	1.40679900	1.28614900
C	3.44192900	1.65350200	-0.89458100
C	3.58593000	1.57962600	1.90884000
H	1.45591500	1.26446100	1.88147000
C	4.66106800	1.81820500	-0.26662700
H	3.37385300	1.69480500	-1.98546200
C	4.73167300	1.77653300	1.13115000
H	3.65580500	1.57105400	2.99880500
H	5.56416400	1.99254800	-0.85594600
H	5.69957000	1.90737500	1.62360800
H	0.84192900	2.11258200	-1.71439000
O	-0.46801300	-0.67044900	0.69444100
C	1.68476600	-0.48364700	-2.09450900
H	1.71274800	0.27773800	-2.89103000
H	2.71621300	-0.84239600	-1.94421000
C	0.79454300	-1.64308600	-2.53240000
H	-0.23573800	-1.29541700	-2.68438600
H	1.18238100	-2.05991300	-3.47306600
H	0.78093700	-2.46071900	-1.79277600
N	1.55366400	-1.61887500	0.79844300
C	1.24967700	-2.45039400	1.94593000
H	1.36459100	-3.51722400	1.70233900
H	1.92794900	-2.18384200	2.77162700
H	0.20962400	-2.26597600	2.23984800
O	2.87926600	-1.46339300	0.48398700
C	3.46686300	-2.65661900	-0.02456400
H	4.46894500	-2.36357800	-0.36384200
H	3.57019600	-3.42613800	0.75781300
H	2.88818500	-3.05794000	-0.87355000
C	1.19021200	0.18029600	-0.83253500

Inflection point:

E(PBE0-dDsC) = -11.12743, thermal correction = 0.28707, solvation energy = -0.08399, imaginary frequency = -236.4646, -45.5051 cm⁻¹

C	-0.13167400	-0.12586300	0.59728600
C	-0.64127500	-0.69174100	1.89772200
H	-0.43053100	-1.77111400	1.83512200
H	-1.73843000	-0.60200300	1.95549100
C	0.45998900	1.17194500	0.48855000
H	0.71904200	1.68790500	1.41693400
H	1.17192800	1.34991500	-0.32566500
C	-0.00189200	-1.01898900	-0.62423800
O	1.00323400	-0.96815600	-1.35634800
C	-1.01079400	-2.76274300	-2.03541000
H	-1.21659500	-3.78794300	-1.69289400
H	-0.01759300	-2.73603200	-2.49757600
N	-1.01190300	-1.84799300	-0.91196800
Pd	2.84882600	-0.60871000	-0.41614600
F	1.82067600	-1.42336800	1.05127700
O	4.65425000	-0.05602600	0.33725500
C	4.93978100	0.53558200	-0.75260300
O	4.06759500	0.43621900	-1.67533100
C	6.19389000	1.29549000	-0.92751500
H	6.56738700	1.63775800	0.04675100
H	6.95473600	0.64178300	-1.38067600
H	6.02674200	2.14330500	-1.60574000
H	-1.77511100	-2.45426000	-2.76518600
O	-2.22329300	-1.56654800	-0.33724400
C	-2.82100500	-2.69858600	0.28777800
H	-3.66787200	-2.29886200	0.86046400
H	-3.20558700	-3.41767800	-0.45351800
H	-2.11380500	-3.20004700	0.96907100
C	-0.99586500	1.43890600	0.03203500
C	-1.28401100	1.47991200	-1.35280200
C	-1.93611600	1.95064800	0.95427300
C	-2.45669000	2.06349500	-1.79921500

H	-0.55661700	1.08218900	-2.06890500
C	-3.10059600	2.53958300	0.50068100
H	-1.71914200	1.90876300	2.02593400
C	-3.35398100	2.60452100	-0.87465700
H	-2.66584000	2.12471400	-2.86951700
H	-3.80806400	2.97285800	1.21122500
H	-4.26518000	3.09307100	-1.23048800
C	0.04553000	-0.12781000	3.12666800
H	1.13581600	-0.21910200	3.01543800
H	-0.20844500	0.92591000	3.32792200
H	-0.25151500	-0.70089800	4.01576700

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9. X-Ray Crystal Structure Data

Submitted by: **Guoqiang Yang**
 Supervisor: **Professor Jieping Zhu**
 Solved by: **Farzaneh Fadaei Tirani**
 Sample ID: **YGQ-Et-acid**

$R_1=7.83\%$

Crystal Data and Experimental of (*R*)-**14** (CCDC 2096533)

Experimental. Single colourless needle-shaped crystals of **ygq-et-acid_twin1_hklf4** were used as supplied. A suitable crystal with dimensions $0.36 \times 0.06 \times 0.04 \text{ mm}^3$ was selected and mounted on a XtaLAB Synergy R, DW system, HyPix-Arc 150 diffractometer. The crystal was kept at a steady $T = 140.00(10) \text{ K}$ during data collection. The structure was solved with the **ShelXT** 2018/2 (Sheldrick, 2015) solution program using dual methods and by using **Olex2** 1.3 (Dolomanov et al., 2009) as the graphical interface. The model was refined with **ShelXL** 2018/3 (Sheldrick, 2015) using full matrix least squares minimisation on F^2 .

Crystal Data. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$, $M_r = 178.22$, monoclinic, $P2_1$ (No. 4), $a = 17.4886(4) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 6.13129(13) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 18.3375(4) \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 99.623(2)^\circ$, $\alpha = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $V = 1938.62(8) \text{ \AA}^3$, $T = 140.00(10) \text{ K}$, $Z = 8$, $Z' = 4$, $\mu(\text{Cu K}\alpha) = 0.663$, 51742 reflections measured, 7136 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0981$) which were used in all calculations. The final wR_2 was 0.2247 (all data) and R_1 was 0.0783 ($I \geq 2 \sigma(I)$).

Compound	YGQ-Et-acid
Formula	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$
$D_{\text{calc.}} / \text{g cm}^{-3}$	1.221
μ / mm^{-1}	0.663
Formula Weight	178.22
Colour	colourless
Shape	needle-shaped
Size/ mm^3	$0.36 \times 0.06 \times 0.04$
T / K	140.00(10)
Crystal System	monoclinic
Flack Parameter	0.1(2)
Space Group	$P2_1$
$a / \text{Å}$	17.4886(4)
$b / \text{Å}$	6.13129(13)
$c / \text{Å}$	18.3375(4)
$\alpha / ^\circ$	90
$\beta / ^\circ$	99.623(2)
$\gamma / ^\circ$	90
$V / \text{Å}^3$	1938.62(8)
Z	8
Z'	4
Wavelength/ Å	1.54184
Radiation type	$\text{CuK}\alpha$
$\theta_{\text{min}} / ^\circ$	2.444
$\theta_{\text{max}} / ^\circ$	75.392
Measured Refl's.	51742
Indep't Refl's	7136
Refl's $I \geq 2 \sigma(I)$	6504
R_{int}	0.0981
Parameters	481
Restraints	1
Largest Peak/ $e \text{ \AA}^{-3}$	0.633
Deepest Hole/ $e \text{ \AA}^{-3}$	-0.406
GooF	1.058
wR_2 (all data)	0.2247
wR_2	0.2167
R_1 (all data)	0.0836
R_1	0.0783
CCDC number	2096533

Structure Quality Indicators

Reflections:	$d \text{ min (Cu}\lambda\text{)}$ $2\theta=150.8^\circ$ 0.80	$I/\sigma(I)$ CIF 17.5	R_{int} CIF 9.81%	Full 135.4° 94% to 150.8° 97.1	
Refinement:	Shift CIF 0.000	Max Peak CIF 0.6	Min Peak CIF -0.4	GooF CIF 1.058	Flack CIF .1(2)

A colourless needle-shaped crystal with dimensions $0.36 \times 0.06 \times 0.04 \text{ mm}^3$ was mounted. Data were collected using a XtaLAB Synergy R, DW system, HyPix-Arc 150 diffractometer operating at $T = 140.00(10) \text{ K}$.

Data were measured using ω scans using Cu K_α radiation. The diffraction pattern was indexed and the total number of runs and images was based on the strategy calculation from the program CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.110a (Rigaku OD, 2021). The maximum resolution that was achieved was $\Theta = 75.392^\circ$ ($0.80 \text{ \AA}$).

The unit cell was refined using CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.110a (Rigaku OD, 2021) on 29766 reflections, 58% of the observed reflections.

Data reduction, scaling and absorption corrections were performed using CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.110a (Rigaku OD, 2021). The final completeness is 97.10 % out to 75.392° in Θ . A Gaussian absorption correction was performed using CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.110a (Rigaku Oxford Diffraction, 2021) Numerical absorption correction based on Gaussian integration over a multifaceted crystal model. Empirical absorption correction using spherical harmonics as implemented in SCALE3 ABSPACK scaling algorithm. The absorption coefficient μ of this material is 0.663 mm^{-1} at this wavelength ($\lambda = 1.54184 \text{ \AA}$) and the minimum and maximum transmissions are 0.762 and 1.000.

The structure was solved and the space group $P2_1$ (# 4) determined by the ShelXT 2018/2 (Sheldrick, 2015) structure solution program using dual methods and refined by full matrix least squares minimisation on F^2 using version 2018/3 of **ShelXL** 2018/3 (Sheldrick, 2015). All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atom positions were calculated geometrically and refined using the riding model.

_twin_special_details: Component 2 rotated by 178.3437° around $[-0.00 \ 1.00 \ 0.00]$ (reciprocal) or $[0.00 \ 1.00 \ 0.00]$ (direct)

The value of Z' is 4.

The Flack parameter was refined to 0.1(2). Determination of absolute structure using Bayesian statistics on Bijvoet differences using the Olex2 results in None. Note: The Flack parameter is used to determine chirality of the crystal studied, the value should be near 0, a value of 1 means that the stereochemistry is wrong and the model should be inverted. A value of 0.5 means that the crystal consists of a racemic mixture of the two enantiomers.

Citations

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Fig. S7: Image of the Crystal on the Diffractometer.

Fig. S8: Image of the Crystal on the Diffractometer.

Fig. S9: Image of the Crystal on the Diffractometer.

Data Plots: Diffraction Data

Data Plots: Refinement and Data

Table S6: Fractional Atomic Coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for **ygq-et-acid_twin1_hklf4**. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} .

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
O1	4657.6(18)	-3163(6)	6482.2(18)	41.7(7)
O2	4446.6(18)	-396(6)	7211.8(18)	40.8(7)
C1	3626(2)	-603(8)	6032(2)	32.9(9)
C2	4292(2)	-1529(8)	6590(2)	34.2(9)
C3	2893(2)	-781(8)	6390(2)	35.4(9)
C4	2761(2)	-2682(8)	6770(2)	37.1(10)
C5	2103(3)	-2935(9)	7097(3)	41.9(10)
C6	1564(3)	-1250(9)	7047(3)	41.9(11)
C7	1681(3)	634(9)	6668(3)	44.1(11)
C8	2340(2)	876(8)	6342(3)	38.4(10)
C9	3817(3)	1759(8)	5864(3)	39.1(10)
C10	4579(3)	2088(10)	5571(3)	48.1(12)
C11	3510(3)	-2005(8)	5328(2)	37.1(9)
O3	5444.0(19)	-2602(6)	8212.2(18)	41.7(8)
O4	5645(2)	-5396(7)	7492.8(19)	46.8(8)
C21	6344(3)	-5442(8)	8729(3)	37.5(10)
C22	5767(2)	-4320(8)	8125(3)	36.4(9)
C23	7149(2)	-5152(9)	8508(2)	37.9(10)
C24	7355(3)	-3198(9)	8221(3)	40.2(10)
C25	8090(3)	-2856(10)	8052(3)	46.8(12)
C26	8641(3)	-4472(11)	8180(3)	51.0(13)
C27	8455(3)	-6434(11)	8475(3)	51.6(13)
C28	7712(3)	-6790(9)	8637(3)	43.2(11)
C29	6364(2)	-4284(9)	9474(2)	39.5(10)
C30	5646(3)	-4599(12)	9841(3)	54.9(14)
C31	6114(3)	-7836(9)	8762(3)	50.8(12)
O5	530.2(18)	1788(6)	8598.6(17)	39.3(7)
O6	785.6(18)	4757(6)	7980.8(17)	38.8(7)
O7	-160.4(19)	2908(6)	6877.5(18)	43.3(8)
O8	-401.8(19)	-124(6)	7468.0(17)	41.7(7)
C41	1523(2)	4301(8)	9186(2)	32.9(9)
C42	897(2)	3459(8)	8566(2)	33.1(9)
C43	2301(2)	4106(8)	8894(2)	33.4(9)
C44	2470(2)	2166(8)	8556(2)	36.8(9)
C45	3152(3)	1922(9)	8261(3)	42.0(10)
C46	3677(3)	3617(10)	8312(3)	45.2(11)
C47	3528(3)	5525(9)	8661(3)	44.7(11)
C48	2842(2)	5787(9)	8947(3)	39.1(10)
C49	1333(2)	6658(8)	9358(2)	37.0(9)
C50	542(3)	6985(10)	9596(3)	45.2(11)
C51	1551(3)	2839(8)	9866(2)	36.9(9)
C61	-929(3)	94(8)	6179(2)	37.6(10)

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
C62	-464(2)	1120(8)	6871(3)	35.7(9)
C63	-1776(3)	-87(9)	6295(2)	41.7(11)
C64	-2125(3)	1673(10)	6583(3)	45.8(11)
C65	-2896(3)	1571(13)	6694(3)	59.1(16)
C66	-3321(3)	-319(14)	6505(3)	62.2(17)
C67	-2978(3)	-2069(13)	6203(3)	60.9(16)
C68	-2215(3)	-1956(10)	6103(3)	51.4(13)
C69	-879(3)	1656(10)	5521(3)	46.4(11)
C70	-1297(3)	799(11)	4781(3)	53.1(13)
C71	-553(3)	-2105(9)	6067(3)	50.4(12)

Table S7: Anisotropic Displacement Parameters ($\times 10^4$) for **ygq-et-acid_twin1_hklf4**. The anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: $-2\pi^2[h^2a^{*2} \times U_{11} + \dots + 2hka^* \times b^* \times U_{12}]$

Atom	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{23}	U_{13}	U_{12}
O1	48.4(17)	32.2(19)	42.6(16)	-5.7(14)	2.6(13)	10.5(14)
O2	45.7(17)	32.5(19)	41.2(16)	-6.5(14)	-1.7(12)	7.1(14)
C1	37(2)	24(2)	37(2)	-1.8(17)	5.9(16)	2.1(16)
C2	38(2)	26(2)	39(2)	-2.7(18)	9.3(16)	-1.6(17)
C3	34(2)	32(2)	40(2)	1.0(18)	3.8(16)	0.0(16)
C4	39(2)	32(3)	39(2)	3.9(18)	3.7(17)	-0.7(17)
C5	42(2)	43(3)	40(2)	4(2)	5.3(17)	-7(2)
C6	37(2)	48(3)	41(2)	-1(2)	8.3(17)	-3.8(19)
C7	39(2)	45(3)	48(3)	-1(2)	8.6(18)	3(2)
C8	38(2)	32(3)	46(2)	4.5(19)	8.2(17)	3.2(17)
C9	43(2)	32(3)	44(2)	2(2)	11.9(18)	-1.1(18)
C10	47(3)	36(3)	65(3)	2(2)	20(2)	1(2)
C11	42(2)	32(3)	38(2)	-3.5(18)	5.4(17)	1.9(17)
O3	49.2(18)	26.8(19)	46.5(17)	-3.7(13)	0.1(13)	5.8(13)
O4	51.8(19)	39(2)	45.1(17)	-9.1(15)	-5.2(13)	12.7(15)
C21	40(2)	28(2)	43(2)	1.1(19)	2.7(17)	-3.4(18)
C22	38(2)	29(2)	40(2)	-2.1(18)	2.8(16)	-3.2(17)
C23	39(2)	39(3)	33(2)	-2.7(19)	-0.4(16)	0.7(18)
C24	42(2)	34(3)	44(2)	0(2)	3.8(17)	0.3(19)
C25	47(2)	52(3)	40(2)	1(2)	4.6(19)	-5(2)
C26	40(2)	68(4)	44(3)	-7(3)	5.3(19)	0(2)
C27	42(2)	58(4)	52(3)	-6(3)	1(2)	12(2)
C28	48(2)	36(3)	44(2)	-2(2)	1.0(18)	8(2)
C29	41(2)	37(3)	39(2)	1.2(19)	0.2(17)	0.9(18)
C30	49(3)	67(4)	50(3)	1(3)	9(2)	-3(2)
C31	51(3)	31(3)	68(3)	4(2)	0(2)	-6(2)
O5	46.9(16)	29.8(18)	39.8(16)	2.9(14)	2.9(12)	-9.1(13)
O6	44.4(16)	31.0(18)	38.5(15)	5.4(14)	0.2(12)	-4.4(13)
O7	53.2(19)	32.1(19)	41.7(16)	2.1(14)	-0.7(13)	-6.4(14)
O8	49.1(18)	35.2(19)	38.3(16)	4.7(14)	0.0(13)	-4.4(14)
C41	37(2)	29(2)	32.6(19)	-0.7(17)	6.5(15)	-0.5(16)
C42	37(2)	27(2)	35(2)	2.2(17)	3.5(15)	0.9(17)
C43	37(2)	32(2)	31.0(19)	3.0(16)	3.2(15)	2.0(16)
C44	40(2)	33(3)	38(2)	-4.0(18)	8.1(16)	-1.3(17)
C45	43(2)	40(3)	42(2)	-4(2)	7.1(18)	8(2)
C46	35(2)	51(3)	49(3)	3(2)	5.6(18)	3(2)
C47	35(2)	45(3)	53(3)	3(2)	3.1(18)	-4.1(19)
C48	37(2)	35(3)	45(2)	-2.6(19)	2.5(17)	-2.5(18)
C49	42(2)	32(3)	38(2)	-2.1(18)	7.7(17)	-0.6(18)
C50	44(2)	38(3)	55(3)	-4(2)	14(2)	2.0(19)
C51	42(2)	33(3)	35(2)	3.0(18)	4.1(16)	-2.6(17)
C61	46(2)	28(2)	38(2)	-1.6(18)	4.7(17)	-2.1(17)
C62	37(2)	29(2)	40(2)	-0.8(18)	3.7(16)	-0.5(16)
C63	44(2)	39(3)	39(2)	5(2)	-1.8(18)	-1.8(19)

Atom	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{23}	U_{13}	U_{12}
C64	49(2)	46(3)	41(2)	2(2)	2.7(19)	5(2)
C65	52(3)	78(5)	46(3)	8(3)	4(2)	16(3)
C66	41(3)	90(5)	53(3)	14(3)	-1(2)	-5(3)
C67	55(3)	74(5)	50(3)	7(3)	-2(2)	-18(3)
C68	54(3)	49(3)	48(3)	-1(2)	-2(2)	-9(2)
C69	52(3)	45(3)	40(2)	-2(2)	2.2(19)	-6(2)
C70	57(3)	58(4)	41(3)	-1(2)	-1(2)	-3(3)
C71	56(3)	37(3)	55(3)	-11(2)	2(2)	7(2)

Table S8: Bond Lengths in Å for *ygq-et-acid_twin1_hklf4*.

Atom	Atom	Length/Å	Atom	Atom	Length/Å
O1	C2	1.222(6)	O5	C42	1.216(6)
O2	C2	1.323(5)	O6	C42	1.324(5)
C1	C2	1.526(6)	O7	C62	1.217(6)
C1	C3	1.538(6)	O8	C62	1.324(6)
C1	C9	1.529(7)	C41	C42	1.530(6)
C1	C11	1.535(6)	C41	C43	1.547(6)
C3	C4	1.397(7)	C41	C49	1.528(7)
C3	C8	1.396(6)	C41	C51	1.529(6)
C4	C5	1.393(6)	C43	C44	1.396(7)
C5	C6	1.392(7)	C43	C48	1.392(6)
C6	C7	1.381(8)	C44	C45	1.397(6)
C7	C8	1.392(6)	C45	C46	1.379(7)
C9	C10	1.533(6)	C46	C47	1.379(8)
O3	C22	1.218(6)	C47	C48	1.396(6)
O4	C22	1.320(6)	C49	C50	1.532(6)
C21	C22	1.531(6)	C61	C62	1.523(6)
C21	C23	1.539(6)	C61	C63	1.535(6)
C21	C29	1.535(7)	C61	C69	1.554(7)
C21	C31	1.526(7)	C61	C71	1.529(7)
C23	C24	1.381(7)	C63	C64	1.388(8)
C23	C28	1.399(7)	C63	C68	1.392(8)
C24	C25	1.387(7)	C64	C65	1.398(7)
C25	C26	1.374(8)	C65	C66	1.388(11)
C26	C27	1.380(9)	C66	C67	1.389(11)
C27	C28	1.397(7)	C67	C68	1.378(8)
C29	C30	1.534(7)	C69	C70	1.522(7)

Table S9: Bond Angles in ° for *ygq-et-acid_twin1_hklf4*.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C2	C1	C3	106.5(3)	C7	C6	C5	119.9(4)
C2	C1	C9	108.6(4)	C6	C7	C8	120.5(5)
C2	C1	C11	109.5(4)	C7	C8	C3	120.7(5)
C9	C1	C3	112.2(4)	C1	C9	C10	115.3(4)
C9	C1	C11	111.4(4)	C22	C21	C23	106.2(4)
C11	C1	C3	108.4(3)	C22	C21	C29	110.5(4)
O1	C2	O2	122.2(4)	C29	C21	C23	107.2(3)
O1	C2	C1	123.9(4)	C31	C21	C22	108.4(4)
O2	C2	C1	113.9(4)	C31	C21	C23	112.4(4)
C4	C3	C1	119.4(4)	C31	C21	C29	112.1(4)
C8	C3	C1	122.7(4)	O3	C22	O4	122.5(4)
C8	C3	C4	117.9(4)	O3	C22	C21	123.9(4)
C5	C4	C3	121.7(4)	O4	C22	C21	113.6(4)
C6	C5	C4	119.3(5)	C24	C23	C21	120.6(4)

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C24	C23	C28	117.8(4)	C45	C46	C47	119.7(4)
C28	C23	C21	121.5(5)	C46	C47	C48	120.8(5)
C23	C24	C25	121.8(5)	C43	C48	C47	120.4(5)
C26	C25	C24	120.1(5)	C41	C49	C50	114.9(4)
C25	C26	C27	119.5(5)	C62	C61	C63	107.9(4)
C26	C27	C28	120.5(5)	C62	C61	C69	107.5(4)
C27	C28	C23	120.4(5)	C62	C61	C71	107.1(4)
C30	C29	C21	115.7(4)	C63	C61	C69	109.4(4)
C42	C41	C43	106.1(3)	C71	C61	C63	113.7(4)
C49	C41	C42	108.6(4)	C71	C61	C69	111.0(4)
C49	C41	C43	112.3(4)	O7	C62	O8	122.4(4)
C49	C41	C51	111.4(4)	O7	C62	C61	123.5(4)
C51	C41	C42	109.3(4)	O8	C62	C61	114.2(4)
C51	C41	C43	109.0(3)	C64	C63	C61	119.5(5)
O5	C42	O6	122.6(4)	C64	C63	C68	118.5(5)
O5	C42	C41	124.4(4)	C68	C63	C61	122.0(5)
O6	C42	C41	113.0(4)	C63	C64	C65	121.2(6)
C44	C43	C41	118.9(4)	C66	C65	C64	119.3(6)
C48	C43	C41	123.1(4)	C65	C66	C67	119.7(5)
C48	C43	C44	118.0(4)	C68	C67	C66	120.4(6)
C43	C44	C45	121.4(4)	C67	C68	C63	120.9(6)
C46	C45	C44	119.7(5)	C70	C69	C61	113.5(5)

Table S10: Torsion Angles in ° for **ygq-et-acid_twin1_hklf4**.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C1	C3	C4	C5	-179.4(4)
C1	C3	C8	C7	179.3(4)
C2	C1	C3	C4	-42.7(5)
C2	C1	C3	C8	138.3(5)
C2	C1	C9	C10	57.3(5)
C3	C1	C2	O1	115.9(5)
C3	C1	C2	O2	-64.2(5)
C3	C1	C9	C10	174.8(4)
C3	C4	C5	C6	-0.2(7)
C4	C3	C8	C7	0.3(7)
C4	C5	C6	C7	0.8(7)
C5	C6	C7	C8	-0.8(7)
C6	C7	C8	C3	0.3(7)
C8	C3	C4	C5	-0.3(7)
C9	C1	C2	O1	-123.0(5)
C9	C1	C2	O2	56.8(5)
C9	C1	C3	C4	-161.5(4)
C9	C1	C3	C8	19.5(6)
C11	C1	C2	O1	-1.2(6)
C11	C1	C2	O2	178.7(4)
C11	C1	C3	C4	75.1(5)
C11	C1	C3	C8	-103.9(5)
C11	C1	C9	C10	-63.4(5)
C21	C23	C24	C25	176.7(4)
C21	C23	C28	C27	-175.8(4)
C22	C21	C23	C24	40.8(6)
C22	C21	C23	C28	-143.6(4)
C22	C21	C29	C30	71.6(6)
C23	C21	C22	O3	-107.8(5)
C23	C21	C22	O4	72.5(5)
C23	C21	C29	C30	-173.1(4)
C23	C24	C25	C26	-1.0(7)
C24	C23	C28	C27	-0.1(7)

Atom	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C24	C25	C26	C27	0.2(8)
C25	C26	C27	C28	0.6(8)
C26	C27	C28	C23	-0.7(8)
C28	C23	C24	C25	1.0(7)
C29	C21	C22	O3	8.0(6)
C29	C21	C22	O4	-171.6(4)
C29	C21	C23	C24	-77.3(5)
C29	C21	C23	C28	98.2(5)
C31	C21	C22	O3	131.2(5)
C31	C21	C22	O4	-48.4(6)
C31	C21	C23	C24	159.1(5)
C31	C21	C23	C28	-25.3(6)
C31	C21	C29	C30	-49.4(6)
C41	C43	C44	C45	178.0(4)
C41	C43	C48	C47	-178.9(4)
C42	C41	C43	C44	-47.0(5)
C42	C41	C43	C48	132.4(4)
C42	C41	C49	C50	58.8(5)
C43	C41	C42	O5	112.0(5)
C43	C41	C42	O6	-68.6(5)
C43	C41	C49	C50	175.8(4)
C43	C44	C45	C46	0.8(7)
C44	C43	C48	C47	0.5(7)
C44	C45	C46	C47	0.9(7)
C45	C46	C47	C48	-1.8(7)
C46	C47	C48	C43	1.1(7)
C48	C43	C44	C45	-1.5(6)
C49	C41	C42	O5	-127.1(5)
C49	C41	C42	O6	52.3(5)
C49	C41	C43	C44	-165.5(4)
C49	C41	C43	C48	14.0(6)
C51	C41	C42	O5	-5.4(6)
C51	C41	C42	O6	174.0(4)
C51	C41	C43	C44	70.6(5)
C51	C41	C43	C48	-110.0(5)
C51	C41	C49	C50	-61.6(5)
C61	C63	C64	C65	179.8(4)
C61	C63	C68	C67	-179.1(5)
C62	C61	C63	C64	45.4(6)
C62	C61	C63	C68	-136.2(5)
C62	C61	C69	C70	177.9(4)
C63	C61	C62	O7	-114.0(5)
C63	C61	C62	O8	67.3(5)
C63	C61	C69	C70	-65.1(6)
C63	C64	C65	C66	-0.7(8)
C64	C63	C68	C67	-0.7(8)
C64	C65	C66	C67	-0.6(8)
C65	C66	C67	C68	1.2(9)
C66	C67	C68	C63	-0.6(9)
C68	C63	C64	C65	1.3(7)
C69	C61	C62	O7	3.9(6)
C69	C61	C62	O8	-174.8(4)
C69	C61	C63	C64	-71.4(5)
C69	C61	C63	C68	107.0(5)
C71	C61	C62	O7	123.3(5)
C71	C61	C62	O8	-55.5(5)
C71	C61	C63	C64	164.0(4)
C71	C61	C63	C68	-17.6(6)
C71	C61	C69	C70	61.1(6)

Table S11: Hydrogen Fractional Atomic Coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for **ygq-et-acid_twin1_hklf4**. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} .

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
H2	4827.97	-953.32	7488.2	61
H4	3129.67	-3832.2	6805.9	45
H5	2023.21	-4243.1	7352.05	50
H6	1115.84	-1395.24	7273.85	50
H7	1308.18	1774.52	6629.62	53
H8	2413.87	2183.96	6085.14	46
H9A	3837.91	2625.73	6322.97	47
H9B	3387.69	2347.74	5496.06	47
H10A	4678.82	3652.38	5528.63	72
H10B	4540.51	1403.88	5082.91	72
H10C	5005.23	1419.53	5912.41	72
H11A	3411.29	-3519.18	5455.73	56
H11B	3978.02	-1939.94	5100.17	56
H11C	3066.78	-1449.53	4979.12	56
H4A	5283.89	-4798.32	7202.06	70
H24	6983.86	-2055.97	8136.19	48
H25	8213.28	-1502.6	7847.26	56
H26	9145.19	-4239.77	8067.15	61
H27	8835.42	-7550.46	8569.54	62
H28	7588.6	-8152.72	8834.71	52
H29A	6823.6	-4808.48	9819.55	47
H29B	6435.12	-2702.27	9399.58	47
H30A	5180.53	-4185.54	9493.28	82
H30B	5690.59	-3680.72	10283.89	82
H30C	5607.45	-6132.49	9981.69	82
H31A	5567.4	-7937.08	8818.47	76
H31B	6437.48	-8539.07	9184.75	76
H31C	6188.5	-8569.34	8304.4	76
H6A	400.31	4319.03	7680.27	58
H8A	-99.62	468.31	7816	63
H44	2113.4	987.36	8524.91	44
H45	3253.64	595.53	8027.77	50
H46	4138.08	3470.44	8106.73	54
H47	3897.28	6674.51	8708.26	54
H48	2744.52	7120.43	9178.48	47
H49A	1351.4	7556.47	8912.59	44
H49B	1740.56	7205.41	9756.22	44
H50A	137.51	6313.2	9231.42	68
H50B	437.5	8549.2	9630.12	68
H50C	545.68	6303.38	10080.27	68
H51A	1691.87	1352.01	9743.07	55
H51B	1041.24	2824.77	10019.94	55
H51C	1939.2	3402.57	10269.8	55
H64	-1835.9	2970.77	6706.94	55
H65	-3127.51	2781.88	6896.45	71
H66	-3843.72	-414.74	6581.59	75
H67	-3270.65	-3351.92	6064.57	73
H68	-1986.38	-3170.45	5900.27	62
H69A	-1105.98	3081.92	5621.42	56
H69B	-326.81	1898.87	5486.68	56
H70A	-1315.09	1943.32	4405.82	80
H70B	-1826.28	371.12	4828.56	80
H70C	-1017.87	-469.68	4633.72	80
H71A	-630.29	-3101.62	6465.88	76
H71B	3.94	-1898.1	6072.97	76
H71C	-790.94	-2723.43	5590.08	76

Table S12: Hydrogen Bond information for **ygq-et-acid_twin1_hklf4**.

D	H	A	d(D-H)/Å	d(H-A)/Å	d(D-A)/Å	D-H-A/deg
02	H2	03	0.84	1.86	2.677(4)	163.3
04	H4A	01	0.84	1.86	2.687(5)	167.5
06	H6A	07	0.84	1.84	2.645(4)	159.3
08	H8A	05	0.84	1.84	2.683(4)	177.7

Submitted by: **Guoqiang Yang**
 Supervisor: **Professor Jieping Zhu**
 Solved by: **Farzaneh Fadaei Tirani**
 Sample ID: **YGQ-PDTacid**

$R_1=3.62\%$

Crystal Data and Experimental of (S)-15 (CCDC 2098832)

Experimental. Single colourless needle-shaped crystals of **ygq-pdtacid** were used as supplied. A suitable crystal with dimensions $0.22 \times 0.02 \times 0.02 \text{ mm}^3$ was selected and mounted on a XtaLAB Synergy R, DW system, HyPix-Arc 150 diffractometer. The crystal was kept at a steady $T = 139.99(10) \text{ K}$ during data collection. The structure was solved with the **ShelXT** 2018/2 (Sheldrick, 2015) solution program using dual methods and by using **Olex2** 1.3 (Dolomanov et al., 2009) as the graphical interface. The model was refined with **ShelXL** 2018/3 (Sheldrick, 2015) using full matrix least squares minimisation on F^2 .

Crystal Data. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{FO}_2$, $M_r = 196.21$, monoclinic, $P2_1$ (No. 4), $a = 11.0424(3) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.31030(16) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 17.7605(5) \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 93.868(3)^\circ$, $\alpha = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $V = 1039.08(5) \text{ \AA}^3$, $T = 139.99(10) \text{ K}$, $Z = 4$, $Z' = 2$, $\mu(\text{Cu K}\alpha) = 0.810$, 34290 reflections measured, 4278 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0459$) which were used in all calculations. The final wR_2 was 0.0931 (all data) and R_1 was 0.0362 ($I \geq 2\sigma(I)$).

Compound	YGQ-PDTacid
Formula	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{FO}_2$
$D_{\text{calc.}} / \text{g cm}^{-3}$	1.254
μ / mm^{-1}	0.810
Formula Weight	196.21
Colour	colourless
Shape	needle-shaped
Size/ mm^3	$0.22 \times 0.02 \times 0.02$
T / K	139.99(10)
Crystal System	monoclinic
Flack Parameter	0.04(9)
Space Group	$P2_1$
$a / \text{Å}$	11.0424(3)
$b / \text{Å}$	5.31030(16)
$c / \text{Å}$	17.7605(5)
$\alpha / ^\circ$	90
$\beta / ^\circ$	93.868(3)
$\gamma / ^\circ$	90
$V / \text{Å}^3$	1039.08(5)
Z	4
Z'	2
Wavelength/ Å	1.54184
Radiation type	$\text{CuK}\alpha$
$\theta_{\text{min}} / ^\circ$	2.493
$\theta_{\text{max}} / ^\circ$	76.444
Measured Refl's.	34290
Indep't Refl's	4278
Refl's $I \geq 2\sigma(I)$	3519
R_{int}	0.0459
Parameters	257
Restraints	1
Largest Peak/ $e \text{ \AA}^{-3}$	0.155
Deepest Hole/ $e \text{ \AA}^{-3}$	-0.173
GooF	1.061
wR_2 (all data)	0.0931
wR_2	0.0878
R_1 (all data)	0.0515
R_1	0.0362
CCDC number	2098832

Structure Quality Indicators

Reflections:	d min (Cu λ) 2 θ =152.9°	0.79	I/ σ (I) CIF	28.5	Rint CIF	4.59%	Full 135.4° 99% to 152.9°	100		
Refinement:	Shift CIF	0.000	Max Peak CIF	0.2	Min Peak CIF	-0.2	GooF CIF	1.061	Flack CIF	.04(9)

A colourless needle-shaped crystal with dimensions 0.22 × 0.02 × 0.02 mm³ was mounted. Data were collected using a XtaLAB Synergy R, DW system, HyPix-Arc 150 diffractometer operating at $T = 139.99(10)$ K.

Data were measured using ω scans using Cu K α radiation. The diffraction pattern was indexed and the total number of runs and images was based on the strategy calculation from the program CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.113a (Rigaku OD, 2021). The maximum resolution achieved was $\theta = 76.444^\circ$ (0.79 Å).

The unit cell was refined using CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.113a (Rigaku OD, 2021) on 14610 reflections, 43% of the observed reflections.

Data reduction, scaling and absorption corrections were performed using CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.113a (Rigaku OD, 2021). The final completeness is 100.00 % out to 76.444° in θ . A Gaussian absorption correction was performed using CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.113a (Rigaku Oxford Diffraction, 2021) Numerical absorption correction based on Gaussian integration over a multifaceted crystal model. Empirical absorption correction using spherical harmonics as implemented in SCALE3 ABSPACK scaling algorithm. The absorption coefficient μ of this material is 0.810 mm⁻¹ at this wavelength ($\lambda = 1.54184\text{Å}$) and the minimum and maximum transmissions are 0.709 and 1.000.

The structure was solved and the space group $P2_1$ (# 4) determined by the ShelXT 2018/2 (Sheldrick, 2015) structure solution program using dual methods and refined by full matrix least squares minimisation on F^2 using version 2018/3 of **ShelXL** 2018/3 (Sheldrick, 2015). All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atom positions were calculated geometrically and refined using the riding model.

The value of Z' is 2. This means that there are two independent molecules in the asymmetric unit.

The Flack parameter was refined to 0.04(9). Determination of absolute structure using Bayesian statistics on Bijvoet differences using the Olex2 results in None. Note: The Flack parameter is used to determine chirality of the crystal studied, the value should be near 0, a value of 1 means that the stereochemistry is wrong and the model should be inverted. A value of 0.5 means that the crystal consists of a racemic mixture of the two enantiomers.

Citations

CrysAlis^{Pro} Software System, Rigaku Oxford Diffraction, (2021).

Sheldrick, G.M., ShelXT-Integrated space-group and crystal-structure determination, *Acta Cryst.*, (2015), **A71**, 3-8.

Sheldrick, G.M., Crystal structure refinement with ShelXL, *Acta Cryst.*, (2015), **C71**, 3-8.

O.V. Dolomanov and L.J. Bourhis and R.J. Gildea and J.A.K. Howard and H. Puschmann, **Olex2**: A complete structure solution, refinement and analysis program, *J. Appl. Cryst.*, (2009), **42**, 339-341.

Fig. S10: Image of the Crystal on the Diffractometer.

Fig. S11: Image of the Crystal on the Diffractometer.

Fig. S12: Image of the Crystal on the Diffractometer.

Data Plots: Diffraction Data

Data Plots: Refinement and Data

Table S13: Fractional Atomic Coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for **ygq-pdtacid**. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} .

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
F1	10123.3(11)	5790(3)	7348.5(7)	35.1(3)
O1	7866.5(15)	6667(3)	6982.7(11)	38.9(4)
O2	7400.0(14)	2586(3)	6886.5(10)	35.3(4)
C1	9463(2)	3609(4)	7139.5(13)	28.7(5)
C2	8156(2)	4442(4)	7004.3(12)	26.9(5)
C3	9636(2)	1690(5)	7776.6(13)	31.6(5)
C4	9064(2)	2327(4)	8506.0(13)	29.0(5)
C5	8151(2)	783(5)	8750.7(14)	36.6(6)
C6	7651(2)	1206(6)	9426.2(15)	44.8(7)
C7	8041(2)	3207(5)	9872.5(15)	42.8(7)
C8	8931(3)	4777(5)	9636.6(14)	43.2(7)
C9	9451(2)	4337(5)	8962.2(14)	37.3(6)
C10	9956(2)	2653(5)	6413.2(15)	39.3(6)
C11	9903(2)	4562(6)	5776.8(15)	47.8(7)
F21	2845.8(11)	5366(3)	6453.4(7)	39.1(4)
O21	5149.1(14)	4326(3)	6602.7(9)	34.4(4)
O22	5672.2(14)	8401(3)	6580.9(10)	39.0(4)
C21	3587(2)	7511(5)	6525.0(13)	31.5(5)
C22	4886(2)	6561(5)	6567.8(12)	28.4(5)
C23	3336(2)	8812(5)	7266.8(13)	34.3(6)
C24	3723(2)	7230(5)	7950.2(13)	31.7(5)
C25	2982(2)	5339(6)	8197.2(13)	40.2(6)
C26	3390(3)	3749(6)	8778.0(15)	50.8(7)
C27	4543(3)	4025(6)	9112.3(14)	49.5(7)
C28	5277(3)	5908(6)	8878.3(14)	46.6(7)
C29	4874(2)	7513(5)	8308.6(13)	39.0(6)
C30	3304(2)	9193(6)	5843.3(14)	40.3(6)
C31	3510(3)	7914(7)	5099.4(15)	58.9(9)

Table S14: Anisotropic Displacement Parameters ($\times 10^4$) for **ygq-pdtacid**. The anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: $-2\pi^2[h^2a^{*2} \times U_{11} + \dots + 2hka^* \times b^* \times U_{12}]$

Atom	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{23}	U_{13}	U_{12}
F1	26.5(6)	28.3(7)	49.5(8)	-3.6(7)	-5.8(6)	-1.7(6)
O1	25.0(9)	27.2(9)	63.0(12)	-5.3(8)	-7.6(7)	3.9(7)
O2	23.5(8)	28.8(9)	51.8(10)	-5.5(8)	-10.0(7)	0.0(7)
C1	23.2(11)	25.0(12)	36.7(12)	-6.6(10)	-5.5(9)	-0.2(9)
C2	26.2(12)	26.2(13)	27.8(12)	-3.3(10)	-2.1(9)	-0.4(11)
C3	26.2(12)	26.2(12)	41.2(13)	-4.0(10)	-5.8(10)	5.4(10)

Atom	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{23}	U_{13}	U_{12}
C4	26.2(11)	24.8(12)	34.3(12)	0.7(10)	-10.7(9)	5.0(10)
C5	38.8(13)	29.0(12)	41.1(14)	-4.4(11)	-4.7(10)	-5.8(12)
C6	43.5(15)	43.6(17)	47.5(15)	-0.1(13)	3.1(12)	-4.4(13)
C7	48.9(16)	43.5(16)	35.3(14)	-2.1(12)	-1.1(12)	11.5(13)
C8	56.4(17)	32.9(14)	38.4(15)	-8.4(11)	-12.4(13)	4.0(13)
C9	39.6(14)	31.2(14)	39.4(14)	-1.6(11)	-8.5(11)	-3.5(12)
C10	32.5(13)	39.4(14)	46.4(15)	-6.3(12)	5.4(11)	5.5(12)
C11	43.7(15)	57.4(18)	42.6(15)	-3.6(13)	5.4(12)	4.3(14)
F21	25.9(7)	48.7(9)	42.2(8)	-6.2(7)	-2.7(5)	-4.1(7)
O21	26.1(8)	34.7(10)	41.8(10)	-6.8(8)	-2.1(7)	3.7(8)
O22	23.4(8)	35.1(10)	57.7(11)	2.3(8)	-2.7(8)	2.5(7)
C21	21.9(11)	37.6(13)	34.4(12)	-1.5(11)	-2.2(9)	2.8(11)
C22	25.4(12)	33.7(13)	25.9(11)	-3.4(10)	1.0(9)	1.4(10)
C23	27.3(12)	41.4(14)	33.5(13)	-0.3(11)	-1.4(9)	9.9(11)
C24	31.4(12)	35.4(14)	28.3(12)	-5.6(10)	1.7(9)	6.6(11)
C25	32.6(12)	53.7(17)	34.8(13)	-2.2(13)	4.8(10)	-3.3(13)
C26	63.2(18)	51.3(18)	39.5(15)	1.7(13)	15.5(14)	-9.1(15)
C27	67.3(19)	49.8(17)	30.7(14)	3.9(13)	-1.3(13)	12.0(16)
C28	49.2(16)	51.1(17)	37.5(14)	-1.0(13)	-12.6(12)	7.8(15)
C29	38.9(14)	39.3(14)	37.7(14)	-5.4(12)	-5.1(11)	-1.9(12)
C30	29.3(12)	54.9(18)	36.0(13)	6.1(13)	-2.6(10)	9.4(13)
C31	51.1(17)	92(3)	33.6(15)	2.7(16)	-0.2(12)	10.4(18)

Table S15: Bond Lengths in Å for **ygq-pdtacid**.

Atom	Atom	Length/Å	Atom	Atom	Length/Å
F1	C1	1.405(3)	F21	C21	1.403(3)
O1	C2	1.224(3)	O21	C22	1.222(3)
O2	C2	1.299(3)	O22	C22	1.306(3)
C1	C2	1.514(3)	C21	C22	1.517(3)
C1	C3	1.525(3)	C21	C23	1.530(3)
C1	C10	1.521(3)	C21	C30	1.520(3)
C3	C4	1.517(3)	C23	C24	1.514(3)
C4	C5	1.392(3)	C24	C25	1.386(4)
C4	C9	1.390(3)	C24	C29	1.390(3)
C5	C6	1.373(4)	C25	C26	1.385(4)
C6	C7	1.377(4)	C26	C27	1.376(4)
C7	C8	1.375(4)	C27	C28	1.370(4)
C8	C9	1.382(4)	C28	C29	1.373(4)
C10	C11	1.516(4)	C30	C31	1.516(4)

Table 116: Bond Angles in ° for **ygq-pdtacid**.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
F1	C1	C2	105.86(17)	C9	C4	C5	118.1(2)
F1	C1	C3	108.55(17)	C6	C5	C4	121.3(2)
F1	C1	C10	106.91(19)	C5	C6	C7	120.0(3)
C2	C1	C3	112.53(19)	C8	C7	C6	119.6(3)
C2	C1	C10	110.78(18)	C7	C8	C9	120.6(2)
C10	C1	C3	111.84(19)	C8	C9	C4	120.4(2)
O1	C2	O2	124.3(2)	C11	C10	C1	114.3(2)
O1	C2	C1	122.1(2)	F21	C21	C22	106.2(2)
O2	C2	C1	113.53(19)	F21	C21	C23	107.84(19)
C4	C3	C1	116.47(19)	F21	C21	C30	108.52(18)
C5	C4	C3	119.2(2)	C22	C21	C23	109.44(17)
C9	C4	C3	122.7(2)	C22	C21	C30	112.20(19)

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C30	C21	C23	112.4(2)	C29	C24	C23	120.5(2)
O21	C22	O22	124.7(2)	C26	C25	C24	120.5(2)
O21	C22	C21	123.1(2)	C27	C26	C25	120.1(3)
O22	C22	C21	112.2(2)	C28	C27	C26	119.8(3)
C24	C23	C21	112.4(2)	C27	C28	C29	120.5(3)
C25	C24	C23	121.0(2)	C28	C29	C24	120.7(3)
C25	C24	C29	118.4(2)	C31	C30	C21	113.3(2)

Table 2: Torsion Angles in ° for *ygq-pdtacid*.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
F1	C1	C2	O1	9.8(3)
F1	C1	C2	O2	-172.77(18)
F1	C1	C3	C4	68.4(2)
F1	C1	C10	C11	-56.6(3)
C1	C3	C4	C5	116.7(2)
C1	C3	C4	C9	-66.3(3)
C2	C1	C3	C4	-48.5(3)
C2	C1	C10	C11	58.3(3)
C3	C1	C2	O1	128.2(2)
C3	C1	C2	O2	-54.3(3)
C3	C1	C10	C11	-175.3(2)
C3	C4	C5	C6	176.5(2)
C3	C4	C9	C8	-177.4(2)
C4	C5	C6	C7	0.8(4)
C5	C4	C9	C8	-0.3(3)
C5	C6	C7	C8	0.2(4)
C6	C7	C8	C9	-1.1(4)
C7	C8	C9	C4	1.2(4)
C9	C4	C5	C6	-0.6(4)
C10	C1	C2	O1	-105.7(3)
C10	C1	C2	O2	71.7(3)
C10	C1	C3	C4	-173.91(19)
F21	C21	C22	O21	-6.2(3)
F21	C21	C22	O22	175.35(18)
F21	C21	C23	C24	65.6(2)
F21	C21	C30	C31	-59.1(3)
C21	C23	C24	C25	-82.3(3)
C21	C23	C24	C29	92.6(3)
C22	C21	C23	C24	-49.4(3)
C22	C21	C30	C31	57.9(3)
C23	C21	C22	O21	110.0(3)
C23	C21	C22	O22	-68.5(3)
C23	C21	C30	C31	-178.2(2)
C23	C24	C25	C26	173.9(2)
C23	C24	C29	C28	-173.2(2)
C24	C25	C26	C27	-0.4(4)
C25	C24	C29	C28	1.9(4)
C25	C26	C27	C28	1.2(4)
C26	C27	C28	C29	-0.5(4)
C27	C28	C29	C24	-1.1(4)
C29	C24	C25	C26	-1.1(4)
C30	C21	C22	O21	-124.6(3)
C30	C21	C22	O22	57.0(3)
C30	C21	C23	C24	-174.8(2)

Table S18: Hydrogen Fractional Atomic Coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for **ygq-pdtacid**. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} .

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
H2	6691	3152.76	6817.74	53
H3A	9300.97	58.73	7590.72	38
H3B	10518.55	1451.15	7892.42	38
H5	7868.64	-590.01	8444.27	44
H6	7035.39	118.18	9585.99	54
H7	7697.82	3500.66	10340.77	51
H8	9190.36	6175.36	9939.61	52
H9	10075.5	5415.28	8809.84	45
H10A	10810.04	2127.87	6520.98	47
H10B	9487.3	1143.42	6242.86	47
H11A	10310.13	3874.54	5348.38	72
H11B	10311.12	6114.58	5951.19	72
H11C	9053.59	4929.07	5619.62	72
H22	6377.14	7813.17	6650.49	58
H23A	3774.06	10439.18	7298.88	41
H23B	2456.46	9173.72	7270.01	41
H25	2186.53	5132.39	7966.23	48
H26	2872.93	2464.72	8945.87	61
H27	4828.23	2913.51	9504.11	59
H28	6071.07	6106.56	9111.71	56
H29	5387.49	8829.54	8157.78	47
H30A	2447.01	9741.61	5838.82	48
H30B	3820.23	10717.07	5892.54	48
H31A	3228.96	9019.4	4681.52	88
H31B	3056.28	6327.76	5065.12	88
H31C	4377.45	7569.2	5070.77	88

Table S19: Hydrogen Bond information for **ygq-pdtacid**.

D	H	A	d(D-H)/Å	d(H-A)/Å	d(D-A)/Å	D-H-A/deg
O2	H2	O21	0.84	1.83	2.668(2)	176.2
C3	H3A	F1 ¹	0.99	2.49	3.277(3)	136.2
C3	H3A	O1 ¹	0.99	2.59	3.543(3)	162.5
O22	H22	O1	0.84	1.81	2.645(2)	169.4

¹+x,-1+y,+z

Submitted by: **Guoqiang Yang**
 Supervisor: **Professor Jieping Zhu**
 Solved by: **Farzaneh Fadaei Tirani**
 Sample ID: **YGQ-435-3**

$R_1 = 3.47\%$

Crystal Data and Experimental of **10c** (CCDC 2109141)

Experimental. Single clear intense yellow irregular-shaped crystals of **ygq-435-3** were used as supplied. A suitable crystal with dimensions $0.13 \times 0.12 \times 0.08 \text{ mm}^3$ was selected and mounted on a XtaLAB Synergy R, DW system, HyPix-Arc 150 diffractometer. The crystal was kept at a steady $T = 140.00(10) \text{ K}$ during data collection. The structure was solved with the **ShelXT** 2018/2 (Sheldrick, 2015) solution program using dual methods and by using **Olex2** 1.5 (Dolomanov et al., 2009) as the graphical interface. The model was refined with **ShelXL** 2018/3 (Sheldrick, 2015) using full matrix least squares minimisation on F^2 .

Crystal Data. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{24}\text{F}_3\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{Pd}$, $M_r = 613.90$, monoclinic, $P2_1/n$ (No. 14), $a = 7.32177(12) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 17.0540(3) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 20.4085(3) \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 99.9799(15)^\circ$, $\alpha = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $V = 2509.76(7) \text{ \AA}^3$, $T = 140.00(10) \text{ K}$, $Z = 4$, $Z' = 1$, $\mu(\text{Cu } K\alpha) = 6.480$, 39837 reflections measured, 5117 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0264$) which were used in all calculations. The final wR_2

was 0.0872 (all data) and R_1 was 0.0347 ($I \geq 2 \sigma(I)$).

Compound	YGQ-435-3
Formula	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{24}\text{F}_3\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{Pd}$
Dcalc	1.625
μ/mm^{-1}	6.480
Formula Weight	613.90
Colour	clear intense yellow
Shape	irregular-shaped
Size/ mm^3	$0.13 \times 0.12 \times 0.08$
T/K	140.00(10)
Crystal System	monoclinic
Space Group	$P2_1/n$
$a/\text{Å}$	7.32177(12)
$b/\text{Å}$	17.0540(3)
$c/\text{Å}$	20.4085(3)
$\alpha/^\circ$	90
$\beta/^\circ$	99.9799(15)
$\gamma/^\circ$	90
$V/\text{Å}^3$	2509.76(7)
Z	4
Z'	1
Wavelength/ Å	1.54184
Radiation type	$\text{Cu}K\alpha$
$\Theta_{\text{min}}/^\circ$	3.399
$\Theta_{\text{max}}/^\circ$	75.613
Measured Refl's.	39837
Indep't Refl's	5117
Refl's $I \geq 2 \sigma(I)$	4772
R_{int}	0.0264
Parameters	454
Restraints	709
Largest Peak/ $e \text{ \AA}^{-3}$	0.728
Deepest Hole/ $e \text{ \AA}^{-3}$	-0.539
GooF	1.073
wR_2 (all data)	0.0872
wR_2	0.0857
R_1 (all data)	0.0374
R_1	0.0347
CCDC number	2109141

Structure Quality Indicators

Reflections:	d min (Cu\α) 2θ=151.2°	0.80	I/σ(I) CIF	58.5	Rint CIF	2.64%	Full 135.4° 98% to 151.2°	100
Refinement:	Shift CIF	0.002	Max Peak CIF	0.7	Min Peak CIF	-0.5	GooF CIF	1.073

A clear intense yellow irregular-shaped crystal with dimensions $0.13 \times 0.12 \times 0.08 \text{ mm}^3$ was mounted. Data were collected using a XtaLAB Synergy R, DW system, HyPix-Arc 150 diffractometer operating at $T = 140.00(10) \text{ K}$.

Data were measured using ω scans with Cu K_{α} radiation. The diffraction pattern was indexed and the total number of runs and images was based on the strategy calculation from the program CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.116a (Rigaku OD, 2021). The maximum resolution achieved was $\theta = 75.613^{\circ}$ ($0.80 \text{ \AA}$).

The unit cell was refined using CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.116a (Rigaku OD, 2021) on 21473 reflections, 54% of the observed reflections.

Data reduction, scaling and absorption corrections were performed using CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.116a (Rigaku OD, 2021). The final completeness is 100.00 % out to 75.613° in θ . A Gaussian absorption correction was performed using CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.116a (Rigaku Oxford Diffraction, 2021) Numerical absorption correction based on Gaussian integration over a multifaceted crystal model. Empirical absorption correction using spherical harmonics as implemented in SCALE3 ABSPACK scaling algorithm. The absorption coefficient μ of this material is 6.480 mm^{-1} at this wavelength ($\lambda = 1.54184 \text{ \AA}$) and the minimum and maximum transmissions are 0.555 and 0.864.

The structure was solved and the space group $P2_1/n$ (# 14) determined by the ShelXT 2018/2 (Sheldrick, 2015) structure solution program using dual methods and refined by full matrix least squares minimisation on F^2 using version 2018/3 of **ShelXL** 2018/3 (Sheldrick, 2015). All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atom positions were calculated geometrically and refined using the riding model.

There is a single molecule in the asymmetric unit, which is represented by the reported sum formula. In other words: Z is 4 and Z' is 1.

Citations

CrysAlisPro Software System, Rigaku Oxford Diffraction, (2021).

Sheldrick, G.M., ShelXT-Integrated space-group and crystal-structure determination, *Acta Cryst.*, (2015), **A71**, 3-8.

Sheldrick, G.M., Crystal structure refinement with ShelXL, *Acta Cryst.*, (2015), **C71**, 3-8.

O.V. Dolomanov and L.J. Bourhis and R.J. Gildea and J.A.K. Howard and H. Puschmann, **Olex2**: A complete structure solution, refinement and analysis program, *J. Appl. Cryst.*, (2009), **42**, 339-341.

Fig. S13: Image of the Crystal on the Diffractometer.

Fig. 14: Image of the Crystal on the Diffractometer.

Data Plots: Diffraction Data

Data Plots: Refinement and Data

Reflection Statistics

Total reflections (after filtering)	40767	Unique reflections	5117
Completeness	0.98	Mean I/σ	37.86
hkl_{max} collected	(9, 21, 25)	hkl_{min} collected	(-8, -20, -24)
hkl_{max} used	(9, 21, 25)	hkl_{min} used	(-9, 0, 0)
Lim d_{max} collected	100.0	Lim d_{min} collected	0.77
d_{max} used	20.1	d_{min} used	0.8
Friedel pairs	4477	Friedel pairs merged	1
Inconsistent equivalents	0	R_{int}	0.0264
R_{sigma}	0.0171	Intensity transformed	0
Omitted reflections	0	Omitted by user (OMIT hkl)	0
Multiplicity	(4961, 4488, 2231, 819, 447, 317, 189, 218, 177, 140, 95, 74, 55, 46, 31, 34, 42, 40, 33, 13, 2)	Maximum multiplicity	36
Removed systematic absences	930	Filtered off (Shel/OMIT)	0

Table S20: Fractional Atomic Coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for **ygq-435-3**. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} .

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
Pd1	6904.3(3)	5509.9(2)	3583.1(2)	32.64(8)
F1A	2700(14)	6469(5)	3459(5)	80(2)
F1B	2280(20)	6379(9)	3241(6)	58(3)
F2A	3243(12)	9169(4)	3961(3)	82(2)
F2B	2370(20)	8872(9)	4073(6)	92(3)
F3A	7831(11)	7870(7)	3056(5)	74(2)
F3B	7660(20)	7950(13)	3279(8)	71(3)
O1	6937(4)	6018.7(14)	6638.6(11)	47.5(6)
O2	10041(3)	2620.9(12)	5220.0(11)	41.7(5)
O3	5203(5)	6940.9(16)	1963.6(13)	67.3(9)
N1	6680(3)	5796.7(14)	4603.8(12)	30.4(5)
N2	7810(3)	4494.1(14)	4071.6(12)	31.6(5)
N3	5969(4)	6451.6(16)	3020.0(13)	42.4(6)
C1	6106(4)	6454.6(18)	4861.1(15)	35.5(6)
C2	6132(4)	6579.8(19)	5535.3(15)	35.9(6)
C3	6797(4)	5983.4(18)	5973.4(15)	34.6(6)
C4	7392(4)	5290.4(17)	5717.6(14)	32.7(6)
C5	7342(4)	5216.5(17)	5042.5(14)	29.4(6)
C6	7985(4)	4500.9(16)	4744.8(14)	29.2(6)
C7	8747(4)	3870.6(17)	5124.7(15)	32.0(6)
C8	9265(4)	3199.1(17)	4813.4(15)	32.5(6)
C9	8983(4)	3170.7(18)	4126.8(16)	36.0(6)
C10	8276(4)	3833.7(18)	3782.7(15)	35.3(6)
C11	6523(6)	6727(2)	6936.8(18)	55.5(9)
C12	10534(6)	1912.1(19)	4914(2)	51.8(9)
C13A	5219(11)	7140(3)	3260(4)	42.7(13)
C18A	6250(9)	7826(4)	3272(4)	53.3(15)
C17A	5592(10)	8517(3)	3506(3)	58.2(17)
C16A	3904(11)	8523(3)	3730(3)	53.0(17)
C15A	2873(10)	7837(4)	3719(3)	54.5(16)
C14A	3531(10)	7145(3)	3484(4)	49.0(14)
C13B	5140(20)	7149(7)	3239(9)	48(2)
C18B	5956(17)	7876(8)	3395(8)	48(2)
C17B	4990(20)	8457(6)	3672(6)	56(2)
C16B	3210(20)	8310(8)	3792(5)	57(2)
C15B	2395(17)	7583(9)	3635(6)	56(2)
C14B	3360(20)	7003(6)	3358(8)	53(2)
C19	5858(6)	6420(2)	2355.7(18)	57.8(10)
C20A	6322(7)	5596(3)	2098(2)	44.5(10)
C20B	7752(18)	5934(7)	2278(6)	56(2)
C21	7460(7)	5162(2)	2698.3(17)	59.2(10)
C22A	4502(9)	5174(4)	1853(4)	75.7(18)
C22B	9700(20)	6288(11)	2472(9)	74(4)
C23A	7535(6)	5707(2)	1577.8(17)	50.3(12)
C24A	9099(6)	6182(2)	1707.9(17)	70.8(14)
C25A	10211(6)	6281(2)	1227(2)	84.7(18)
C26A	9758(7)	5906(3)	615(2)	82.6(18)
C27A	8193(7)	5432(3)	485.3(16)	82.8(18)
C28A	7082(6)	5332(2)	966.5(19)	67.4(13)
C23B	7505(15)	5713(7)	1545(4)	57(2)
C28B	8883(13)	5813(7)	1162(5)	67(2)
C27B	8613(15)	5540(7)	510(5)	69(3)
C26B	6965(17)	5167(7)	242(4)	68(3)
C25B	5587(14)	5067(6)	625(4)	63(3)
C24B	5857(14)	5340(6)	1277(4)	55(2)

Table S21: Anisotropic Displacement Parameters ($\times 10^4$) for **ygq-435-3**. The anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: $-2\pi^2[h^2a^{*2} \times U_{11} + \dots + 2hka^* \times b^* \times U_{12}]$

Atom	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{23}	U_{13}	U_{12}
Pd1	42.50(14)	28.74(12)	28.24(12)	3.67(8)	10.49(9)	2.96(9)
F1A	88(5)	67(3)	100(6)	26(4)	53(4)	-2(3)
F1B	45(4)	83(6)	42(5)	21(4)	-1(3)	-7(4)
F2A	126(5)	60(3)	60(3)	-14(2)	15(3)	40(3)
F2B	137(8)	71(6)	69(5)	-12(5)	21(5)	54(6)
F3A	64(3)	66(3)	94(6)	-9(4)	20(3)	-10(2)
F3B	85(7)	64(6)	63(7)	-10(6)	9(5)	-21(5)
O1	70.8(16)	42.4(13)	30.6(11)	-7.3(9)	12.3(11)	-11.8(11)
O2	55.4(13)	26.8(11)	42.4(12)	4.5(9)	7.3(10)	4.3(9)
O3	119(3)	51.4(16)	36.7(13)	16.8(12)	26.9(14)	34.3(16)
N1	33.8(12)	28.8(12)	28.7(12)	0.6(9)	5.4(9)	-2.5(10)
N2	34.3(12)	30.1(12)	30.4(12)	0.2(9)	5.5(10)	-3.0(10)
N3	64.0(17)	34.6(13)	31.8(13)	7.8(11)	17.5(12)	12.3(13)
C1	37.2(15)	33.2(15)	35.4(15)	0.1(12)	4.8(12)	0.0(12)
C2	38.2(15)	33.5(15)	37.0(15)	-5.1(12)	8.6(12)	-2.3(12)
C3	38.9(15)	34.0(15)	31.8(14)	-3.7(12)	8.2(12)	-11.0(12)
C4	38.8(15)	28.1(14)	30.7(14)	0.6(11)	4.7(11)	-8.4(12)
C5	30.0(13)	27.3(13)	30.8(13)	1.0(11)	4.6(11)	-6.5(11)
C6	29.6(13)	27.4(13)	29.9(13)	0.9(11)	3.4(11)	-6.5(11)
C7	35.4(14)	29.7(14)	30.6(14)	1.2(11)	4.9(11)	-6.2(11)
C8	34.9(14)	25.1(13)	37.6(15)	4.7(11)	6.1(12)	-3.3(11)
C9	40.6(16)	27.2(14)	39.9(16)	-2.6(12)	6.6(13)	-2.0(12)
C10	42.0(16)	31.2(15)	33.2(15)	-2.3(12)	7.6(12)	-1.1(12)
C11	76(3)	51(2)	39.6(18)	-12.7(16)	10.4(17)	-5.6(19)
C12	70(2)	26.4(16)	59(2)	0.4(15)	11.6(18)	4.2(16)
C13A	66(3)	34(2)	28(2)	9(2)	8(2)	16(2)
C18A	72(3)	44(3)	42(3)	-7(2)	4(3)	14(3)
C17A	76(4)	49(3)	46(3)	-10(3)	3(3)	8(3)
C16A	78(4)	46(3)	34(2)	-4(2)	8(3)	26(3)
C15A	84(4)	48(4)	35(3)	3(3)	20(3)	26(3)
C14A	76(3)	40(3)	36(3)	8(2)	23(3)	18(3)
C13B	71(4)	40(4)	33(4)	2(4)	11(4)	13(4)
C18B	69(4)	41(4)	35(4)	-11(3)	7(4)	16(4)
C17B	86(5)	42(4)	37(4)	-15(3)	7(4)	24(4)
C16B	89(5)	41(4)	38(4)	-8(4)	6(4)	25(4)
C15B	81(5)	50(5)	38(4)	6(4)	13(4)	22(4)
C14B	78(4)	53(4)	32(4)	6(4)	18(4)	22(4)
C19	89(3)	49(2)	39.9(18)	11.6(15)	24.8(17)	25.9(19)
C20A	70(3)	33(2)	34(2)	1.0(16)	16.9(19)	5.5(19)
C20B	84(4)	44(4)	43(4)	5(3)	25(4)	11(4)
C21	102(3)	47(2)	33.7(17)	11.3(15)	25.9(18)	28(2)
C22A	77(4)	54(4)	95(5)	-16(3)	13(4)	-3(3)
C22B	69(8)	74(9)	82(9)	18(8)	23(7)	-14(7)
C23A	81(3)	36(2)	39(2)	11.5(19)	26(2)	16(2)
C24A	98(3)	54(3)	68(3)	4(2)	36(3)	11(3)
C25A	114(4)	58(3)	93(4)	16(3)	48(4)	7(3)
C26A	118(4)	67(4)	75(3)	16(3)	51(3)	32(3)
C27A	128(4)	72(3)	54(3)	9(3)	33(3)	38(3)
C28A	106(3)	58(3)	42(2)	4(2)	22(2)	31(3)
C23B	87(4)	43(4)	45(4)	7(4)	26(4)	15(4)
C28B	104(4)	54(4)	53(3)	9(3)	38(4)	24(3)
C27B	108(5)	64(5)	47(4)	14(4)	43(4)	32(4)
C26B	106(6)	57(5)	46(5)	10(4)	27(5)	28(5)
C25B	96(6)	48(5)	46(5)	6(4)	19(5)	15(5)
C24B	85(4)	41(4)	42(4)	2(4)	19(4)	9(4)

Table S22: Bond Lengths in Å for **ygq-435-3**.

Atom	Atom	Length/Å	Atom	Atom	Length/Å
Pd1	N1	2.174(2)	C13A	C14A	1.3900
Pd1	N2	2.051(2)	C18A	C17A	1.3900
Pd1	N3	2.024(3)	C17A	C16A	1.3900
Pd1	C21	2.008(3)	C16A	C15A	1.3900
F1A	C14A	1.302(7)	C15A	C14A	1.3900
F1B	C14B	1.321(12)	C13B	C18B	1.3900
F2A	C16A	1.323(5)	C13B	C14B	1.3900
F2B	C16B	1.324(10)	C18B	C17B	1.3900
F3A	C18A	1.310(7)	C17B	C16B	1.3900
F3B	C18B	1.315(12)	C16B	C15B	1.3900
O1	C3	1.345(4)	C15B	C14B	1.3900
O1	C11	1.409(4)	C19	C20A	1.558(6)
O2	C8	1.349(4)	C19	C20B	1.646(12)
O2	C12	1.435(4)	C20A	C21	1.546(6)
O3	C19	1.236(4)	C20A	C22A	1.521(8)
N1	C1	1.337(4)	C20A	C23A	1.510(5)
N1	C5	1.366(4)	C20B	C21	1.606(12)
N2	C6	1.358(4)	C20B	C22B	1.538(16)
N2	C10	1.343(4)	C20B	C23B	1.523(12)
N3	C13A	1.419(4)	C23A	C24A	1.3900
N3	C13B	1.442(9)	C23A	C28A	1.3900
N3	C19	1.345(4)	C24A	C25A	1.3900
C1	C2	1.389(4)	C25A	C26A	1.3900
C2	C3	1.386(4)	C26A	C27A	1.3900
C3	C4	1.392(4)	C27A	C28A	1.3900
C4	C5	1.378(4)	C23B	C28B	1.3900
C5	C6	1.476(4)	C23B	C24B	1.3900
C6	C7	1.385(4)	C28B	C27B	1.3900
C7	C8	1.394(4)	C27B	C26B	1.3900
C8	C9	1.381(4)	C26B	C25B	1.3900
C9	C10	1.383(4)	C25B	C24B	1.3900
C13A	C18A	1.3900			

Table S23: Bond Angles in ° for **ygq-435-3**.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
N2	Pd1	N1	78.22(9)	O1	C3	C4	116.3(3)
N3	Pd1	N1	106.94(10)	C2	C3	C4	118.6(3)
N3	Pd1	N2	174.53(10)	C5	C4	C3	119.8(3)
C21	Pd1	N1	171.48(14)	N1	C5	C4	122.3(3)
C21	Pd1	N2	95.07(12)	N1	C5	C6	115.6(2)
C21	Pd1	N3	79.95(13)	C4	C5	C6	122.1(3)
C3	O1	C11	119.3(3)	N2	C6	C5	116.3(2)
C8	O2	C12	117.3(3)	N2	C6	C7	121.2(3)
C1	N1	Pd1	130.3(2)	C7	C6	C5	122.5(3)
C1	N1	C5	116.8(3)	C6	C7	C8	119.8(3)
C5	N1	Pd1	112.84(19)	O2	C8	C7	116.0(3)
C6	N2	Pd1	116.79(19)	O2	C8	C9	124.8(3)
C10	N2	Pd1	125.5(2)	C9	C8	C7	119.1(3)
C10	N2	C6	117.7(3)	C8	C9	C10	117.6(3)
C13A	N3	Pd1	125.0(4)	N2	C10	C9	124.3(3)
C13B	N3	Pd1	126.8(8)	C18A	C13A	N3	117.4(5)
C19	N3	Pd1	119.7(2)	C18A	C13A	C14A	120.0
C19	N3	C13A	115.0(4)	C14A	C13A	N3	122.6(5)
C19	N3	C13B	112.9(8)	F3A	C18A	C13A	123.5(6)
N1	C1	C2	124.5(3)	F3A	C18A	C17A	116.5(6)
C3	C2	C1	118.0(3)	C17A	C18A	C13A	120.0
O1	C3	C2	125.1(3)	C18A	C17A	C16A	120.0

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
F2A	C16A	C17A	121.6(5)	C22A	C20A	C21	110.8(4)
F2A	C16A	C15A	118.4(5)	C23A	C20A	C19	108.2(3)
C15A	C16A	C17A	120.0	C23A	C20A	C21	108.4(4)
C16A	C15A	C14A	120.0	C23A	C20A	C22A	114.7(4)
F1A	C14A	C13A	114.7(6)	C21	C20B	C19	99.8(7)
F1A	C14A	C15A	125.3(6)	C22B	C20B	C19	122.5(11)
C15A	C14A	C13A	120.0	C22B	C20B	C21	112.9(10)
C18B	C13B	N3	128.2(10)	C23B	C20B	C19	105.1(9)
C18B	C13B	C14B	120.0	C23B	C20B	C21	108.5(9)
C14B	C13B	N3	111.4(10)	C23B	C20B	C22B	107.2(11)
F3B	C18B	C13B	115.4(12)	C20A	C21	Pd1	113.9(3)
F3B	C18B	C17B	124.6(12)	C20B	C21	Pd1	107.7(5)
C13B	C18B	C17B	120.0	C24A	C23A	C20A	120.3(3)
C16B	C17B	C18B	120.0	C24A	C23A	C28A	120.0
F2B	C16B	C17B	117.9(10)	C28A	C23A	C20A	119.7(3)
F2B	C16B	C15B	122.1(10)	C25A	C24A	C23A	120.0
C17B	C16B	C15B	120.0	C24A	C25A	C26A	120.0
C16B	C15B	C14B	120.0	C27A	C26A	C25A	120.0
F1B	C14B	C13B	131.4(12)	C28A	C27A	C26A	120.0
F1B	C14B	C15B	108.6(12)	C27A	C28A	C23A	120.0
C15B	C14B	C13B	120.0	C28B	C23B	C20B	123.3(8)
O3	C19	N3	124.9(3)	C28B	C23B	C24B	120.0
O3	C19	C20A	120.9(3)	C24B	C23B	C20B	116.5(8)
O3	C19	C20B	122.6(5)	C23B	C28B	C27B	120.0
N3	C19	C20A	113.4(3)	C28B	C27B	C26B	120.0
N3	C19	C20B	102.2(5)	C25B	C26B	C27B	120.0
C21	C20A	C19	106.5(3)	C24B	C25B	C26B	120.0
C22A	C20A	C19	107.9(4)	C25B	C24B	C23B	120.0

Table 24: Torsion Angles in ° for **ygq-435-3**.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
Pd1	N1	C1	C2	-176.0(2)
Pd1	N1	C5	C4	177.6(2)
Pd1	N1	C5	C6	-3.0(3)
Pd1	N2	C6	C5	5.3(3)
Pd1	N2	C6	C7	-174.0(2)
Pd1	N2	C10	C9	176.1(2)
Pd1	N3	C13A	C18A	111.4(4)
Pd1	N3	C13A	C14A	-68.1(6)
Pd1	N3	C13B	C18B	100.7(11)
Pd1	N3	C13B	C14B	-72.4(10)
Pd1	N3	C19	O3	175.3(4)
Pd1	N3	C19	C20A	5.4(5)
Pd1	N3	C19	C20B	-39.2(6)
F2A	C16A	C15A	C14A	-179.5(6)
F2B	C16B	C15B	C14B	-178.1(12)
F3A	C18A	C17A	C16A	178.5(7)
F3B	C18B	C17B	C16B	-178.2(16)
O1	C3	C4	C5	-178.2(3)
O2	C8	C9	C10	-176.0(3)
O3	C19	C20A	C21	168.8(4)
O3	C19	C20A	C22A	-72.2(6)
O3	C19	C20A	C23A	52.4(6)
O3	C19	C20B	C21	-158.3(5)
O3	C19	C20B	C22B	76.4(13)
O3	C19	C20B	C23B	-46.0(10)
N1	C1	C2	C3	-0.1(5)
N1	C5	C6	N2	-1.3(4)

Atom	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
N1	C5	C6	C7	177.9(3)
N2	C6	C7	C8	-3.2(4)
N3	C13A	C18A	F3A	2.1(7)
N3	C13A	C18A	C17A	-179.5(7)
N3	C13A	C14A	F1A	0.4(6)
N3	C13A	C14A	C15A	179.5(7)
N3	C13B	C18B	F3B	5.9(15)
N3	C13B	C18B	C17B	-172.5(16)
N3	C13B	C14B	F1B	-8.1(13)
N3	C13B	C14B	C15B	173.7(14)
N3	C19	C20A	C21	-20.8(5)
N3	C19	C20A	C22A	98.2(5)
N3	C19	C20A	C23A	-137.2(4)
N3	C19	C20B	C21	55.2(7)
N3	C19	C20B	C22B	-70.1(12)
N3	C19	C20B	C23B	167.5(7)
C1	N1	C5	C4	1.2(4)
C1	N1	C5	C6	-179.3(2)
C1	C2	C3	O1	179.0(3)
C1	C2	C3	C4	-0.4(4)
C2	C3	C4	C5	1.2(4)
C3	C4	C5	N1	-1.7(4)
C3	C4	C5	C6	178.9(3)
C4	C5	C6	N2	178.1(3)
C4	C5	C6	C7	-2.7(4)
C5	N1	C1	C2	-0.4(4)
C5	C6	C7	C8	177.6(3)
C6	N2	C10	C9	-2.4(5)
C6	C7	C8	O2	178.3(3)
C6	C7	C8	C9	-0.8(4)
C7	C8	C9	C10	3.1(4)
C8	C9	C10	N2	-1.5(5)
C10	N2	C6	C5	-176.0(3)
C10	N2	C6	C7	4.7(4)
C11	O1	C3	C2	-5.2(5)
C11	O1	C3	C4	174.2(3)
C12	O2	C8	C7	178.0(3)
C12	O2	C8	C9	-2.9(5)
C13A	N3	C19	O3	1.5(7)
C13A	N3	C19	C20A	-168.4(5)
C13A	C18A	C17A	C16A	0.0
C18A	C13A	C14A	F1A	-179.1(7)
C18A	C13A	C14A	C15A	0.0
C18A	C17A	C16A	F2A	179.5(6)
C18A	C17A	C16A	C15A	0.0
C17A	C16A	C15A	C14A	0.0
C16A	C15A	C14A	F1A	179.0(8)
C16A	C15A	C14A	C13A	0.0
C14A	C13A	C18A	F3A	-178.4(8)
C14A	C13A	C18A	C17A	0.0
C13B	N3	C19	O3	3.4(9)
C13B	N3	C19	C20B	148.9(8)
C13B	C18B	C17B	C16B	0.0
C18B	C13B	C14B	F1B	178.2(16)
C18B	C13B	C14B	C15B	0.0
C18B	C17B	C16B	F2B	178.1(12)
C18B	C17B	C16B	C15B	0.0
C17B	C16B	C15B	C14B	0.0
C16B	C15B	C14B	F1B	-178.6(13)
C16B	C15B	C14B	C13B	0.0
C14B	C13B	C18B	F3B	178.4(14)
C14B	C13B	C18B	C17B	0.0

Atom	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C19	N3	C13A	C18A	-75.2(6)
C19	N3	C13A	C14A	105.3(5)
C19	N3	C13B	C18B	-88.1(12)
C19	N3	C13B	C14B	98.9(8)
C19	C20A	C21	Pd1	27.8(5)
C19	C20A	C23A	C24A	50.0(5)
C19	C20A	C23A	C28A	-130.0(4)
C19	C20B	C21	Pd1	-50.9(7)
C19	C20B	C23B	C28B	133.4(8)
C19	C20B	C23B	C24B	-51.6(10)
C20A	C23A	C24A	C25A	180.0(4)
C20A	C23A	C28A	C27A	-180.0(4)
C20B	C23B	C28B	C27B	174.8(11)
C20B	C23B	C24B	C25B	-175.2(11)
C21	C20A	C23A	C24A	-65.1(4)
C21	C20A	C23A	C28A	114.8(4)
C21	C20B	C23B	C28B	-120.6(8)
C21	C20B	C23B	C24B	54.4(10)
C22A	C20A	C21	Pd1	-89.3(5)
C22A	C20A	C23A	C24A	170.5(4)
C22A	C20A	C23A	C28A	-9.5(6)
C22B	C20B	C21	Pd1	80.8(11)
C22B	C20B	C23B	C28B	1.6(14)
C22B	C20B	C23B	C24B	176.6(10)
C23A	C20A	C21	Pd1	144.1(3)
C23A	C24A	C25A	C26A	0.0
C24A	C23A	C28A	C27A	0.0
C24A	C25A	C26A	C27A	0.0
C25A	C26A	C27A	C28A	0.0
C26A	C27A	C28A	C23A	0.0
C28A	C23A	C24A	C25A	0.0
C23B	C20B	C21	Pd1	-160.6(7)
C23B	C28B	C27B	C26B	0.0
C28B	C23B	C24B	C25B	0.0
C28B	C27B	C26B	C25B	0.0
C27B	C26B	C25B	C24B	0.0
C26B	C25B	C24B	C23B	0.0
C24B	C23B	C28B	C27B	0.0

Table S25: Hydrogen Fractional Atomic Coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for **ygq-435-3**. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} .

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
H1	5648.24	6864.73	4562.23	43
H2	5707.78	7059.82	5691.29	43
H4	7830.68	4869.66	6007.64	39
H7	8917.08	3895.95	5596.41	38
H9	9264.73	2712.42	3899.17	43
H10	8108.7	3820.75	3310.67	42
H11A	5239.37	6877.86	6762.79	83
H11B	7364.39	7138.88	6835.26	83
H11C	6678.1	6656.29	7419.86	83
H12A	11455.33	2029.5	4632.68	78
H12B	9425.88	1685.77	4641.41	78
H12C	11055.95	1536.77	5260.12	78
H17A	6296.8	8985.89	3514.18	70
H15A	1719.2	7840.74	3871.6	65
H17B	5554.46	8953.31	3779.43	67
H15B	1178.45	7483.14	3717.09	68

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
H21A	8796.13	5243.94	2693.32	71
H21B	7209.68	4592.39	2647.34	71
H21C	8595.4	4835.22	2761.89	71
H21D	6418.36	4846.24	2459.29	71
H22A	3867.9	5423.64	1443.87	114
H22B	3712.73	5203.43	2194.5	114
H22C	4751.63	4623.42	1763.88	114
H22D	9624.57	6860.63	2435.6	111
H22E	10503.94	6087.83	2171.96	111
H22F	10219.52	6141.74	2930.66	111
H24A	9408.92	6438.24	2125.7	85
H25A	11279.87	6605.74	1315.73	102
H26A	10517.19	5974.36	286.65	99
H27A	7883.57	5175.46	67.54	99
H28A	6012.59	5007.95	877.51	81
H28B	10010	6067.91	1345.22	81
H27B	9554.7	5608.36	248.6	83
H26B	6779.68	4980.35	-202.94	82
H25B	4459.93	4811.88	442.13	75
H24B	4915.19	5271.42	1538.76	66

Table S26: Atomic Occupancies for all atoms that are not fully occupied in **ygq-435-3**.

Atom	Occupancy	Atom	Occupancy	Atom	Occupancy	Atom	Occupancy
F1A	0.659(13)	C18B	0.341(13)	H22B	0.728(4)	C28A	0.728(4)
F1B	0.341(13)	C17B	0.341(13)	H22C	0.728(4)	H28A	0.728(4)
F2A	0.659(13)	H17B	0.341(13)	C22B	0.272(4)	C23B	0.272(4)
F2B	0.341(13)	C16B	0.341(13)	H22D	0.272(4)	C28B	0.272(4)
F3A	0.659(13)	C15B	0.341(13)	H22E	0.272(4)	H28B	0.272(4)
F3B	0.341(13)	H15B	0.341(13)	H22F	0.272(4)	C27B	0.272(4)
C13A	0.659(13)	C14B	0.341(13)	C23A	0.728(4)	H27B	0.272(4)
C18A	0.659(13)	C20A	0.728(4)	C24A	0.728(4)	C26B	0.272(4)
C17A	0.659(13)	C20B	0.272(4)	H24A	0.728(4)	H26B	0.272(4)
H17A	0.659(13)	H21A	0.728(4)	C25A	0.728(4)	C25B	0.272(4)
C16A	0.659(13)	H21B	0.728(4)	H25A	0.728(4)	H25B	0.272(4)
C15A	0.659(13)	H21C	0.272(4)	C26A	0.728(4)	C24B	0.272(4)
H15A	0.659(13)	H21D	0.272(4)	H26A	0.728(4)	H24B	0.272(4)
C14A	0.659(13)	C22A	0.728(4)	C27A	0.728(4)		
C13B	0.341(13)	H22A	0.728(4)	H27A	0.728(4)		

10. NMR Spectra of New Compounds

ygq-2

7.368
7.356
7.352
7.343
7.339
7.337
7.335
7.332
7.318
7.242
7.239
7.236
7.231
7.229
7.224
7.219
7.216
7.210
7.207

— 3.592

— 3.154

— 1.534

**S1, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-2

refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang

— 177.833

— 146.181

— 129.024

— 126.592

— 124.828

— 66.414

— 46.974

— 43.393

— 28.315

**S1, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-31pure
refe_1H_zg CDCl₃

**1a, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-31pure
refe_13C_cpd CDCl₃

**1a, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-1

**S5, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**S5, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-233 p Me
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 56

7.167
7.146
7.135
7.114

**1b, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-233 p Me
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 56

**1b, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-231-1

**1c, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-231-1

**1c, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-4

7.613
7.609
7.595
7.592
7.589
7.579
7.574
7.455
7.453
7.448
7.434
7.431
7.419
7.415
7.367
7.362
7.357
7.353
7.350
7.346
7.340
7.335
7.330
7.317

— 3.126

— 2.717

— 1.588

**1d, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-4

— 177.760

— 145.359

— 140.746

— 138.966

— 128.916

— 127.361

— 127.024

— 126.980

— 126.152

— 59.142

— 46.752

— 33.579

— 26.762

**1d, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-5

**1e, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-5

**1e, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-5

**1e, ^{19}F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl_3)**

— -117.194

ygq-229-12

**1f, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-12

**1f, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-3

7.463
7.460
7.441
7.438
7.161
7.158
7.139
7.137

3.107
2.736

1.517

**1g, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-3

177.284

145.420

131.464

127.501

119.926

59.233

46.706

33.525

26.678

**1g, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-231-3p

1h, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)

ygq-231-3p

1h, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)

ygq-231-3p

**1h, ^{19}F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl_3)**

— -62.333

ygq-229-6

7.227
7.221
7.207
7.201
7.195
7.188
7.077
7.061
7.020
7.001

3.101
2.670
2.342
1.531

**1i, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-6

177.904

146.103

137.873

128.281

126.900

126.463

122.629

59.102

46.828

33.585

26.766

21.661

**1i, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-7

**1j, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**1j, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**1k, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**1k, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**1k, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

— -62.506

ygq-229-8
 7.356
 7.353
 7.339
 7.334
 7.319
 7.314
 7.231
 7.227
 7.219
 7.213
 7.208
 7.201
 7.196
 7.193
 7.188
 7.182
 7.176
 7.172
 7.167
 7.153
 7.149
 7.134
 7.130
 7.049
 7.046
 7.029
 7.026
 7.021
 7.017
 7.001
 6.997

**11, ¹H NMR
 (400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-8
 177.408
 161.960
 159.510
 133.798
 133.670
 127.874
 127.791
 126.649
 126.600
 124.397
 124.363
 115.988
 115.766
 59.179
 44.126
 33.624
 25.461
 25.447

**11, ¹³C NMR
 (100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-8

11, ^{19}F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl_3)

— -114.208

ygq-231-2
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 58

7.423
7.403
7.340
7.320
7.303
7.284
7.264
7.178
7.159
7.140

**1m, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-231-2
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 58

177.095

143.670
133.098
130.771
127.538
127.274
126.729

**1m, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-2

**1n, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-229-2

**1n, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-272
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang

**1q, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-272
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang

**1q, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-272
refe_19F_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 38

**1q, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-241-2

6.845
6.836
6.824
6.799
6.786
6.778

— 3.970

— 3.121

— 2.870

— 1.490

**1p, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-241

refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 / gpt/ gyang 54

176.991

156.886

156.823

154.424

154.360

142.102

142.025

141.948

134.677

134.537

134.396

109.736

109.669

109.567

109.501

62.100

62.067

62.035

59.371

— 46.555

— 33.565

— 26.623

**1p, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

1p, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)

ygq-229-9

7.837
7.833
7.820
7.816
7.813
7.799
7.794
7.753
7.728
7.495
7.491
7.478
7.474
7.471
7.459
7.454
7.442
7.440
7.436
7.423
7.419
7.415
7.410
7.393
7.388

**10, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**10, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-281

**1r, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-281

**1r, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-281

—63.206

**1r, ^{19}F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl_3)**

ygq-284

7.754
7.734
7.729
7.707
7.651
7.630
7.115
7.109
7.093
7.088
6.912
6.906

3.847
3.836
3.832
3.828
3.817

3.097

2.690
2.495
2.478
2.462

1.720
1.703
1.688
1.673
1.656
1.501

**1s, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-284

**1s, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-284

1s, ^{19}F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl_3)

ygg-173
refe_1H_zg CDCl3

7.336
7.334
7.330
7.317
7.315
7.302
7.297
7.292
7.253
7.249
7.244
7.236
7.234
7.232
7.229
7.210
7.207
7.204
7.194
7.189
7.184
7.174
7.171
7.168

3.097
2.648
2.297
2.281
2.278
2.262
2.244
2.226
1.920
1.902
1.886
1.883
1.868
1.864
1.849
1.830
1.492
0.787
0.768
0.750

**1t, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygg-173
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyran 21

**1t, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-210

7.331
7.326
7.313
7.310
7.298
7.293
7.288
7.257
7.253
7.247
7.239
7.235
7.232
7.206
7.202
7.199
7.189
7.184
7.179
7.170
7.167
7.163

3.088
2.644
2.244
2.223
2.211
2.202
2.195
2.185
2.169
1.824
1.808
1.799
1.791
1.782
1.770
1.749
1.503
1.192
1.190
1.173
1.164
1.155
1.150
1.146
1.137
1.134
1.131
1.129
1.120
1.116
1.112
1.095
0.927
0.909
0.891

**1u, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-210

177.632

145.811

128.300

126.084

126.026

58.982

50.386

40.418

33.485

23.966

17.836

14.873

**1u, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

7.317
7.313
7.292
7.220
7.181
7.16
7.13
7.104
7.100
7.098
7.095
7.249
7.245
7.240
7.232
7.230
7.228
7.225
7.216
7.212
7.209
7.199
7.197
7.194
7.189
7.176
4.474
4.468
4.459
4.453
4.443
4.437
4.356
4.350
4.340
4.334
4.325
4.319
3.094
2.632
2.236
2.224
2.204
2.192
1.889
1.877
1.857
1.845
1.825
1.813
1.737
1.722
1.715
1.706
1.700
1.684
1.675
1.660
1.653
1.644
1.638
1.628
1.622
1.532
1.267
1.255
1.252
1.214

**1w, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-263-2
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 opt/ gyang 39

177.004

145.240

128.387

126.243

126.010

84.890

83.257

58.986

50.201

38.287

33.465

31.181

30.988

23.084

20.251

20.196

**1w, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq

1w, ^{19}F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl_3)

— -218.052

ygq-263-3

7.347
7.328
7.309
7.274
7.259
7.241
7.221
7.203
7.185
3.524
3.507
3.490
3.104
2.647
2.269
2.250
2.245
2.235
2.226
2.221
2.207
2.193
2.185
1.850
1.836
1.822
1.817
1.808
1.799
1.793
1.775
1.771
1.754
1.736
1.718
1.700
1.520
1.452
1.437
1.432
1.417
1.413
1.401
1.395
1.379
1.365
1.359
1.350
1.346
1.333
1.329
1.316
1.312
1.299
1.295
1.278
1.179
1.174
1.164
1.156
1.146
1.137
1.120
1.109

**1v, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-263-3

**1v, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-321

**1x, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**1x, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

7.317
7.316
7.315
7.314
7.313
7.312
7.311
7.310
7.309
7.308
7.307
7.306
7.305
7.304
7.303
7.302
7.301
7.299
7.298
7.297
7.296
7.295
7.294
7.293
7.292
7.291
7.290
7.289
7.288
7.287
7.286
7.285
7.284
7.283
7.282
7.281
7.280
7.279
7.278
7.277
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6.000

**1y, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-263-1
refe_13c_cpd CDCl₃ /opt/gyan/38

177.833
161.641
145.251
128.674
128.393
126.975
126.938
126.900
126.863
126.256
126.026
123.284
123.181
122.856
122.532
122.208
120.590
114.541

68.036
58.988
50.241
38.309
33.467
29.736
23.110
20.949

**1y, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**1y, ^{19}F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl_3)**

7.338
7.334
7.330
7.326
7.315
7.310
7.306
7.239
7.235
7.229
7.226
7.217
7.214
7.209
7.204
7.194
7.191
7.188
3.098
2.630
2.245
2.233
2.213
2.201
2.181
2.169
2.084
2.079
2.069
2.057
2.049
2.043
2.040
2.034
2.031
2.024
2.022
2.016
2.009
2.006
1.997
1.994
1.982
1.908
1.897
1.876
1.865
1.844
1.832
1.822
1.557
1.450
1.436
1.424
1.419
1.413
1.410
1.407
1.404
1.393
1.329
1.324
1.318
1.314
1.310
1.303
1.298
1.284
1.273

**1z, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**1z, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

1z, ^{19}F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl_3)

7.288
7.266
7.188
7.186
7.180
7.175
7.160
7.156
7.113
7.110
7.095
7.091
7.077
7.073
7.059
7.055
7.041
7.036
3.090
2.865
2.859
2.835
2.829
2.824
2.799
2.794
2.625
2.610
2.590
2.576
2.504
2.477
2.467
2.462
2.451
2.442
2.432
2.427
2.416
2.316
1.896
1.882
1.877
1.862
1.728
1.725
1.722
1.715
1.711
1.702
1.700
1.689
1.595
1.595
1.429
1.425
1.418
1.414
1.402
1.393
1.383
1.379
1.372
1.368
1.364
1.358
1.354
1.349
1.345
1.337

**1aa, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-330-p

178.630

143.719
142.853

129.968
126.905
126.400
126.201

58.853

50.034

37.805
34.900
33.855
26.776
26.741
25.721

**1aa, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-344new

7.783
7.696

3.497
3.177

1.829

**1ab, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-344new

174.132
168.270

134.062
131.902

123.162

60.708
60.693

34.048
24.907

**1ab, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-332-p

**[D₆]-1a, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-332-p

**[D₆]-1a, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-113

-109.233
-109.248
-109.262
-115.058
-115.072

**6, ^{19}F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl_3)**

ygq-163-2A
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang

7.615
7.310
7.306
7.297
7.292
7.287
7.282
7.276
7.271
7.264
7.248
7.243
7.233
7.229
7.224

3.661
3.418
3.383
3.361
3.325
3.148
3.135
3.112
3.088
3.053

1.590
1.535

3a, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)

ygq-163-2A
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 6

171.345

135.342
130.749
128.272
127.070

98.268
96.384

61.391

43.816

34.447

23.280

3a, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)

ygq-155-3-f

**3a, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-153-b2
refe_1H_zg CDCl₃

**4a, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-153-b2
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 gyang 55

ygq-153-B-Fyqq-155-3-F

7.335
7.334
7.312
7.310
7.307
7.308
7.304
7.297
7.294
7.292
7.289
7.285
7.281
7.272
7.267
7.265
7.263
7.260
7.257
7.251
7.248
6.724
6.719
6.713
6.707
6.704
6.702
6.701
6.687
6.683

**7, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**7, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**7, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

yqq-15-1-1

**S6, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-15-1-1

**S6, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-15-1-1-F

**S6, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-15b
refe_1H_zg CDCl3

7.308
7.305
7.302
7.298
7.289
7.285
7.381
7.369
7.366
7.364
7.360
7.320
7.317
7.313
7.303
7.298
7.293
7.285
7.281
7.276
7.268
7.264
7.260

4.788
4.766
4.668
4.646
4.605
4.583
4.486
4.464

3.523
3.327
3.070

1.704
1.699

**S7, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-15b
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3

172.111
171.667

140.316

140.290

129.186

127.690

126.117

90.188

88.430

66.739

66.134

51.004

50.815

46.894

42.971

18.911

18.856

**S7, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**S7, ^{19}F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl_3)**

ygq-236-2p
refe_1H_zg CDCl_3 /opt/ gyang 52

7.132
7.111
7.103
7.082

3.671
3.368
3.332
3.312
3.277
3.141
3.114
3.078
3.054
3.019
2.320

1.576
1.521

**3b, ^1H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl_3)**

ygg-236-2p
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 52

171.367

136.601
132.184
130.579
128.984

98.294
96.417

61.378

43.460
43.237

34.490

23.182
21.219

**3b, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygg-236-2p
refe_19F_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 56

-153.007

**3b, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-237-1p
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 1

**3c, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-237-1

**3c, ¹³C NMR
(125 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**3c, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-236-2p-a
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang

7.600
7.583
7.580
7.546
7.525
7.453
7.435
7.415
7.355
7.337
7.330
7.318
7.311

3.688
3.471
3.436
3.415
3.379
3.198
3.174
3.163
3.138
3.103

1.632
1.577

**3d, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-236-2p-a
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 /opt/gyang 7

173.227

140.995
139.914
134.458
131.164
128.866
127.321
127.143
126.976

98.270
96.386

61.430

43.568
43.353

34.645

23.279

**3d, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-236-2p-a
refe_19F_cpd CDCl3 /opt/gyang 7

-153.100

**3d, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-237-3p-a
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 30

7.218
7.204
7.197
7.183
6.993
6.971
6.950

3.653
3.397
3.361
3.338
3.302
3.145
3.141
3.104
3.068
3.047
3.011

1.581
1.526

**3e, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-237-3

171.398
163.141
161.193
132.255
132.191
131.104
115.180
115.012
97.993
96.481
61.464
43.098
42.965
34.161
23.154

**3e, ¹³C NMR
(125 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-237-3p-a
refe_19F_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 30

-116.124

-153.840

**3e, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-236-3
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 38

7.281
7.275
7.260
7.198
7.178

3.671
3.414
3.379
3.355
3.320
3.165
3.161
3.111
3.076
3.055
3.019

1.594
1.540

**3f, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-237-3p
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 26

171.158

133.884
133.019
132.087
128.406

98.039
96.153

61.504

43.290
43.070

34.305

23.252

**3f, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-236-3
refe_19F_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 38

-153.767

**3f, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-237-4p-a
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 31

7.426
7.419
7.415
7.403
7.399
7.392
7.129
7.108

3.657
3.387
3.351
3.327
3.292
3.153
3.149
3.081
3.046
3.025
2.989

1.580
1.525

**3g, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-237-4

171.279

134.411

132.479

131.369

121.164

97.776

96.265

61.516

43.309

43.154

34.161

23.189

**3g, ¹³C NMR
(125 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**3g, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**3h, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

yqq-236-4p-a
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 38

**3h, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

yqq-236-4p
refe_19F_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 39

**3h, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-238-1p-a
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 25

7.198
7.179
7.161
7.072
7.050
7.043
7.022

3.672
3.373
3.338
3.317
3.282
3.142
3.114
3.079
3.054
3.019
2.329
1.584
1.529

**3i, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-238-1p-a
refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 25

173.994
137.788
135.203
131.501
128.144
127.796
127.752
98.268
96.387
61.357
43.784
43.622
34.490
23.234
21.523

**3i, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**3i, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

7.245
7.241
7.230
7.227
7.224
7.217
7.204
7.130
7.119

3.668
3.389
3.365
3.350
3.327
3.161
3.089
3.065
3.050
3.026

1.576
1.540

**3j, ¹H NMR
(600 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-238-2

**3j, ¹³C NMR
(150 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-238-2
refe_19F_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 18

**3j, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-238-3
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 18

7.524
7.519
7.507
7.503
7.449
7.433
7.430
7.423
7.404
7.385

3.649
3.496
3.461
3.437
3.401
3.193
3.163
3.153
3.149
3.137
3.102

1.605
1.551

**3k, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-238-3

171.326
136.392
134.209
130.903
130.690
130.477
130.265
127.411
127.384
127.358
127.333
126.981
125.177
123.980
123.953
123.927
123.901
123.374
121.570
97.614
96.358

61.577
43.552
33.716
23.100

**3k, ¹³C NMR
(150 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-238-3
refe_19F_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 18

**3k, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-239-1b

7.284
7.280
7.277
7.264
7.260
7.251
7.245
7.240
7.231
7.226
7.220
7.212
7.207
7.096
7.093
7.078
7.074
7.059
7.055
7.038
7.034
7.030
7.013

3.705
3.344
3.290
3.203
3.199

1.585
1.530

**3l, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-239-1

171.547
162.542
160.911
132.963
132.835
129.009
128.955
123.967
123.943
122.423
122.319
115.471
115.319
97.532
96.276
61.523
36.081
33.963
22.555

**3l, ¹³C NMR
(150 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-239-1b

**3l, ^{19}F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl_3)**

ygq-239-2p

**3m, ^1H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl_3)**

ygq-239-2

ygq-239-2pF

ygq-239-3pp

3n, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)

ygq-239-3

3n, ¹³C NMR
(150 MHz, CDCl₃)

ygq-239-3pp

**3n, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-278-1p

**3q, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-278-1p

171.569
162.997
162.943
161.352
161.297
129.114
129.046
128.978
111.479
111.325
111.292
111.182
111.150
97.119
95.860
61.656
33.805
30.100
29.932
22.297
22.173

**3q, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-278-1-F

**3q, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-249-5c

6.830
6.822
6.808
6.786
6.771
6.764

3.965
3.676
3.351
3.315
3.292
3.256
3.183
3.179
3.027
2.991
2.971
2.935
1.580
1.526

3p, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)

ygq-239-5c

refe_13C_cpd CDCl3 /opt/wang 60

177.885

156.606
156.543
154.146
154.083

135.580
135.440
135.301
130.830
130.742
130.657

114.565
114.498
114.400
114.331

97.807
95.919

61.988
61.956
61.923
61.584

43.130
42.909

34.123

23.185
22.981

3p, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)

ygq-249-5c

**3p, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-239-4pp

ygq-239-4

ygq-239-4paa
refe_19F_cpd CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 54

ygq-290-4

ygq-290-4

ygq-290-2

ygq-290-2

ygq-290-2

ygq-176
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang

7.803
7.297
7.294
7.288
7.282
7.277
7.264
7.260
7.250
7.244
7.237
7.234
7.226
7.218

3.580
3.376
3.340
3.303
3.268
3.116
3.081
3.067
3.045
3.032
2.171
2.134
2.120
2.094
2.067
1.911
1.892
1.874
1.857
1.839
1.821
1.803
1.785
0.991
0.973
0.954

ygq-176
refe_13C_cp CDCl3 /opt/ gyang 18

170.810

135.351
130.699
128.261
127.075

101.611
99.680

61.171

43.134

34.974

30.438

7.910
7.861

ygq-307-1-1

**3u, ¹³C NMR
(150 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-307-1-1

**3u, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

7.386
7.301
7.298
7.294
7.285
7.280
7.271
7.267
7.260
7.254
7.243
7.237
7.232
7.224
7.218
7.215
7.212
4.499
4.484
4.469
4.380
4.366
4.351
3.574
3.382
3.347
3.311
3.275
3.122
3.095
3.086
3.072
3.037
1.860
1.855
1.848
1.843
1.826
1.821
1.814
1.808
1.749
1.746
1.730
1.715
1.712
1.702
1.697
1.684
1.667
1.651
1.642
1.637
1.631
1.625
1.613
1.609
1.596
1.585
1.578
1.509
1.497
1.494
1.487
1.481
1.476
1.465
1.458
1.446

**3w, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-307-3-1

171.029

135.075
130.664
128.301
127.166

100.721
99.449
84.452
83.363

61.254

43.271
36.500
33.986
30.511
30.380

19.503
19.473
19.441

**3w, ¹³C NMR
(150 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**3w, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-307-3-1
 refer to CDCl₃ (ppm) Yang

**3v, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-307-4-1

**3v, ¹³C NMR
(150 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**3v, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

7.283
7.282
7.280
7.281
7.276
7.271
7.267
7.260
7.258
7.253
7.250
7.246
7.236
7.230
7.220
7.216
7.211
3.565
3.373
3.368
3.354
3.352
3.338
3.308
3.300
3.265
3.118
3.083
3.069
3.031
1.870
1.852
1.847
1.841
1.835
1.817
1.811
1.806
1.622
1.618
1.614
1.612
1.607
1.597
1.591
1.580
1.575
1.569
1.565
1.559
1.550
1.549
1.545
1.536
1.534
1.523
1.515
1.445
1.442
1.431
1.428
1.425
1.422
1.416
1.413
1.410
1.401
1.397
1.380

**3x, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

0.0 9.5 9.0 8.5 8.0 7.5 7.0 6.5 6.0 5.5 5.0 4.5 4.0 3.5 3.0 2.5 2.0 1.5 1.0 0.5 0.1
f1 (ppm)

ygq-326

**3x, ¹³C NMR
(200 MHz, CDCl₃)**

200 190 180 170 160 150 140 130 120 110 100 90 80 70 60 50 40 30 20 10 0
f1 (ppm)

**3x, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

**3y, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-307-5-1

ygq-307-5-1

7.335
7.308
7.308
7.308
7.300
7.294
7.289
7.287
7.280
7.276
7.270
7.266
7.260
7.254
7.236
7.227
7.224
7.221
7.207
7.204
7.201
3.590
3.387
3.352
3.319
3.283
3.117
3.101
3.082
3.067
3.052
3.032
2.143
2.123
2.116
2.104
2.096
2.089
2.076
2.069
2.061
2.050
2.042
2.042
1.846
1.842
1.832
1.816
1.812
1.800
1.771
1.765
1.759
1.747
1.740
1.732
1.727
1.719
1.712
1.699
1.692
1.678
1.669
1.662
1.657
1.650
1.637
1.629
1.623
1.609

**3z, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-338-p

**3z, ¹³C NMR
(150 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-338

3z, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)

3aa, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)

ygq-339-p

**3aa, ¹³C NMR
(150 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-seven

**3aa, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-354

7.872
7.864
7.858
7.851
7.737
7.729
7.723
7.716

4.303
4.267
4.257
4.241
4.221
4.205
4.169
— 3.723

— 3.240

— 1.668
— 1.612

**3ab, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-354-2-13C

170.345
168.075

134.142
131.901

123.495

95.960
94.685

— 61.711

42.873
42.705

— 33.669

21.735
21.580

**3ab, ¹³C NMR
(150 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-354

**3ab, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-340-p1

7.315
7.310
7.307
7.300
7.294
7.287
7.281
7.276
7.270
7.265
7.260
7.248
7.245
7.241
7.233
7.229
7.225
7.221

**[D₅]-3a, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-340-p1

ygq-349new

**14, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-349new

**14, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)**

ygq-375
refe_1H_zg CDCl3 /opt/ gyang

15, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CDCl₃)

15, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CDCl₃)

ygq-375

15, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CDCl₃)

ygq-424

ygq-424

**10a, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CD₂Cl₂)**

ygq-440

**10c, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CD₂Cl₂)**

ygq-440

ygq-440-3

ygq-428
refe_1H_zg CD2Cl2 /opt

8.511
8.496
8.462
8.057
8.047
8.042
7.673
7.670
7.655
7.652
7.649
7.562
7.556
7.546
7.541
7.296
7.291
7.287
7.282
7.277
7.269
7.265
7.253
7.249
7.166
7.163
7.160
7.149
7.145
7.140
7.130
7.126
7.123
6.867
6.852
6.817
6.812
6.810
6.805
6.794
6.789
6.787
6.782
6.773
6.769
6.764
6.760
6.751
6.746
6.743
6.739
6.728
6.723
6.721
6.716
6.716
2.529
2.427
2.407
1.604

**10b, ¹H NMR
(400 MHz, CD₂Cl₂)**

ygq-428
refe_13C

188.132
165.137
161.987
160.205
160.125
160.060
160.074
160.016
160.069
158.869
158.693
158.620
158.152
158.067
158.025
158.008
157.918
157.879
157.731
156.154
154.249
149.881
149.807
149.201
147.508
147.224
128.220
127.495
127.312
126.731
125.821
123.802
123.186
101.016
100.978
100.912
100.879
100.759
100.721
100.660
100.622
100.501
100.465
100.403
100.365
52.649
38.119
28.544

**10b, ¹³C NMR
(100 MHz, CD₂Cl₂)**

ygq-426

-114.017
-114.029
-114.037
-114.047
-114.365
-114.376
-114.387
-115.790
-115.800
-115.808
-115.818

**10b, ¹⁹F NMR
(377 MHz, CD₂Cl₂)**

